

**AN INVESTIGATION OF FACTORS AFFECTING THE PERFORMANCE OF
QUICK SERVICE RESTAURANTS, A CASE STUDY OF SUBWAY FRANCHISE IN
LONDON, UNITED KINGDOM**

BY

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**A THESIS SUBMITTED IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THEREQUIREMENTS
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ABSTRACT

Reviewing the literature in this field, the researcher has noticed that there is insufficient or missing information about factors affecting the performance of Subway franchise as a Quick Service Restaurant. After the first initial research it was found that there is many studies on the bigger competitors like McDonalds and Starbucks but very little on Subway and the researcher could not find any published doctoral thesis on this topic as well. This study aims to fill the gap in that area by identifying the most important factors affecting the performance of Subway in London by conducting a conclusive research and with the help of quantitative data collection method. As of 2019 this study is possibly within the very few(if not the first) in-depth doctoral thesis focusing on the performance of Subway within the Quick Service Restaurants industry. Performance in the eye of the researcher is defined based on the ranking of fast-food restaurants published by the QSR magazine which is the most respected publisher in this industry.

Objective: Subway's vision statement since 1974 has been to "Be the #1 Quick Service Restaurant (QSR) franchise in the world while delivering fresh, delicious sandwiches and an exceptional experience." However, after years of efforts by the company to achieve this vision, according to the QSR magazine published in August 2016, Subway is #3 after McDonalds and Starbucks respectively. In response to this problem, the main purpose of this research is to examine factors affecting the performance of Subway in the QSR and provide possible recommendations to how Subway could place itself as the #1 QSR franchise in the world. This study aims to investigate to what extent does Consumer Preference, Health Issues, Internal and External Pressures, and Employee Turnover affect the performance of Subway in London, United Kingdom.

Methods: This study contains of both primary and secondary data collection. Surveys and questionnaires were designed and conducted to collect the primary data and the secondary data was collected from company reports, articles, books, and other reliable online sources. The use of these two methods of data collection enhances the reliability of this research. Tertiary sources were not used in this study as there is a high risk that the data might either be wrong or misinterpreted. Surveys was used to collect the quantitative data and all the questions are in accordance with the literature review of this study.

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Contents

Table of Figures	11
List of Tables.....	12
Chapter 1: Background and Introduction	13
Introduction:.....	13
Lodging Services.....	14
Travel and Tourism Services	14
Food and Beverage Services	15
The full-service restaurant.....	15
The speciality restaurant.....	15
Definition of Fast-food.....	16
An introduction to QSR	17
Performance and QSR.....	18
QSR Rankings	21
QSR market in the UK	22
Key consumer trends	23
Franchising	23
Franchise and the business development	24
Benefits of franchising	27
Franchising in the United Kingdom.....	29
Subway.....	30
More about Subway.....	31
Problem Statement.....	33
Research Questions and Objectives	34
Main Research Question.....	34
Research Aim	34
Conceptual Framework	35
Justification	35
Hypotheses	36
LITERATURE REVIEW	36
Consumer Preference	37
Past research.....	39
Experimental research.....	44
Geography and the Economics	46

Sociology and anthropology	47
Health Issues	52
Calorie	56
Customer behaviour	58
Analytic Model	59
Hospitality and its Customer Behaviour	60
Maslow's Hierarchy of needs.....	61
Physiological Needs.....	62
Safety Needs	63
Social Needs	63
Esteem Need	64
Self-Actualization Needs	64
Calorie Labelling and its Implications	64
Labelling in the QSR	65
Health Claims and Food Decisions	68
Regulating Factors.....	69
Internal and External Pressures	70
Labour	70
The Minimum Wage.....	71
The Rise in Earnings	72
The Plateau in Productivity	73
Social Policy and Labour Supply.....	73
Work vs. Welfare	74
Where Are We?.....	74
Where Do We Go from Here?.....	75
Changed Materials	76
Political/legal.....	76
Economic.....	78
Technological	79
Socio-cultural	80
Environmental.....	81
Urban Systems	82
Stakeholders	82
Customer Tastes	83
Corporate Management	83

Objectives of Corporate Management Accountability	84
Competition	84
Porter's Five Forces.....	85
Competitive Rivalry.....	85
Threat of New Entrants.....	86
Threat of Substitutions	86
Power of Buyers	86
Power of Suppliers.....	87
Competitive Positioning.....	88
Marketing Planning.....	88
Value Chain	93
VRIO Analysis	95
Porter's Generic Strategy.....	96
Employee Turnover.....	97
Tangible Cost Factors.....	99
Intangible Cost Factors	100
UK Restaurants.....	100
Satisfaction and Retention Relationship.....	103
Justification for Job Satisfaction Research in the QSR.....	104
Herzberg Two-Factor Theory	104
Basic Concepts and Modifications	104
Assessment of Two-Factor Theory.....	107
Equity Theory	109
Methods of Reducing Inequity.....	110
Dissatisfaction Resulting from Inequity	113
Summary of Pritchard's (1969) Extensions	113
Assessment of Equity Theory.....	114
Instrumentality Expectancy Theories	115
Basic Concepts and Modification.....	115
Vroom's (1964) Model	115
The Lawler and Porter (1967a, 196 7b) Models	118
Comparison of Various Expectancy Models	120
Assessment of Expectancy Theory.....	122
Cornell Studies of Satisfactions.....	123
Basic Concepts	123

Descriptive and Evaluative Measures	125
Assessment of Cornell Studies	126
Need Fulfilment Theory	126
Basic Concepts and Modification	126
Maslow's (1943) Need Hierarchy Theory.....	127
Alderfer's (1969) E.R.G. Theory.....	129
Work Adjustment.....	132
Assessment of Need Fulfilment Theory.....	134
Hofstede Cultural Model.....	135
Hofstede model of national culture.....	135
Power Distance Index	136
Hierarchy Within the Organisation	136
Organizational Decision-Making	136
Compensation Bands	136
Power Delegation.....	136
Leadership.....	137
Supervisory Staff	137
Individualism VS. Collectivism.....	137
Time	138
Challenging Tasks	138
Individual Accomplishments	138
Work-life VS. Social life	138
Creativity.....	138
Merit	139
Masculinity VS. Femininity.....	139
Egoism	139
Motivation Factors.....	139
Gender Role Differentiation.....	139
Uncertainty Avoidance Index.....	140
Open to change.....	140
Risk Taking.....	140
Flexibility	140
Job Satisfaction Survey	140
RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	144
Introduction	144

Research Philosophy	144
Research Approach	146
Rationale	147
Research Methods	147
Data Collection Techniques	148
Research Design	149
Data Collection.....	149
Sample Size	150
Researcher’s Bias	151
Access and ethical issues	151
Chapter : DATA ANALYSIS.....	153
Internal Factors	153
Target population	153
Role of the Researcher.....	153
Correlation Coefficient.....	154
Positive Correlation.....	154
Negative Correlation	154
The Pearson Coefficient	155
Multiple linear regression	155
Demographic questions	156
Second Survey	173
Generalizations	173
Data Analysis.....	174
Limitations	174
Ethical Considerations.....	174
Results of the survey.....	175
The Demographics	176
Consumer preferences.....	176
Selecting the restaurant.....	178
Customer Satisfaction	178
Improvement Implications.....	180
RECOMMENDATIONS.....	182
Reducing Turnover	184
Legal Factors	188
Business Climate	188

Internal pressures	188
Recommendations for Future Research	189
Covid-19 and future pandemics.....	189
CONCLUSION	191
REFERENCES	194

Table of Figures

Figure 1 Subway and McDonalds stores globally (McDonalds and Subway 2019).....	18
Figure 2 Food Attitudes and Behaviours Study BSG (2017)	21
Figure 3 Age demographics of fast-food consumption (MCA 2019).....	22
Figure 4 Cognitive Consumer Behaviour Model (Hall, 2016)	59
Figure 5 Maslow’s Hierarchy of needs (Research History, 2012)	61
Figure 6 Porter’s Five Forces – Fast-food Industry	87
Figure 7 The Boston Consulting Group matrix	89
Figure 8 The Subway company’s position in the Mckinsey matrix (Mckinsey, 2009)	91
Figure 9 Standardising global marketing strategy	94
Figure 10 VRIO model	95
Figure 11 Number of enterprises by employment size (IFF Research, 2019)	101
Figure 12 Number of enterprises by turnover (IFF Research, 2019)	102
Figure 13 Labour productivity in the Food and Beverage Services division, 1997-2019 (IFF research, 2019).....	102
Figure 14 Theoretical Model: Herzberg’s Motivation-Hygiene Theory.....	109
Figure 15: Hofstede cultural dimensions.....	135
Figure 16 Sample Size Calculation.....	150
Figure 17 Gender distribution.....	158
Figure 18 The percentage of participant’s age.....	160
Figure 19 The percentage of participant’s education background.....	162
Figure 20 The percentage of participant’s job position	164
Figure 21 The percentage of participant’s job classification	165
Figure 22 The percentage of participant’s years of service	166
Figure 23 Frequency of participant’s visit	176
Figure 24 Overall satisfaction and perceived value of the participants	178
Figure 25 Satisfaction degree of the participants.....	180

List of Tables

Table 1 Top 10 brands ranked by QSR (QSR magazine, 2017)	33
Table 2 Consumer research on Food service industry	51
Table 3 VRIO analysis on Subway	95
Table 4 TOWS Analysis	96
Table 5 Research philosophies (Saunders et al., 2016, p. 129).....	145
Table 6 IRS Data analysis.....	157
Table 7 Participant's age.....	159
Table 8 The participant's education background.....	161
Table 9 The participant's job position	163
Table 10 The participant's job classification	165
Table 11 The participant's years of service	167
Table 12 The Descriptive Statistics	169
Table 13 The correlation coefficient (satisfaction and turnover).....	170
Table 14 The correlation coefficient (dissatisfaction and turnover)	172
Table 15 The multiple regression (satisfaction and turnover)	174
Table 16 The multiple regression (individual satisfaction factors and turnover)	174
Table 17 The multiple regression with Linear Combination (dissatisfaction and turnover)	175
Table 18 The multiple regression (individual dissatisfaction factors and turnover).....	175
Table 19 Gender, age, and occupation of the participants	178
Table 20 Reasons for visiting fast-food outlets	180
Table 21 Linkert scale questions of perceived value by the participants.....	181
Table 22 Implication for improvement by the participants.....	183

Chapter 1: Background and Introduction

Introduction:

“Hospitality industry is defined as products and services offered to the consumer away from home. It encompasses food and beverage services, lodging services, tourism and travel services and other related services” (QSR, 2008).

The history of hospitality industry goes back to some 12,000 years. With the establishment of money at some time in the sixth century B. C. came the first impetus for people to trade and travel. Early inns became available for the traveller’s needs for lodging. At the beginning, these inns were nothing more than small parts of private dwellings. There was little change for several hundred years. Not until the Industrial Revolution occurred in England were their signs of progress in the business of inn keeping. This business, later the hotel and restaurant business paralleled the growth of trade, travel, and industry. Development of different travel modes has been a determinant in the growth of the hospitality industry.

As each new form of transportation brought down the cost of travel and increased its convenience the steamship, the railroad, and the automobile travel became possible for those other than the elite. “The commercial jet airplane in 1959 ushered in the era of international air travel. All these inventions contributed to the development of services provided to travellers away from home, namely, the hospitality industry” (Nykiel, 1983).

“The hospitality industry encompasses many segments. To gain a better understanding of what the hospitality industry is, it was important to understand several definitions, explanations, and classifications. A brief review of the history of hospitality industry was also included.

Nykiel (1983) defined the hospitality industry as products and services offered to the consumer away from home. It encompasses travel, lodging, eating, entertainment, recreation, and gaming. Each component of the industry is very complex unto itself, and often interrelates either vertically or horizontally with other components” (Nykiel, 1983).

Lundberg (1984) explained “what the field of hotel and restaurant administration is: It is an area of work and study that applies principles and information from several disciplines to the problems of selling food, beverage, and lodging to persons away from home A closely related extension of the field of serving the public is the area covered by food service in institutions: food served in schools, colleges, hospitals, and industry” (Lundberg, 1984). The management

of city and country clubs is also within the purview of the broader field of hotel and restaurant management.

In addition, Nenemeier (1982) classified the hospitality industry into three broad categories:

- 1- Lodging services
- 2- Travel and tourism services
- 1- Food and beverage services

Lodging Services

The hotel, motel, motor hotel, inn, resort, and so forth, represent one segment of the industry. Facilities in this category all offer sleeping accommodations to people, generally transient, with permanent residences elsewhere. Many lodging properties also offer food and/or beverage services which is the second component of the industry.

There are four major classifications of this lodging segment of the industry today: 1) the commercial or transient hotel which focuses its market primarily on individuals traveling for business reasons.

Some examples of this type of lodging services includes the 1) Hilton and Marriott; 2) the resort hotel; usually located at a vacation spot such as at the shore or in the mountains; 3) the residential hotel, essentially, apartment buildings offering maid service, a dining room, room meal service and so forth; and 4) the motel-motor hotel, which has free parking and targets family travellers.

Travel and Tourism Services Travel agencies, transportation businesses and governmental and other agencies promoting travel are examples of enterprises in the tourism segment of the hospitality industry. Airline food and beverage services and those for the motoring public along highway routes address the travelling market specifically (Nenemeier, 1982). depicts the tourism system. It is a common opinion that businesses of any type that provide services to the travelling public, obviously including food and business operations, are an integral part of the travel and tourism segment.

Thus, the many types of commercial food and beverage services already referred to are again an important element of this segment.

Food and Beverage Services

Food and beverage operations in hotels, clubs, and restaurants are examples of the commercial, for profit, part of this segment of the hospitality industry. Food services in schools, nursing homes, hospitals, and military services suggest the wide variety of operations in the institutional, not-for-profit, category of food and beverage services. This segment of the industry is the third largest of all businesses. One of every three meals eaten is eaten away from home.

One problem with describing the restaurant business is that it changes so fast that today's description is liable to be outdated tomorrow. Moreover, restaurants take such various forms that it is almost impossible to suggest a model to fit all operations. However, the basic terminology is still needed.

The full-service restaurant:

A traditional full-service restaurant offers a wide variety of menu choices, waitresses or waiter's service, and food prepared primarily from raw or fresh ingredients. There are three kinds of full-service restaurants:

1. Independent luxury restaurants-restaurants which emphasize exquisitely prepared, sophisticated menu items, usually requiring highly skilled chefs. Prices are quite expensive.
2. Lower-priced restaurants-restaurants with simple and inexpensive menu, usually prepared from fresh or raw ingredients and served by waitresses. These operations are sometimes called Mom and Pop restaurants.
3. Cafeteria-restaurants produce a large quantity of food in limited menu items. They use semi-skilled cooks who follow recipes exactly, weighing and measuring each ingredient.

The speciality restaurant:

All the specialty operations tend to simplify their production processes. They incorporate a large element of self service in order to reduce the labour cost. Because the specialty restaurant requires less labour, the savings would mean lower cost for the guests. Although not all specialty restaurants are affiliated with chains or franchise groups, most of them are. All the specialty restaurants are modelled on one pattern-fast-food concept.

Definition of Fast-food

1. "Donald E. Lundberg in his book *The Hotel & Restaurant Business*" offered the following definition: "Fast-food means quick service-the food already prepared and held, limited menu items, and no table service"
2. Eric F. Green in his book "Profitable food and beverage management planning" mentioned that "Fast-food restaurants are low price, quick service, and convenient"
3. "Lynn W. Robbins and Thomas P. has defined fast-food restaurants as Eating establishments that utilize standard food preparation, service, equipment, management systems, and labour-saving techniques in providing a limited food menu".
4. Dewey A. Dyer in "So You Want to Start a Restaurant?" "Defined the fast-food restaurants are "Restaurants in this groups ordinarily specialize in a very limited menu, relatively inexpensively priced. They are situated in convenient location".

With above definitions, characteristics of the fast-food can be summarised as follows:

1. Limited menu products.
2. Low price Items.
3. Established in convenient location.
4. Quick, limited, and standardized service.

Fast-food restaurants have become a major market for eating-out, because of low price, quick service, and convenience. Fast-food restaurants are probably the fastest growing foodservice operations in terms of both sales and numbers of units. From 2001-2011, the market share for food was 30% and the real growth was 2.9%. The customer count of fast-food reached 40% of the take-away and foods consumed outside of home. This meant QSR's served two of five meals eaten away from home. While full-service units accounted for 27.6%.

According to a survey by NRA, more than 200 foodservice representatives were asked, "Which foodservice area will be the most Important in the 1990s?" QSR's were chosen by 26% of the participants. Family restaurants came in second. According to a research projected by the Food Marketing Institute, 76% of the take-out food were carried away from fast-food units, compared with 30% from supermarkets and 29% from independent deli restaurants. A report which analysed sales and unit trends by menu and service types was conducted by Restaurants Hospitality magazine. More than two thirds of the Top 100's total sales went to quick-service restaurants. The quick-service segment alone among the Top 100 chains accounted for 70% of the group's total units.

An introduction to QSR

QSR or quick service restaurants, also generally known as fast-food restaurants are characterized by its cuisines and minimal table service. Foods in this type of restaurants are normally limited and they are cooked in bulk in advance, these foods are then packaged and ready to order by franchisees. Quick service outlets are usually operated in a franchise, which provide these outlets with ingredients, supplies and guidelines about how to operate.

“The term fast-food was introduced by Merriam Webster in 1951 Human Resource Management Refers to the Policies, practices and systems that influence employee’s behaviour, attitude and performance, it plays an active role in attracting, Motivating, Rewarding and Retaining Employees”(Webster, 1951).

McDonalds and Subway are the two most popular examples of these types of restaurants.

Quick service restaurants are expanding fast because they use franchise models, and this allows them to open stores in large areas and the cost of starting each restaurant is normally shared between the franchisor and the franchisee. Some QSR like Uncle Sam’s is still operating under traditional business models with quite a few stores in the US that are not franchised. Nando’s is also another example that is not using a franchise model but operates as a company owned restaurant in the UK.

However, most of the quick service restaurants across the globe are using a franchise model

Redacted due to copyright restrictions.

**Figure 1: Subway and McDonalds stores globally
(McDonalds and Subway 2019)**

Figure 1

Performance and QSR

Today QSR is a huge industry and growing fast across the globe. The most popular chains like McDonald's and Subway are well known within this industry and operate in many countries. Based on a research in the US, on average Americans spend more money for fast-food than their education, cars, PC's, music, and movies combined (Schlosser, 2001).

Additionally, QSR's play an important role in the growth of economy of the nations they operate in. Moreover, they provide many employment opportunities, and contribution to the government revenues.

Eventually, different studies expose the value that fast-food sector holds within the global economic climate as well as individuals' eating choices.

Organisations are constantly searching for means of holding on to their current consumers and in addition find ways to draw in new ones while staying within their profit as well as being competitive in the market. Today customers have more selections than ever before; they are a lot more versatile in their choices and are always seeking new choices and offers.

With the purpose of developing a lucrative and long-lasting connection with consumers, it is essential for the administration of firms to recognize the qualities that consumers view as important and perceive vital in order to decide (Walter, 2011).

QSR's run in an extremely competitive and vibrant atmosphere. For that reason, to be able to endure, it is necessary to gain competitive advantage over other competitors has a long-term success. Thus, the increasing rate in the QSR sector, performance has been deemed a standard that would certainly affect its success. In order to boost company performance, the organization must start with improving its staff members' performance. This is vital particularly in the QSR market where employees are a significant asset to the survival of the business. In order to make the staff members completely contributed to the business, the organisation needs to constantly guarantee that they are associated with the task given to them. When workers involvement in high in a company, they would certainly go the extra way to carry out or execute their task better than workers who are simply trying to get the job done. Therefore, job involvement might affect the organizational results (Talatand Ishfaq, 2011).

Involved employees are described as the degree to which a job is the main source of interest in their life. It is known to be a significant resource of an industrial requirements as well as satisfaction. (Dubin, 1968), Like Lawler and Hall (1976), who specified that a person that is completely associated with his/her task, he or she would deal with the work as an incredibly vital part of his/her life. Simply put, individuals who have a high degree of work involvement in the workplace will perform much better and create greater work result.

A lot of the firms think that if workers are satisfied with their job, it will certainly create a greater level of task participation. Typically, to have staff members pleased with the work, the company will certainly need to be concerned about their well-being like their psychological needs. Unquestionably, numerous aspects are influencing the staff members' involving more in their job, where one of the basic aspects are characteristic of the job, training, and motivation.

How an organization treats its workers would certainly influence the staff members' perspectives about their work and the company itself. This declaration signifies that how the business treats its workers would certainly influence to what extent these employees are willing to get involved in their job (Shore, Tetrick and Wayne, 1999).

Blau and Boal (1999) concluded that “staff members' work involvement has a high connection with their performance. Once more, this plainly confirmed that highly involved employees can bring huge contribution to organizational success as well as performance” (Blau and Boal, 1999).

Consequently, no matter the kind of organization, worker's involvement in their job is one of the top issues for companies. Presently, QSR is rising greatly, and it is expanding all over the globe. Therefore, researching about the aspects impacting the involvement of employees in the workforce grow into a main issue amongst all the brands in QSR industry. Because this involvement influences the worker's initiatives as well as the company's performance, this study partly focuses on researching about the aspects influencing worker's involvement in the workplace.

With the growing consumer needs and wants, the rivalry within this industry becomes more difficult. In addition, numerous research concluded that the QSR market has a very high failure rate amongst other similar businesses in the hospitality sector. “Parsa (2011) mentions that inadequate performance, as well as high rate of failure within this sector, are as a result of misunderstanding that the organisations have about the customer's needs and wants” (Parsa et alia, 2011).

These issues have been very well known within this industry and are the main concern amongst the franchises. Consumers anticipate getting adequate value from their purchases and they demand to have their needs fulfilled. Failing to do this would have an unwanted consequence, like decrease in customer satisfaction, which may result in losing the customers and thus affecting the business profitability.

“Numerous international fast-food companies have customized their food selection to match the local nutritional preferences. As an example, vegetarian hamburgers are offered on food selections in India, pork is not offered in Muslim nations, instead halal food is supplied to customers, salmon sandwiches appear on menus in Norway” (Smith, 2011 and Lodha, 2014).

But, “challengers of fast food are worried about its dietary shortcomings while others criticize it for 'destroying local culinary value's (Smith, 2013)”. Additionally,

“Overconsumption of fast-food can cause a higher threat of chronic illness. Nonetheless, fast-food on its own is not the only cause for this illness” (Keller, 2008).

Based on a research by Johansen (2012), “this sector generally offers high-quality products safe for usage. In addition, the author takes into consideration the QSR market as huge industry that creates millions of jobs and helps boost the economy of nations”(Johansen, 2012).

QSR Rankings

According to the 2017 Food Attitudes and Behaviours Study by Benenson Strategy Group (BSG), "they looked at how significant QSR chains ranked in terms of importance to diners, such as trust and concerns apart from revenues. Subway placed as one of the most trustworthy of the QSRs studied, with 60% of consumers indicating they trust the brand name, while Chick-fil-A ranked 2nd with 59%, and Wendy's was 3rd with 55%.

McDonald, Subway and chick-fil-'s were the top-three ranked in terms of "caring about more than earnings," as well as Chick-fil-A, Subway and Dunkin Donuts rated highest for caring about customers."

Redacted due to copyright restrictions.

Figure 2: Food Attitudes and Behaviours Study

BSG (2017)

Figure 2

QSR market in the UK

QSR's market in the United Kingdom is one of the fast-growing industries with revenue of £18 billion and an annual growth of 2.4% during the past five years regardless of the economic uncertainties in the UK. Quick Service Restaurants are generally very labour intensive, and this industry currently employs more than 320,000 in the UK only (QSR 2018).

The fast-food industry is developing rapidly, and the traditional view of unhealthy and greasy foods is changing. Therefore, many QSRs have adapted to more health-conscious markets. For example, Subway and McDonalds have added healthier options on their menu during the recent years by providing salads and healthy wraps along with the traditional burger, fries, and sandwiches.

Based on a research by Deloitte LLP, QSR's are being driven by younger age groups like millennial and generation z's who eat out-of-home more frequently. This graph demonstrates the out of home eating frequency by age groups driven by changing demographics.

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**Figure 3: Age demographics of fast-food consumption
(MCA 2019)**

Figure 3

Key consumer trends

According to Deloitte LLP research there are nine key long-term consumer trends in this industry, these trends are:

- 1- “Healthy eating: low calories options, vegetarian and vegan diets, allergen aware dishes (gluten free).
- 2- Informality: Using restaurants as a place to socialize, on the go lifestyles requiring grab and go options.
- 3- Use of digital technology: online reviews, pre-ordering, digital menus.
- 4- Experience-driven behaviour: Providing a unique and exceptional experience.
- 5- Value scrutiny: value for money, set menus, instant rewards.
- 6- Provenance: increased consumer focused on provenance and sustainability.
- 7- Premiumisation: gourmet fast food and indulgence trends.
- 8- Consumer promiscuity: lack of brand loyalty and willingness to experiment with alternative cuisines.
- 9- Home delivery: home delivery is growing exceptionally in the UK and currently it is at 10 times faster than the total earning-out-market” (Deloitte, 2019).

Franchising

“Franchising can be observed as a growth model for already existing businesses that have the development capacity, as well as a model for introducing a new business that considerably lowers unpredictability and risk. Self-initiate own new business (considerable start-up capital, a great deal of time to establish a rewarding business), or acquiring an existing business entity (a substantial capital required) nowadays is more high-risk as well as harder to begin, if investors want to prevent several of the typical start-up mistakes, after that a sensible solution is to buy a franchise (shorter time to a start-up business, lower initial capital, significantly lower level of risk, much safer but not assured business future)” (Wykes, 2001).

Alternatively, “numerous business utilizes this model for development as well as growth of their own business, reinforcing their very own identity and market position.

Therefore, it is concluded that the franchise is an excellent approach for new or smaller sized companies (franchise users) which have far better opportunities for business start-up or

growth, along with larger businesses (franchise providers) that have much more growth opportunities” (Pipes, 2003).

"Franchise is an arrangement that generally fosters the quick growth of new businesses and permits the exploitation of low chances." (Oxenfeldt and Kelly, 1968, 69). Moreover "franchise may represent a faster way to establish a new business chance." (Selden, Gipson, and Parker, 2008). However, one of the most appropriate theories of franchising is the resource scarcity theory. “This theory recommends that the franchising system can expand faster, using other resources through the franchisee. The franchise model of business has been effectively executed for several years in developed nations (Andrew et al. 2007; Hsu and Jang 2009)”.

Franchise and the business development

“Its vast use began in the 40s and also 50s as well as nowadays franchising is among the fastest establishing kinds of business all over the globe (Mendelsohn, 2005; Antonowicz, 2011)”. A franchise can be described as a relationship between two parties, where the franchisor is providing the right of sale to a particular product or services within the selected area in a certain amount of time or offers the franchisee the right to use their profession trademark, or brand, products or services, and the franchisee would normally utilize their service understanding and their experience, or the operational procedure. The franchisee then pays the franchisor a particular (preliminary) fee to obtain the right to start using an effective business system as well as pays a percentage of their sales to the franchisor. This is normally called a Royalty and this fee for Subway is currently at 12% which consists of 8% royalty and 4% for advertisement purposes.

“Franchising can be likewise specified as a method for the circulation of product or services that allows an independent entrepreneur (i.e., the franchisee) to acquire from the parent company (i.e., a franchisor that runs a network of outlets) the right to sell the service or products under its trademark name and also to utilize its business techniques (Lafontaine 1992; Combs, Michael, and Castro giovanni 2004; Pruett and Winter 2011)”.

Additionally, “franchising is a system in which the franchisor gives a licence, trademark, as well as recommendations, and aid in arranging, merchandising, and handling business as a long-lasting business relationship” (Andrew et al., 2007). To put it simply, “franchising is a contractual inter-firm business partnership that is formed in between a grantee (franchisee) and also a grant (franchisor) for selling the franchisor's item, using the franchisor's trademark

and exclusive business system in a defined location for a specific duration (Dant and Grunhagen 2014)”.

“Franchising is simply an approach for increasing a business as well as dispersing items as well as solutions with a licensing connection. In franchising, franchise business (an individual or company that provides the license to a third party for the doing of a business under their marks) not just specify the product or services that will certainly be provided by the franchisees (a person or company who is granted the license to do business under the trademark and brand name by the franchisor) yet also supply them with an operating brand name, system, and support” (International Franchise Association, 1999).

“The franchisee buys an already proven business model with a system established by a franchisor with a structured collection of operational procedures that normally lowers the threat significantly contrasted to the traditional business (Shane and Hoy 1996; Spinelli, Rosenberg, and Birley 2004)”. “Franchising influences transfer of technology as well as business approaches and deal of top-quality products and services at sensible costs (Dwivedy 2002)”.

“Franchises are differentiated by 3 characteristics: the franchisor has a trade or service mark and also certifies it to franchisees in return for royalty payments, franchisees spend for the right to be part of the system, as well as the franchisor gives its franchisees with a system for working” (Kotler and Keller, 2006).

The franchise relationship between the franchisee and the franchisor is administered by an agreement between the two parties, wherein the franchisor is generally responsible to offer: specialist and support, suggestions, expertise as well as experience, and they should make sure that the system procedure is in place and that it’s up to the standards of the business, whereas the franchisee is required to purely value the criteria of the company and the techniques that the franchisor expects them to run the business. “The franchisor (typically legal entity) grants the civil liberties of the business under its trading name, most often has a franchise business partnership with multiple recipients, thus ensuring the recognizability and also high quality of its solutions or items to consumers (their buyers) on a wider geographical footprint. A franchisee (natural or lawful person) is a business entity acting individually on its own part yet under defined terms of the franchisor (who intends to maintain the identity, credibility, quality, and brand identity) which are regulated by contract.

Although franchisors and franchisees are legally independent from each other, they share the very same targets (Insa-Ciriza 2003; Berbel-Pineda and Ramirez-Hurtado 2012)”.

In this model of business, the franchisor offers a successful and proven business model as well as a widely known product/brand idea, while the franchisee adds supervisory proficiency, regional market understanding as well as resources (Oxenfeldt as well as Kelly 1969).

According to Lewandowska (2014) “the franchise is the financial relationship that the owner of the procedure, or licence (franchisor) provides to the other event (the franchisee) the right to use them readily for the payment or contractual benefit. The franchise business's success originates from the franchisor rate of interest that the franchisee is making business success, since the franchisor will therefore have an economic advantage (with agreed portions of the franchisor's income). The recipient pays a franchise cost and pays royalties continuously, thus giving a nonstop income source for more growth and also expansion of the franchise” (Lewandowska, 2014).

“A franchisor that has enduring successful understanding and experience in the business sector that have an effective and identifiable product and/or service (name/brand), a reliable and well-known business idea-- may believe whether to expand the business in an additional area by opening its very own affiliates, or choose to offer a regional firm a franchise. In the second situation, the franchisor shares the costs, the threat, and the results of business growth with the franchisee, who becomes their business companion. Depending on the type of business and task of the franchisor, and whether the franchisee has a property or otherwise, the first expenses can be differed in a large range. Franchise costs are brought by the franchisee, and the danger of starting a business as well as costs of funds. The franchisor has to establish its own sales team for development and assistance of the franchising network, aiming to make best use of earnings, which inevitably increases the income as well as number of employees (Alpeza, Erceg, and Peterka, 2015)”. Nevertheless, if a particular franchise model is useful and profitable in a specific locations, it does not necessarily guarantee its success in another location (various competition, different customer criteria, various customer behaviours, attitude, culture, religious or various other personalized, and so on). Consequently, before getting into franchising it is vital to think about the needs to recognize the regional market as well as whether this business is truly feasible in that specific area.

Benefits of franchising

There are many benefits offered by a franchise model which makes it ideal and motivates investors to get into this type of business. The most noticeable benefits are: faster and more efficient growth by using a proven model, being able to use funds offered by the franchisor, aids from the franchisor in terms of providing manuals, expertise and the know-how of doing the business, being able to share all the risks associated in the business with the franchisor, larger access to the regional market conditions, better involvement as well as motivation through increased turnover as well as earnings, and as a result greater involvement via locating new partners.

“The franchisor can thus accomplish higher and faster growth, with sensible use of own capital and also justification of business as well as financial threats (with less investment, reduced threat, new areas in a broader area where brand advertises as well as strengthens name, product/service, business idea of the franchisor), while boosting the income as well as dignity, the monetary position of the franchisor itself, in addition to the worth of the franchise system for which new franchisors will be interested. Therefore, faster development results in economies of scale with marginal financial investment (Maitland 2000; Shane 2005)”. “Where franchise business provide three major sources: managers, cash, and time. A few of the considerable benefits to franchisee are the use of an effective and tried and tested business concept (if it is consisted of in contract), a proven and also effective brand, a well-known special business image, making use of educational services, training, coaching, consultancy services (especially if the franchise recipient has no expertise and experience)” (Maitland 2000; Shane 2005).

“The amount of initial capital investment is compensated with the advantages of supplying manufacturing and/or service sources (availability as well as rates of raw materials, refunds, centralized purchase of basic materials), schedule of market research outcomes (available top quality info such as possible acquiring power of prospective consumers, specific niches, rates and conditions of sale of competition, genuine demand, legislation, requirements), as well as there is additionally the opportunity of financing from the franchisor.

Considering that the topic of the franchise arrangement is a validated, successful, standard product, service, business concept, and also trademark, and the agreement consists of assistance in selecting the location, training and hiring of staff members, suggestions and help in the purchase and also plan of sales or solution space, taking innovation, i.e. the whole business procedure as well as proven business procedures when all the specified elements of

such an agreement are taken into account, the threat of an unsuccessful business is a lot lower” (Maitland 2000; Shane 2005).

Drawbacks in franchise business for franchisor are mirrored in the losing total control of their system because the business would be run by someone outside of the company, since the franchisor is no longer the proprietor of the franchise place, as well as monitoring and controlling the workplace because that would be done by the franchisee independently. Therefore, from time to time it is possible that the franchisee would not comply with guidelines and policies of the franchisor which is called a non-compliance. “Non-compliance with the guidelines and business rules, developing their own policies and means of operating, non-objective coverage on incomes, and for this reason a decreased percentage in earnings which franchisee pays to franchisor. There is additionally a realistic opportunity that after the expiration of the franchise arrangement, the franchisee comes to be a rival to the franchisor in such a way that they create their own services or product (based on obtained understanding, business experience, business procedure, etc.)” (Weinrauch, 1986).

“The largest disadvantage in franchise business for franchisee is long contractual business responsibility that franchisee should purely abide by, and such a liability is most often a very long period. Despite the spent funds by the franchisor, the legal responsibility of the franchisee is to pay precisely the acquired royalties from the recognized turnover, which brings about the reality that the franchisor does not participate just as in selecting the division of profits from the recognized business activity, therefore they are not equal partners. Furthermore, the franchisee monetary obligations are compulsory, irrespective of the understood turnover” (Weinrauch, 1986).

Weinrauch (1986, 1) also found that “the owners of established local businesses are usually brought in by the prospects of attaining increased growth and profitability through franchising” (Weinrauch, 1986, 1). “Well-publicized, rags-to-riches' tales concerning successful franchisors have aided to create the illusion that this form of organization supplies a quick, simple shortcut to business success. The economic impact that franchise business has on the world economy is manifested in output and production of new tasks, an increase of the tax base, economic innovation, development of small and medium entrepreneurship, as well as procurement of new abilities and capabilities (Alon, 2006)”.

“Franchising at its finest is a partnership that develops trust, opens interactions, and accumulates benefits to both the franchisor and its franchisees(Antonowicz 2011, 9)”.

"Franchisees also develop an all-natural group for an informal or official cooperative initiative and gain the natural benefits of group purchasing powers well as franchise business contributes to the establishment of trust, interaction, and advantages for both sides in the franchise partnership, and success means growth and boosted profitability of the franchise. This business model came to be an efficient chance for small tourist ventures, which cannot afford to finance their growth (Dreyer, 1998)".

"Although the franchise business has its lots of benefits, the franchise cannot promptly address all the problems and also provide totally safe and secure business success (Mahacek and Lihtar 2013)". Additionally, "Sustainability of the franchise business design depends not only on financial sustainability but additionally on meeting the franchisee's demands through formal administration mechanisms to guarantee secure, enduring franchisor-franchisee partnerships as well as the economic sustainability of the chain (Monge, Sanz, and Zavala, 2017)".

Franchising in the United Kingdom

Franchising has a rich history in the UK which can be seen all the way back to the Feudal practices in the 16th Century England when the feudal lords occasionally granted permission to peasants to use their lands in return for certain fees (British Franchise Association, 2017b). At present, the franchise industry plays a key role in improving the economy and national productivity of the UK.

According to the latest survey on the franchise industry conducted by the British Franchise Association (BFA), there are 901 franchise brands in the UK with 44,200 franchise outlets (British Franchise Association, 2016). The survey further indicates that 621,000 persons were employed in franchise industry, while generating GBP 15.1 billion (USD 19.65) in 2015.

The most interesting data point in the survey is the fact that 97% of the franchised units in the country were operating profitably, with more than 50% recording turnover in excess of GBP 250,000 (USD 321,300). This goes to support the empirical findings that franchised businesses are profitable and could be more so than independently owned ventures (Hua & Dalbor, 2013).

In the UK, there are no specific laws guiding franchise business partnership (British Franchise Association, 2017a). Apart from the BFA Code of Ethics that guides the conduct of franchise business in the country, contracts in the industry are enforced according to the existing general business and commercial laws (Pratt, 2017). The important commercial and business laws that are relevant to parties entering into franchise partnership in the UK include The Trading Scheme Act 1996, The Fair-Trade Act 1973, The Marks Act 1994, The Data Protection Act 1998, and The Bribery Act 2010 (British Franchise Association, 2017a).

Other issues on which proper legal counsel may be needed to conduct a successful franchise business especially for franchisors include pricing controls, exclusivity, tying practices and online sales by franchisees (Drakes, 2017). Thus, the foregoing discussion has shown that the franchising is an important business model in the UK with the industry contributing meaningfully to enterprise promotion, job creation and GDP growth in the country.

Subway

“Subway, the globe's largest restaurant chain, was founded in 1965. The creator, 17-year-old Fred DeLuca, intended to go to university, however he could not manage it. A good friend of DeLuca's, Peter Buck, suggested him to open a small submarine sandwich shop so he can make some money. At first DeLuca was not excited about the idea, but after thinking of it for a while, he became a lot more interested. Buck promised to spend \$1000. In the summertime of 1965, Pete's Super Submarines opened in Connecticut, USA. (Subway History, 2009)”.

“Ten years later, in 1974, DeLuca and Buck chose to turn their business into a franchise. Because of the lack of time and economic restrictions, they did not wish to employ any kind of experts. They were established to begin finding franchisees by themselves. Brian Dixon, a friend of Fred DeLuca's, was the first Subway franchisee. The restaurant remained in Wallingford, Connecticut, and it was opened in the summertime of 1974. The initial worldwide Subway restaurant was opened in Bahrain 3 years later in 1977. Throughout the last 44 years, Subway has expanded rapidly. Today, there are more than 45,000 Subway restaurants in 113 countries” (Subway, 2019).

“The year 1974 was a huge modification for Subway. Developing into a franchise company opened many doors. 35 years earlier, when DeLuca and Buck chose to enter franchising, Subway was a little restaurant. It was a large danger, but they intended to take it and it deserved it” (Subway History, 2009).

“From the year 2000 and onwards, Subway has opened a lot more restaurants than ever throughout its background. One reason for this development was Jared S. Fogle, a 30-year-old American man. At that time, Fogle was a secondary school teacher experiencing being obese. After Fogle found out that he could not live to see his 35th birthday, he wished to transform his way of living. Fogle developed his own Subway diet, which consisted of two subs, a footlong and six-inch. He was additionally involved in sports too. In 3 months, Fogle lost practically 45 kilos, and at the end of the diet regimen, he had increased that quantity. Fogle's diet regimen motivated many other individuals. Thousands of individuals all over the world intended to change their way of life and tried the Subway diet too. Since 2000, Jared S. Fogle has cooperated with Subway, and he is among the vital individuals in Subway's marketing. He circumnavigates the world telling his astonishing tale to people. Fogle has additionally joined several Subway projects (Subway History, 2009)”.

“When DeLuca started running his sandwich business in 1965, he promoted his restaurant, ‘Pete's Submarines’, on the radio. A few years later, it was changed to Subway, as it is understood today. The Subway chain has used lots of mottos throughout the last 44 years, however one of one of the most widely known mottos is ‘eat fresh’. It was introduced in 2004. ‘Eat fresh’ tells customers that Subway uses just newly baked bread as well as fresh ingredients. Mottos might differ from country to country. Subway also has clubs for its participants, the sub club, as well as the subway card. In this club, customers gain a various number of stamps relying on what they get. Being a subway-card proprietor, customers make a various number of points depending upon how much money they spent (Subway History, 2009)”.

More about Subway

“Subway supplies customers a broad option of sandwiches called ‘Subs’. Sandwiches are constantly fresh baked, and customers can select if they desire their sandwiches toasted or non-toasted. There are 2 different dimensions of sandwiches, a 6 inch. (15cm) and a foot long (30cm). Subway likewise offers sodas together with the sandwiches. Cookies, chips, coffee, hash browns and delicious chocolate can be bought as accompaniments.

Subway has a huge sandwich selection. There are more than two million various sandwich mixes. Healthy as well as light subs can be appreciated in Subway restaurants. This fast-food chain offers sandwiches, which include only six grams of fat or less.

Customers determine what they desire their sandwiches to consist of. The filling can be ordered double, or some things can be left out. The Subway chain also has a vast array of dressings that can be selected from. The customer can select between take-away as well as having it at the restaurant. Any kind of subs can likewise be ordered as a salad. Salads was added in the food menu in 1980” (Subway History, 2009).

“Birthday celebrations and various other events can be celebrated in Subway restaurants. On the food selection, customers can discover a catering part, which contains sub plates, giant subs, and cookie plates. The giant subs can be made to any size depending on the amount of people. Sub platters consists of 15 4 inches. cookie platters have 36 (minimum) delicious cookies(Subway, 2019)”.

As of 2019, there are over 45,000 Subway chain restaurants operating in 113 countries across the world and it considers to be the fastest growing franchise restaurant globally. There are new shops opening all the time and Subway currently employs over 200,000 employees.

According to Subway headquarters, they have added 5,000 new jobs in the UK and Ireland by 2020 in an expansion. The company has opened an additional 500 shops within two years, from 2500 stores in 2017 to 3000 stores in 2020.

The country director, Peter Dowding said: “the move will strengthen the chain's position within the UK market”. He said: “The growth expansion has been continual. What we have achieved over the last few years has been phenomenal for the brand and for our franchisees across the UK and Ireland”. (Dowding, 2017)

“We set some very ambitious targets in 2012, where we said we would get 3,000 stores by 2020 and we are well on our way to achieving that”. “In fact, we will be opening our 2,500th store, which is a fantastic achievement for the brand in the UK. It strengthens our position in the market as being the leading quick-service chain in the UK.”

The company’s turnover in the UK and Ireland has reached to over £515million in 2016.

“Subway's UK operation has been going through a massive brand transformation, with plans to kick-start a new online ordering platform. The business was also tackling the Brexit-induced rise in inflation by working with its suppliers to lock down prices for the next couple of years” (Dowding, 2017).

Problem Statement

Subway's vision statement since 1974 has been to "**Be the #1 Quick Service Restaurant (QSR) franchise in the world while delivering fresh, delicious sandwiches and an exceptional experience**" (Subway, 2020). However, after years of efforts by the company to achieve this vision, according to the QSR magazine published in 2017, Subway is #3 after McDonalds and Starbucks respectively(QSR, 2017). This study aims to identify why Subway was unable to achieve this by providing an in-depth analysis of the company and applying relevant theories and past research.

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Table 1

Table 1: Top 10 brands ranked by QSR (QSR magazine, 2017)

In response to this problem, the main purpose of this study is to examine factors affecting the performance of Subway in the fast-food industry and recommendations to how Subway could place itself as the **#1 QSR worldwide**.

These factors have been shown to contribute to the quality of performance for Subway and will be further explained in the literature review:

- 1- Consumer Preferences**
- 2- Health Issues**
- 3- Internal and External Pressures**
- 4- Employee Turnover**

Although many factors contribute to the performance of QSR like consumer preferences, health issues and pressures both internally and externally which are all explained here. Based on the research and findings on this thesis the most important factor is employees, they are at the core of this business, they handle all the day-to-day tasks and the business success mostly depends on them. Therefore, Employee turnover is the most important part of this thesis as there is substantial evidence that it is highly related to job satisfaction and performance and is highly prioritised by this study and more work has been done to address this issue including a separate survey on this matter.

Research Questions and Objectives

Main Research Question

To what extent do Consumer Preference, Health Issues, Internal and External Pressures, and Employee Turnover affect the performance of Subway in London, United Kingdom?

Research Aim

To identify the key factors that affect the performance of the QSR and to examine their relationship among attributes that enhance the performance of the Subway franchise in London, United Kingdom. After the first initial research, Consumer preferences, Health issues, Internal and external pressures and Employee turnover has been found to significantly affect the performance of Subway and the aim of this research is to investigate these factors further and provide recommendations on how they should address them. The researcher believes by implementing these recommendations Subway could greatly enhance their position within this industry.

Conceptual Framework

Conceptual Framework

Justification

This conceptual framework demonstrates the link between “Consumer Preferences”, “Health Issues”, “Internal and External Pressures” and “Employee Turnover” to the overall performance of Subway. Furthermore, “Consumer Preferences” and “Health Issues” are directly related to each other and to the performance.

Similarly, “Internal and External Pressures” and “Employee Turnover” are directly related to each other and to the overall performance but not to the other two factors. Therefore, “Consumer preferences” and “health issues” are considered as external factors and “Internal and External Pressures” and “Employee Turnover” are the internal factors based on this framework.

The researcher believes that the company can greatly improve its performance in the market by focusing on these issues. Performance in the eye of the researcher is defined based on the ranking of fast-food restaurants published by the QSR magazine which is the most respected publisher in this industry.

Hypotheses

- 1- Even though QSR's are offering healthier options, health issues still negatively affect the performance of Subway because the perception of fast-food is generally negative and customers have become more health conscious in the recent years.
- 2- Employee Turnover negatively affects the performance of Subway because the rate of turnover in this industry is very high.
- 3- Consumer Preferences is an important factor in this business as many competitors are directly competing in this market. Therefore, consumers have the bargaining power, and this could negatively affect the performance of Subway.
- 4- Internal and External Pressures exist in every business however, this has a bigger effect on fast-food restaurants because they must maintain a very high standard in food quality, customer satisfaction and cost reduction. Therefore, it could negatively affect the performance of Subway.

LITERATURE REVIEW

“The fast-food industry employs 14.4 million people and is expected to produce 1.7 million more jobs by 2026 (National Restaurant Association, 2016). With \$782.7 billion in sales annually, service quality is a prime issue of employee performance” (National Restaurant Association, 2016).

“The perception of value depends on the degree to which customers believe that the product will contribute to fulfilling their goals. Creating value for consumers is a very important source of competitive advantage for a retailer. However, retailers have strong beliefs about those aspects of their business demonstrated by experience as being important for obtaining the goals and profits they are looking for” (Skytte & Bove, 2004).

In this section, issues perceived to be affecting Subway’s performance in the UK is being discussed. Starting with Consumer Preference and followed by Health Issues, Internal and External Pressures and Employee Turnover.

Consumer Preference

This section is separated into a few subsections; it includes segmentation, targeting and positioning. Each section then is sustained by popular literary works along with previous and also speculative research study on this subject.

Over the last decade, the fast-food market has actually been growing internationally as the number of fast-food outlets boosted rapidly. Recognizing customer behaviour and preference assists to create public policy. Fast-food operators should recognize customers' problems as well as develop effective ways to educate them. For instance, MacDonald's can decrease food waste by informing consumers not to leave the food uneaten. By studying consumer behaviour, Subway has the ability to establish and also implement prices, distribution, and promotional approaches. For the fast-food market, consumer behaviour has a strong effect on the advancement of advertising method formula, economic health, and also government plans. Concepts of customer behaviour are used by Subway to establish special advertising strategies to enhance sales. Because of the fast-changing of consumers' tastes as well as choices, Subway must develop the appropriate marketing mix including products, price, place, and promotion to affect the need for their products.

One approach that Subway could utilize to gather information from its customers is a qualitative study which assists them to find what consumers believe as well as really feel about the products offered. Qualitative research consists of observation, one to one interviews and focus groups which are vital when Subway is checking new products or developing new marketing campaigns. By observing the consumers' behaviour, Subway can obtain understanding into customers' behaviour and also extensive comments. Face to face interviews can be conducted by Subway which makes it possible for the individuals to talk freely and also discuss the products offered. For example, it enables the individuals to try a new products before launch and request them to give comments on it. Besides, organizing a focus group permits Subway to connect and develop excellent connections with their customers. For instance, they can carry out meetings with different kinds of customers to review a specific product.

A widely known model discussed in this section is the SERVQUAL model, which is short for the Service Quality model and is the research technique to capture and analyse consumer expectations and understandings of the service.

However, there are some problems concerning this approach as service quality alone does not show the complete dining experience, thus making it not sufficient. Possibly to address this issue a better way is to conduct more details speculative research study to have described information on the dining experience for consumers. This sort of experimental research study is not typically done within this industry; therefore, it is advised that Subway ought to conduct their very own experimental study within their outlets to have a much deeper understanding of their customer's wants and needs something that is not presently being done in the shops.

“The study of consumer behaviour potentially manages how individuals may act in their role as customers. However, in exercise often tends to focus upon behaviours related to searching, purchasing, as well as utilizing services and products. Customers might be dealt with as groups, market segments, identified by geo-demographic features and assumed to have typical mindsets and practices. Additionally specific, subjective viewpoints might provide an insight into behaviour patterns (Schiffman and Kanuk, 1991)”.

Today, quick service restaurants are a part of the hospitality sector. However, in the past some authors were including it in the Tourism industry. Much research have been done on the hospitality industry and its different sectors, but there is a few articles or publications devoted to customer study in the QSR sector. This market is a crucial market, in regards to economic turnover, even though it adds in some ways to both hotels and tourism, it has its own different features.

“QSR, take-always, and even contract catering, are much more volatile, unpredictable, and fashion-prone than resorts or traveller attractions. Thus, in concept food solution offers a specifically fascinating location for examining customer practices and preference. The food service market has functions that establish it aside from various other locations of the service field such as professional and financial solutions (Johns, 1999)”.

“It is closely concerned with food option and top-quality meal yet at the same time has long been thought about to use an abundant meal experience to which several various other factors add up (Smith, 1967)”.

“Quick service restaurants exemplify 2 facets of post-modern customer society. It is adaptable, artisan-focused, and context-dependent adequate to provide a high degree of customisation. Thus, it can offer an ultimately temporary short-lived product in a very simulated atmosphere: typical standards of postmodernism (Jameson, 1984)”.

Past research

“The goals of survey studies typically suit a three-stage schema of segmentation (learning who will certainly come to dine) targeting (identifying what groups of consumers desire) as well as positioning (recognizing what style a certain restaurant uses the marketplace). The geodemographic characteristics often utilized to mark sections are just secondary signs of exactly how consumer groups are most likely to act. Therefore, scientists frequently refine geodemographic segments using psychographic steps such as psychographic ranges, or indications of intended behaviour, as well as there is a resultant obscuring of the segmentation, targeting and positioning functions”(Bowen, 1998).

QSR or fast-food industry consists of several literatures on segmentation. As an example, “Nayga and Capps (1994) associate the need for various sorts of restaurants to different socio-economic sections”. While “Binkley (1998) shows that demographic and income differences have less effect upon the need for fast food than the population density of metropolitan areas”. Furthermore, “Shoemaker (1998) identifies teams of college canteen customers with different requirements, utilizing his findings to show just how segmentation should drive service technique”. Several well-known research studies in this sector are focused on a specific niche section. As an example, “Becker-Suttle et al. (1994) and Williams et al. (1997), respectively, determine the eating preferences of older customers, as well as the factors that inhibit this group from using full-service restaurants”. Furthermore, “Reynolds et al. (1998) mentions that among older customers, males were more likely to visit fast-food restaurants than females”. Moreover, “McClain et al. (1993) analyse the methods which United States restaurants cater for customers in wheelchairs, locating problems with around 50% of all restaurants”. Additionally, “an interview survey of the issues as well as stress and anxieties of obese female customers found that they felt ‘on display’ or guilty at being ‘caught out’ eating, as opposed to diet habits (Zdrodowski, 1996)”.

There are several research studies on consumer preferences published back in the 1970s and 1980s which even today researchers are referencing them in their studies. Even though there are a few disagreements and other sub-theories in this section, a summary of them is mentioned below.

“Customers are thought to watch a service such as a restaurant meal in terms of a set of attributes: i.e., attributes that make it desirable, referring different levels of value to every

characteristic. For instance, one market segment might be drawn in by a restaurant's affordable price, an additional by its food quality, another by its practical area, and so forth. Consumers evaluate the overall value of an offering in terms of the level to which each quality exists and the significance they see the characteristic as having” (Winterfeldt and Edwards, 1986; French, 1988).

According to Winterfeldt and Edwards (1986), “this general examination creates an attitude towards a restaurant, which may be just one of 2 kinds: a pre-experience mindset (expectation), or a post-experience performance evaluation. More academic refinement argues that customers assess their experience according to exactly how well actual performance confirms or disconfirms their assumptions (expectancy disconfirmation concept). Thus, in principle customer perspectives in the direction of a meal experience can be gauged by deducting assumption ratings from the scores of actual efficiencies. A favourable general attitude to a restaurant is believed to lead to repeat business” (Winterfeldt and Edwards, 1986; French, 1988).

“Much food service consumer research reflects this wide theoretical structure. Thus, several writers have examined restaurant qualities, ending the primary ones to be the choice and high quality of food as well as drink, the cost or value, service, atmosphere, place, and comfort. One study utilizes multidimensional scaling of this credit to position food and beverage offerings in Korean resorts. Some authors differ regarding the relative importance of qualities, specifically the food and beverage” (Kim, 1996).

Another study found that “sanitation, high quality, and value to be the 3 most important attributes in fast food restaurants, while ambience as well as menu selection were reasonably useless” (Pettijohn et al., 1997). Moreover, “the evidence recommends food quality and value to be the most significant restaurant qualities and question the assumption of classic ideas such as that of Campbell-Smith (1967) that the complete bundle of attributes comprising the ‘food experience’ determines consumer behaviour. Clark and Wood (1998) reported that the order of feature relevance is rather different in various designs of restaurant” (Clark and Wood, 1998). Furthermore, “Auty (1992) concluded that the relative importance of attributes changes with the type of eating occasion”.

“The role of attribute actions in segmentation is demonstrated by Oh and Jeong (1996) that segment the fast-food market based on customers' expectations of food, comfort, environment, as well as service” (Oh and Jeong, 1996).

Moreover, “Kara et al. (1995), revealed that demographically comparable groups of US and Canadian fast-food customers had different assumptions of the kind of food served, the area of restaurants and the cost of the dish”. Other researchers studied about different characteristics of the restaurants, for example “Tefft (1995) reports that Canadian customers were inspired by the taste of food, instead of its nutritional properties” (Tefft, 1995).

“During the 1980s, Parasuraman et al. (1986) made a big contribution to customer research in service sectors with the SERVQUAL tool. This makes use of 26 standardised questions to measure generalised service characteristics that are taken into consideration pertinent to all service markets. Parasuraman et al. (1986) showed that their 26 things could be regularly lowered into five service measurements: reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangibles. They determined service top quality by separately scaling customers' assumptions and perceptions of service performance as well as subtracting the latter from the previous. Therefore, SERVQUAL conformed to the body of knowledge concerning customer behaviour and at the same time provided a generalisable set of service qualities” (Parasuraman, 1986).

“The applicability of SERVQUAL in the food service has been demonstrated by Bojanic and Rosen (1994) as well as Lee and Hing (1995), while Stevens et al. (1995) have created a somewhat modified tool that they call DINESERVE. Numerous other writers have made use of the instrument in attitude surveys of restaurant customers (Richard et al., 1994)”. “Although SERVQUAL summarises service features in a satisfiable theory method, it takes little account of other empirical attributes of the restaurant experience, most significantly food quality. Johns and Tyas (1996) changed the SERVQUAL range by including food-related items, however, were incapable to acquiring clear factor patterns corresponding to those of Parasuraman and his associates. Johns et al. (1995) employed multivariate stats to associate SERVQUAL ratings to empirically identified features of the food experience, finding a clear distinction between food and service. Numerous empirical research by various other writers reconfirm the significance of food quality and showed that customers see service among several factors impacting the quality of restaurant offerings. Customer satisfaction is a much more practical method of conceptualising actions of restaurant performance, because it can be based upon a totality of qualities, including both food as well as service. Most of the short articles talked about above that empirically determine restaurant quality features are essentially worried about assessing customer satisfaction” Johns and Tyas (1996).

“Pizam and Ellis (1999) reviews the theory basis underpinning customer satisfaction. Consumer satisfaction is concerned not just with quality values but additionally with more comprehensive value systems” (Pizam and Ellis, 1999).

For instance, “Sun (1995) identifies consumer participation (i.e., the value of the option to the individual at the time of acquisition) as a significant factor affecting restaurant customers' satisfaction. Through values, customer satisfaction is also related to society”. Furthermore, “Hsu, (1997) recorded that Korean university student assessed restaurants in the order dining>quick service>family style, yet their pattern of use showed the opposite order of preference. Nevertheless, it is not clear whether this demonstrates cultural preference for restaurant designs or a culturally determined tendency to provide the ‘right’ reaction” (Hsu, 1997).

Moreover, “Becker et al. (1999) found that United States and Hong Kong trainees had various assumptions of restaurant service. The Asians valued respect, helpfulness, and cleanliness, while US students needed eye contact, personalisation, and product knowledge” (Becker et al., 1999). In addition, “Goll (1994) goes over ways in which the business values (i.e., corporate culture) influence customer satisfaction” (Goll, 1994).

There are numerous studies researching about the connection between customer satisfaction and repeat purchases by customers. For example, “Clark and Wood (1998) reported that concrete aspects like the high quality and selection of food are the vital factors in consumer commitment yet note that the principle of food quality may be interpreted in extremely different, subjective means” (Clark and Wood, 1998). Additionally, “Pettijohn et al. (1997) gauged customer contentment using empirical characteristics, finding that satisfied customers had a significantly greater purpose of returning. A much more in-depth study of the satisfaction-repurchase relationship is that of Kivela et al. (1999a, b, 2000)” (Pettijohn et al., 1997).

“These authors use a step-by-step theoretical version that defines satisfaction in regards to expectations and performance making use of empirical qualities. Satisfaction is in turn pertaining to return behaviour via a logistic regression expression. The model likewise consists of customer qualities and situational factors such as the dining celebration, the customer's participation, and their involvement as well as money available to them, and therefore it attains a legitimate analysis of the likelihood of return.

Kivela et al. (2000, p. 28) concludes that service quality is not the vital attribute for creating repeat business and suggest that restaurant qualities, along with relationship marketing strategies have better influence”.

“Studies into consumer behaviour normally handles antecedents such as product/service attitudes or customers' specified intents to repurchase. Nonetheless, the correlation between objective and action may be quite little and generally includes other factors (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975)”. Nevertheless, other authors have attended directly to behaviour. As an example, “Lyons (1996) identifies factors underlying whining practices from focus group as well as interview data. She found that degrees of customer involvement as well as dissatisfaction made complains more likely, yet situational and personal factors additionally played a part. She notes that restaurant problems were a lot more concerned abstract and social concerns than those encountered in other service sectors” (Lyons, 1996). Furthermore, “Huang and Smith (1996) studied customer feedbacks to unacceptable dining experiences, concluding that restaurants must constantly clarify the reasons for unsatisfactory service and offer compensation” (Huang and Smith, 1996).

Moreover, “Lynn and Graves (1996) discuss tipping practices, though mostly in terms of its motivation value for service staff members”. Additionally, “An even more consumer-oriented study by Rogelberg et al. (1999) uses a policy-capturing technique to examine the method people judged tipping in hypothetical restaurant circumstances. A lot of participants evaluated the suggestion from the price of the dish, but the quality of the food and service and the kindness of the team additionally had an impact. Rogelberg's group did not find a relationship between customer satisfaction and tipping. Two surveys have examined the repercussions of voucher used behaviour regarding pizza restaurants. Wilbourn et al. (1997) distinguished 3 market sectors based upon pizza value assumptions and coupon-proneness” (Rogelberg et al., 1999). Likewise, “Garretson and Chow (1997) reports that vouchers improved buying intents and lowered regarded purchase risk yet likewise triggered service quality assumptions to drop” (Garretson and Chow, 1997).

At the end, these studies are extensively interested in finding market segments, target markets and positioning offerings about them. They commonly accomplish this with geo-demographical information added by perspective actions. Customers are expected to examine QSR with set of characteristics, as well as different concepts link consumers' mindsets to associate attributes. The major among these is span disconfirmation concept. Empirically found that qualities of QSR often are liable to prioritise the quality of food as

well as the value that they are offering. Service, ambience, and benefit likewise regularly show up, though differing in significance between different outlets.

“Service quality dimension with the SERVQUAL instrument makes generalisation feasible, not just between restaurants yet even between different industries within the service market. However, this tool neglects food quality, and consumer satisfaction, which can encompass the completeness of foodservice attributes, appears a better outcome measure” (Garretson and Chow, 1997).

Experimental research

The experimental study practice relates to dining in restaurants by means of a feature of the “food itself” and the scenario where its consumed. Remarkably, the environments where the food is consumed was not studied enough. A few of these studies are “The results of photo (Singson, 1975)” and “colours (Stephenson, 1969)” as well as “music (Bruner, 1990)” these were mostly done during the 60’s and 70’s. “It is asserted that McDonald's use of colour and picture to manage the behaviour of their customers (Love, 1995) and Robson (1999) considers up alternate style strategies for fast-food restaurants”.

“Milliman (1986) reports that slow sentimental songs caused people to remain longer over their meal”. However, amore current research study by “Herrington and Capella (1996) found that the familiarity and the preference of the music by customers are related to customers staying loner in the restaurants however, the volume and tempo of the music was not related”. “Birch et al. (1984) mentions that from preference experiments that the moment of day, and the speed of a meal affect taste assumptions. In the food service market, consumption times are mainly culturally pre-determined, and one might anticipate suitability, i.e., of the design of food and service to the meal occasion to be of even more importance. Nonetheless, there is a pattern far from culturally ‘appropriate’ consumption towards snacking, all-day breakfasts and more, which might indicate extent for a research approach based upon physiologically as opposed to socially identified eating times” (Birch et al., 1984).

Another study of food culture done by “Meiselman and Bell (1992) discovered that including typical food parts such as cheese to pasta made it appear more British to customers, however an item that was provided an Italian name was perceived as even more ethnic”.

Furthermore, “Bell and Meiselman (1995) note that sauces made foods seem " ethnic". Briefly adding an Italian motif to food selections and design not only boosted consumers' understandings of restaurant ethnicity, yet likewise elevated general understandings of food quality and the dish experience. The more acquainted customers were with a style the less variety they perceived it to supply, yet a short duration of Italian (i.e., familiar) thing nonetheless raised assumptions of total menu selection for numerous months, even after the motif was taken out (Bell and Meiselman, 1995)”. “Social context experiments expose that the amount individuals eat increases with the size of the group (de Castro, 1989)”. Moreover, “Individuals are also much more prone to attempt new foods if they first see others consuming and appreciating them (Pliner and Hobden, 1994)”. Additionally, “Bell and Meiselman (1995) reported that individuals' rates of drinking are to some extent determined by the consumption rate of the individual they are with” (Bell and Meiselman, 1995). “Schutz (1988) reports that steps of suitability (i.e., the viewed suitability of a given food to the time and area of consumption) outperform preference scales”. Therefore, “appropriateness ranges would appear to have substantial scope for examining eating conventions as well as situational factors, and it shows that context influences food selection even more than hedonic factors (Marshall, 1993)”. Moreover, “Cardello et al. (1996) studied customers' expectations of numerous institutional foods.

Subjects constantly ranked military food as poor in quality, even though a lot of them had never tried it, and they anticipated to such as institutional and airline company foods less than equal meals purchased in a restaurant”(Cardello et al., 1996). Additionally, “Collison and Turner (1988) used a hedonic scale and several regressions to compare two types of meal experience. They report that tangible food was the leading factor in the quality of everyday meal experiences, but for ‘special’ meals, such as Christmas supper, environment was more vital” (Collison and Turner, 1988).

There is fewer experimental research compared to the survey studies, even though it provides a substantial opportunity. One of the most popular experimental approaches is the following:

“In student and staff canteens and student-run public restaurants, and this approach provides a tried and tested methodology, which can be applied widely to food service scenarios. Relevance scaling does have a substantial application, as do problems about timing, ethnicity, the physical environment, as well as the social context of dining.

The work of Collision and Turner (1988) adds further support to the findings of characteristic research studies reviewed in the previous area” (Nick Johns, 2002).

Geography and the Economics

There are several yearly economic reports published on the restaurant business and QSR but the problem with these reports is that they are normally restricted in scope, not logical, and become outdated very fast. However, in many countries there are government publications periodically, which offers deeper analysis on this sector and therefore most researchers tend to use these reports in their literature. For instance, “Holm et al. (1995) offer an in-depth evaluation of retailing (including food service) in Scandinavia, thinking about basic fads in populace, families, and employment” (Holm et al., 1995).

Additionally, “Nayga and Wanzala (1996) provide a county-level evaluation of customer spend and cost circulation in the USA. No serious attention seems to have been paid to forecasting, or to evaluating the contribution of the restaurant business to regional or national economic climates” (Nayga and Wanzala, 1996).

Moreover, “Carmin and Norkus (1990) researched the elasticity of need for menu things, reporting that a 1% change in rate had a noticeable result upon consumer acquiring practices” (Carmin and Norkus, 1990). The location of outlets is vital in this business however, it seems to be neglected by researchers and not many studies are available solely based on this. “Smith (1983, p. 545) keeps in mind that the place designs made use of by large restaurant chains are confidential and requires openly available guidelines for restaurant place and also success”(Smith, 1983).

And in another study by “Arbel and Pizam (1977) identifies partnerships in between traveller preferences as well as hotel circulation patterns, but no similar work has been done on restaurants” (Arbel and Pizam, 1977). Nevertheless, two documents by “Smith (1983, 1985) evaluate restaurant area patterns regarding geographical issues, such as the distribution of populaces and industries (including rivals)”. The first publication by Smith (1983) “bargains mostly with the approach, which is applied to nationwide secondary information

from Canada. This paper analyses the areas of different restaurant types in terms of advertising and marketing approaches and talks about the effects for restaurant siting (Smith, 1983). Although it makes a considerable contribution to expertise in the field, the paper has been criticised for over-selectivity concerning sectors as well as for offering insufficient detail" (Smith, 1983). Two years after the first research another publication by "Smith (1985) applies a comparable study technique to 8 cities in Ontario, supplying a much more thorough evaluation of the heap and cluster of various sorts of restaurants. This post likewise checks out spatial correlations with various other land uses (i.e., household, business as well as recreation structure) in addition to traffic levels and populace distributions.

This study was somewhat idiosyncratic, given that it included fast food, doughnut, and ice cream stores, yet made little effort to set apart other restaurant categories. There is clearly scope for using Smith's method to shed a light on the sitting of restaurant units and the growth of chains, specifically as more advanced economic-geography versions, e.g., of monocentric metropolitan areas are appearing" (Smith, 1985).

Sociology and anthropology

"Timber (1992, 1996) asserts that despite its social and economic significance, eating in restaurants has been mainly disregarded by sociologists" Moreover, "Mennell et al. (1992) comment that a lot less study has been dedicated to the sociology of food intake than to that of employment, for which they point out works by Mars and Nicod (1984), Whyte (1949) and others". Additionally, "Warde and Martens (1998) regret perceived sociological disregard of dining in a restaurant and its role in contemporary intake. They claim that eating in restaurants is significant since it enhances the penetration of commodification as well as customer culture into daily life".

Furthermore, "Jamal (1996) offers a great research study of acculturation of the British public with the accessibility of Indian foods" (Jamal, 1996). "Riley (1994) and Warde et al. (1999) make more in-depth comments regarding social adjustments in consumption. Riley (1994) asserts that eating out in Britain has no emotional or social anchor and because there is no social agreement of what great consumers tends to examine their meal experience on its instant subjective effect and value for money". Additionally, he declares that "although there is a basic advertising and marketing presumption that food quality and variety are the essential factors in customer experience, it is the alternative and the abstract that really matter". He advises that restaurants pursue a "genuine" setting, which he dense as one which

makes a distinct declaration, without any convicting messages. “Warde et al. (1999) also argue that modern Western populaces lack an axed social system, and this drives individuals to seek a progressively wide range of aesthetically equal cultural categories” (Warde et al., 1999).

“Reynolds (1993) regrets that food offered to tourists on Bali is shedding its authenticity via a reverse of this process: Food for that reason is among the last areas of authenticity that is affordable regularly by the traveller. Yet because it cannot be transported, preserved, or placed in a galley to be revered it is the most convenient to deteriorate and copy (Reynolds, 1993).

Poor duplicates of all art types, such as artefacts and carvings and ersatz Western food are being supplied as actual 'social' experiences. The view of conventional society as seen by the traveller to Bali is being deteriorated. (Reynolds, 1993)”.

“These remarks reflect the postmodern character of modern-day intake, which is claimed to lack any sense of ‘historicity’ or geography, and which sells signs and simulacra rather than definitions as well as credibility (Jameson, 1984)”. In this light Riley's (1994) suggestion of “authentic environments, scenarios characterised by a super-abundance of homologous indications, are a lot more akin to hyper reality than to real authenticity (e.g., Eco, 1986)”. This framework should additionally state the “Peacock’s (1992) ‘new customer’ who likewise look for novel indicators to include in the collection in which she lives”. As well as “Jamal's (1996) instances of ‘Indian’ dishes unknown in that subcontinent. The restaurant sector's volatility and fashion-proneness make it a specifically intriguing prospective subject for postmodern evaluation” (Jamal's, 1996).

Moreover, “Pine and Gilmore's (1998) insurance claim that the Western economic climate is changing from a service base to an ‘experience’ base, equally as in the recent previous manufacturing paved the way to solutions. The foodservice sector is most likely to be at the forefront of such a change and postmodernist thinking might well develop the basis for understanding and anticipating developments here” (Pine and Gilmore's, 1998).

“Ritzer's (1996) comments concerning McDonald's are likewise appropriate in this context. He says (Ritzer's, 1996) that customers are progressively coming to value ‘efficiency, calculability, predictability and control’, because of adjustments in way of life, group factors, and innovation. Various authorities consider McDonald's a postmodern sensation, yet the rationalisation of fast-food service negate postmodernist insurance claims of increasing

impracticality with the spreading of signs, simulacra, as well as pseudo-objects. Ritzer resolves this dilemma by wrapping up (Ritzer, 1996) that ‘much less extreme postmodern alignment allows us to see phenomena like McDonald's as having both modern-day as well as postmodern attributes. Nevertheless, customers seek efficiency, calculability, predictability, and control in a non-logical means, for instance dining at McDonald's when they can eat much more inexpensively and efficiently at home (Ritzer, 1996, p. 147)’. Additionally, “(Ritzer, 1996, p. 154) he notes that McDonald’s has succeeded in automating the customer, they enter a kind of automated system through which they are impelled and from which they are ultimately ejected when they are refuelled” (Ritzer, 1996). Hence, possibly the “rationality that Ritzer sees is not situated in manufacturing, however in the service, where it is required to support the consumption line(Baudrillard, 1988) that basically defines post modernity”.

A very interesting strategy by Finkelstein (1989) in the sociology of dining in a restaurant suggests that food is a subservient element of the dining experience. “The event comes to be enjoyed as a form of entertainment and a part of a modern spectacle in which social relations are mediated through visual images and imagined atmosphere. This is a far remove from the sensations of ingestion. (Finkelstein, 1989)”.Finkelstein’s view allows her to have an accurate and rich understanding of the dining experience in restaurants. She fully highlights the value of this experience: “In our society, much of dining out has to do with self-presentation, through images of what is currently valued, accepted, and fashionable the restaurant is a place where we experience excitement, pleasure, and a sense of personal well-being the images of wealth, happiness, luxury, and pleasant social relations are ironically represented through its ambience, decor, furnishings, lighting, tableware and so on. These are in turn dominated by fashion and distinct waves of style. (Finkelstein, 1989)”.

The primary problem with her approach is with “interpersonal power relationships, considering dining out as a kind of ‘uncivilised sociality’ (Finkelstein, 1989, p. 5) in which power-plays are masked by manners. Her publication appears to look for a go back to an idealised world in which people are similarly awkward as well as mindful to one another, prevent power differentials and do not mediate their exchanges via signatory examples of standing as well as eminence. (Finkelstein, 1989)”.

It is questionable that working out such scenarios is a vital part of our social experience and growth, but “she could have set her disagreement at practically any type of social gathering, given that power plays are by no means unique to restaurants. Power connections are a

popular theme in sociology and their function in eating in restaurants. Mennell et al. (1992)". "Finkelstein (1989, p. 20) writes that she essentially disregarded the data she collected, because they were 'constantly and extremely naïve' as well as the task of dining out 'somehow thwarted scrutiny'. She compares them (Finkelstein, 1989) with a research study by Law (1985) in which participants cited convenience, value, quality, cleanliness, and service as the reasons they ate at McDonald's.

These characteristics are extremely alike to those reported by the empirical studies gone over in earlier in this research, and in this sense the resemblance between this study and the quantitative research discussed earlier stands out. Both seek to obtain beneath the stated value remarks of restaurants toward more general stable facts. However, simply discarding the face value data in order to accept a well-established theoretical area such as power relationships seems unsatisfactory. A different academic framework is required, which can coherently suit customers' discourse and observed behaviour" (Finkelstein, 1989).

Another way is to conduct and analyse the data driven from interviews. "Levy (1981) makes an early effort at this, when he analyses customer myths of food and family members utilizing a structuralism framework stemmed from Levi-Strauss. However, he limits his data to denotative, rather than connotative definitions, and this potentially exciting approach yields relatively little new consumer information" (Levy, 1981).

Nonetheless, "Manning and Cullum-Swan (1994) use semiotic analysis to McDonald's fast-food outlets. They make a thorough and interesting evaluation of the food selection and its discussion and extract subtle overtones of indicating within the eating circumstance. It is feasible that semiotics might ultimately give a path to the undiscovered territory of restaurants' understanding (Manning and Cullum-Swan, 1994)".

To conclude, sociological, as well as anthropological perspectives of dining out provide us with a better understanding and assumptions of this act. "Individual rationality, intentions, preference and contentment, the cornerstones of advertising and marketing psychology, are here replaced by social pressures of fashion, power relationships, rationalised service, and signs" (Bell and Meiselman, 1995).

There are several studies done on customers in QSR concerning with some elements of segmentation, like, recognising demand, positioning, and characterising section. Lots of these studies have established a systematic academic framework with a direct relationship between repeat custom and attitudes of restaurants.

The major issue is that characteristics and the experience of dining in restaurants differs from one another. Therefore, some authors have as a result generalised a set of attributes like the service quality to restaurants. Nevertheless, there are some concerns about this approach as service quality alone does not reflect the full dining experience, thus making it insufficient. Perhaps to address this issue a better way is to conduct experimental research to have more detailed data on the dining experience for customers. these researchers are not commonly done within this industry; therefore, it is recommended that Subway should conduct their own experimental research within their outlets to have a deeper understanding of their customer needs and wants.

Summary of the four areas of Food Service Consumer Research

Area	Practical focus	Methods used	Theoretical focus	Prominent authors
Survey research	Segmentation	Geodemographic, attitude & behaviour-based surveys	Attribute theory	e.g. Nayga, Oh, Knutson
	Targeting	Modelling	Expectancy-disconfirmation	Reviews by Pizam and Ellis, Bowen
	Positioning		Repeat business	Kivela, Inkbaran and Reece
Experimental research	Customer preferences	Control of specific variables.	Factors affecting food preference	Bell, Cardello <u>et al.</u> , De Castro, Meiselman, Schutz
Economics and geography	Spatial and socioeconomic location	Analysis of secondary data	Population flow and behaviour	Holm <u>et al.</u> , Nayga and Wanzala, Smith
Sociology and anthropology	Individual experience	Depth interview	Power relations	Finkelstein, Mennel et al., Ritzer, Warde and Martens, Wood
	Wider social context	Observation	Social impact	
		Literature review	Semiotics	

Table 2

Table 2: Consumer research on Food service industry

“Location and economic factors appear to be as crucial as the attributes of food and service yet have received little research study focus (Binkley, 1998)”. Another research by “Smith (1983, 1985) explain the application of an ideal approach as well as more recent modelling strategies are also available. Anthropological and sociological studies have the

prospective to improve customer research in the food service sector by casting light on the private experience that underlies customer behaviour.(Smith, 1983, 1985)".

There are a lot of concerns with the social effects of the food market amongst researchers; however, a couple of these authors have used other approaches like "semiotics" and "discourse analysis" to further analyse the customers within this market. This would allow them to have a means towards recognizing assumptions of restaurant experiences. Generally, there appears to be a need for studies to look for new methods as well as to exchange suggestions and viewpoints between disciplines.

Health Issues

This chapter explains about the health issues and concerns that both the government and the customers have regarding the fast-food industry. It includes statistics and studies done on this subject and further explains about the need for a clear indication of calorie and nutrition labelling on the products. This is then supported by different theories and models throughout the chapter.

Britain has one of the highest obesity rates in Europe, with two in three adults overweight or obese and the NHS costs £6bn a year treating obesity-related ill-health, a number that is forecast to rise to £10bn a year by 2050. The government has announced plans in 2021 to introduce a 9 pm watershed on TV and a restriction on paid-for advertising online for unhealthy food as well as drink, plus new limitations on the advertising of unhealthy food as well as drink in retail outlets and online. This could additionally increase to an overall ban on fast food advertising online. This new regulation indicates that tv and online advertising on food with high fat, salt and also sugar components will be restricted which might have serious repercussions for the QSR as well as advertising and marketing that Subway is no exception of that. That's why the move has actually been met severe objection from the Food and Drink Federation in the UK.

The review, by the Centre for Food Policy at London's City University, discovered that easy accessibility to fast-food 24-hour a day throughout the UK makes losing weight "challenging" for countless individuals who are trying. "Individuals participating in weight management reported eating much more, simply because the food was quickly offered, and this continuous exposure caused them to want food more often". At the same time, NHS

warns of a feasible link between obesity and severe disease from Covid, with specialists claiming that being obese rises by around 37% the chances of dying from the condition.

Since the introduction of calorie labelling a couple of years back, there have been numerous research done on this matter, especially regarding the efficiency of this law and whether it has worked to cut down the obesity rate. As an example, there was an experiment back in 2018 regarding whether providing calorie labelling at the point-of-purchase on a restaurant menu has an influence on food options and intake amongst teenagers who eat consistently at fast-food outlets. The experiment concluded that amongst the sample made use of calorie labelling of food has no influence on consumption, although after training and educating the customers around calorie labelling the results of the experiment significantly boosted.

On the other hand, in another study, around 300 individuals looked at the impact of calorie labelling on food choices as well as consumption. The results from the research showed that typically the individuals consumed fewer calories when the food selections provided both calories and the advised day-to-day intake.

Based upon these 2 research and a lot more, it is safe to assume that those customers who are really calorie-conscious would certainly take advantage of these tags, whereas those that are not calorie-conscious would certainly profit less from it. Another interesting study found that individuals like to stabilize an unhealthy main course with a healthy and balanced snack, or a healthy and balanced main dish with an unhealthy dessert, instead of picking 2 unhealthy or 2 healthy and balanced main courses and desserts.

From the findings of this research, it is safe to presume that calorie labelling might aid to minimize these concerns by educating the consumers about the number of calories each food contains. Although Subway is among the healthiest fast-food alternatives in the market, health problems still adversely impact them because of the bad perception of customers on it.

Subway is currently using calorie labelling in all their branches throughout the UK however as displayed in the previous studies, labelling has really little influence on consumption, yet after educating the public around it the outcomes can extremely well enhance. It is advised that Subway interact and advertise more often concerning calorie usage as well as its results on our overall health and wellness.

“The increasing appeal of eating out has suggested that the hospitality industry has adjusted to satisfy demand, resulting in the boosting variety of restaurants (Longart, 2015)”. “Fast-

food outlets accommodate the customers searching for preference, low cost, and high quality. Fast food restaurants together with rapid casual restaurants (don't provide table service) are integrated as well as classified as Quick Service Restaurants (QSR) within the restaurant industry, offsetting more than 50% of sales within the market (Franchise Help, 2018)".

For that reason, "the rising demand and appeal of the fast-food sector can trigger some concerns particularly for the health and wellness of consumers. Fast food products are renowned for having high energy density and glycaemia loads in addition to offering customers with large portion sizes.

For that reason, health and wellness specialists think the increase in fast-food extravagance is contributing to the increasing rate of overweight/obesity levels (Rosenheck, 2008)".

Additionally, "these growing concerns are not limited to USA with expanding rates of obesity within the UK, 2015 numbers suggesting 58% of women as well as 68% of men were overweight/obese (NHS, 2017, A)". For that reason, introducing the calorie labelling within QSR's. "As a result of the boosting appeal of dining in a restaurant and overweight/obesity rates increasing has captured the attention of policy makers (Ellison, 2012)".

Additionally, "The Food and Drug Administration (FDA) as well as The Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency (MHRA) have presented a legislation with the aim to assist educate consumers on the food they are consuming outside the home to help in reducing the weight gain (Harnack and French, 2008)".

Moreover, "As a result of this, the new law suggests chain restaurants or similar food sellers with greater than 20 restaurants require labelling the calorie intake of their foods on menus (FDA, 2016)".

One of the key factors of weight problems and obesity is from "overindulging in calories with two-thirds of grownups in America being overweight/obese (Federal Register, 2014)". Vicious (2006) states that "nearly a 3rd of food consumption is done so outside the house within the UK and USA (Vicious, 2006). Furthermore, "With many individuals having little understanding of calories and the dietary material for that reason taking too lightly the calories and nutritional value within food products causing the food labelling law by the FDA (Federal Register, 2014)". "Statistics reveal that the adult weight problems level in the UK is 26% only 13% lower than the USA (National Statistics,

2017)”. Consequently, Mintel (2017) mentions that “menu labelling is the first step to assist consumers consume healthier and choose far better dish options with 26% of customers currently curious about calories on food selections (Mintel, 2017)”. One of the most important reasons of how companies and organizations market their products to their consumers. Today, consumers have become very health-conscious therefore they pay attention to what they consume, the way their food is prepared and as well as the impacts that the food production has on our environment.

During the past 20 years there was an increase of concerns about the ways food is produced as well as the different conditions that food are grown. The primary reason for this concern is the disease commonly known as the “Mad Cow” in Europe.

Because of that there has been an increase of demand for info about where the food is originated from, and the methods used during the production of food. With this type of information then customers can be aware of the quality and the safety of the food they are about to consume.

Based on a research from UK foresight report (2011), “the adjustment in values as well as ethical positions of customers will certainly have a major impact on food usage. Therefore, food safety and security and food system governance will be influenced. Instances consist of problems of national interest as well as food sovereignty, the acceptability of modern technology (for instance genetic modification, nanotechnology, cloning of animals, synthetic biology), the significance accorded to particular regulated and extremely defined manufacturing methods such as organic and related management systems, the value put on animal welfare, the relative importance of ecological sustainability as well as biodiversity protection, and concerns of equity and fair trade (UK foresight report, 2011)”.

Businesses especially in quick service restaurants are willing to adapt to new trends in food consumption if they believe that it will increase sales and improve customer satisfaction. But there is difference between how consumers and retailers process information about different product attributes and that is because of the difference in their buying behaviour, strategies, and targets.

“The assumption of value depends on the level to which consumers believe that the product will certainly add to meeting their goals. Value creation for customers is an extremely important source of competitive advantage for a business. Nonetheless, stores have strong

beliefs regarding those aspects of their business demonstrated by experience as being important for obtaining the earnings and goals they are searching for” (Skytte & Bove, 2004).

However, the fast-food industry is developing rapidly, and the traditional view of unhealthy and greasy foods is changing. Therefore, many QSRs have adapted to more health-conscious markets. For example, Subway and McDonalds have added healthier options on their menu during the recent years by providing salads and healthy wraps along with the traditional burger, fries, and sandwiches.

Calorie

“Calories within food relates to the amount of energy it consists of (NHS,2017, B)”. NHS further explains that “the recommended standards for calorie intake for males are around 2,500 kcal a day, with females’ intake being 2,000 kcal a day. The standards are open to alter as they are based upon size, age, as well as levels of physical health together with a combination of other factors. By eating a lot more calories than made use of, it leaves the extra calories to be saved as fat. Over time this builds up, resulting in being overweight (NHS,2017, B)”.

Nutrition

“Professor Barbara Shannon's Study (1988) of Nutrition as a factor affecting food service is especially timely. The effects of consumerism can be seen in many industries, but that force has not yet begun to affect the food service field seriously.

As an industry, we Still have time to act without pressure, but nutrition will certainly affect the industry's future, particularly in such a rapidly growing area of public sector feeding as school lunch and congregate feeding for the aging.

Professor Shannon's study (1988) reveals' important, but currently neglected areas for research. The effect of the food service establishes ment's production system (reconstitution and holding of product) on nutritional values has not been adequately studied nor has there been definite work on nutrition retention in frozen prepared food. Since institutional feeding is increasing rapidly and the use of frozen prepared food is accelerating.

In all food service settings, a clear understanding of the nutritional issues related to the two interacting areas of concern is called for. Consumerists, once aroused by an irresponsible (even if unintentional) rendering of services, generate pressures that are difficult and

expensive to deal with. We may hope that the research necessary to identify the relevant issues will be forthcoming.

It seems likely that an essential part of the food service worker's knowledge base in a future, increasing consumerist world will include an understanding of then handling of products for maximum nutrition retention, particularly in mass feeding where 30 percent or more of the guest's nutritional intake is controlled by the establishment” (Shannon, 1988).

According to World Health Organisation, “Nutrition looks at the body's dietary needs, lay out the food that assists to keep a healthy diet. If your body does not receive the appropriate foods, it can cause bad nutrition, in turn, triggering lowered resistance and a raise the chance of diseases (World Health Organization, 2017)”.

For that reason, “signifying the relevance of nutrition with previous experiments additionally indicating that nutritional labelling can result in healthier buying. Results have shown that supplying nutrition info on food menu is not just beneficial to consumers but also the restaurant, as it can assist to get reassurance as well as confidence from the customer and establish a much better customer image of the information’s source (Hwang and Lorenzen, 2008)”.

According to a Nation's Restaurant News survey, most Americans appeared unconcerned about nutritional or dietary issues when going out to eat at a restaurant. Only one out of three American diners reported nutritional or dietary concerns influenced their eating places. Women were more concerned about the health aspects of eating out than were men.

There were 35% of the women answered "yes," compared with only 25% of the men when they were asked "Do you ever choose a restaurant based on nutritional or dietary concerns?"

Among demographic segments, the 35- to 45-year-old respondents and the most highly educated group were most concerned about dietary and nutritional issues. Fat was mentioned by 11% of all respondents. Another 11% said that cholesterol was an issue.

In a recent survey of Consumer Report's Readers, “three out of five said that they went to fast-food restaurants more to get in and out quickly than for the quality of the food. When they were asked to rate the various aspects of fast-food restaurants, 40% of the respondents perceived that they were eating only fair or poor nutritionally; only 4% of them were willing

to award top marks for nutrition. About 60% said they are 'worried' about nutritiousness at these QSR's" (Consumer Report's Readers, 2017)

Customer behaviour

"Consumer behaviour can be specified as the behaviour that consumers present in searching for, buying, making use of, examining, and disposing of service or products (Schiffman, Kanuk, and Hansen, 2012). Customer behaviours manage the various ways in which people communicate in their role as a consumer, regarding browsing, acquiring as well as the products (John, 2002)".

"Restaurants in all areas of hospitality (chains and hotels), take-away, contract caterers are extra spontaneous, fashion-prone, and adjustable hotel or tourist attractions. These are attributes within the Food service sector that established it aside from other services. It closely focuses on food options and high quality in addition to providing an abundant meal experience to which numerous other factors contribute" (John,2002).

Customer Behaviour and its Theories

"Over 300 years ago Bernoulli developed the very first description for decision-making. Von Neumann and Morgenstern then went onto expanding this theory naming it the utility theory (Richarm, 2005)". The Utility theory further explains that the decision-making by customers is heavily related to anticipated end results because of customer choices. According to this theory, customers were taken into consideration as "rational actors who were able to estimate the probabilistic outcomes of uncertain decisions and select the outcome which maximized their well-being (Richarm, 2005)".

These tasks consist of: "need recognition, information search, evaluation of alternatives, the building of purchase intention, the act of purchasing, consumption and finally disposal (Bray, 2008)". Customer practices has developed using lots of unique stages because of "new research methodologies and also paradigmatic come close to being embraced (Bray, 2008)".

"This progression has ended up being noticeable in the contemporary meaning of customer behaviour; customer behaviour and decision-making includes a range of diverse models as well as methods specifically when considering the hospitality sector. Several models are developed on customer behaviour, for instance, the "cognitive approach" which "explains exactly how certain microorganisms or variables can influence the action due to the outcome of purchasing decisions" (Stanton, 2016),

"The cognitive approach views individuals as 'Information processors' recognizing the

impact of environment and social experiences when processing info. During the 1950's Hebb presented the Stimulus-Organism-Response model playing a significant component in the advancement of cognitive psychology (Hall, 2016)”.

**Figure 4: Cognitive Consumer Behaviour Model
(Hall, 2016)**

Figure 4

“There are 2 distinctions when analysing the customer behaviour model; they are prescriptive or analytic. Although this model does not directly connect to the calories on menus, it can be made use of to obtain a far better understanding of just how customers make their choices, specifically within the hospitality sector” (Bray, 2008).

Analytic Model

“The analytic models supply a structure of the crucial elements that are reported to describe the practices of consumers. These models highlight the influencing factors and bring together the relationships between the factors influencing consumer decision-making (Bray, 2008)”.

Prescriptive Models

“Prescriptive Models supply a framework and assistance on the framework of customer behaviour. perspective models consist of the order in which components ought to show up and suggest the impact that should be observed given certain causal factors. highlighting what stimuli must be customized or emphasised to make it possible for a specific feedback from customers (Bray, 2008)”.

Hospitality and its Customer Behaviour

As demonstrated in these models "consumers perform a hierarchy of requirements and expectations, connected partially to the setting in which the choice is made (Williams, 2002, pg.51). The difficulty with linking these models with the hospitality sector is regularly altering with the choices being made on 'high degrees of irregularity as well as intangibility' (Williams, 2002, pg. 51) specifically in the fast-food market, where the experience can be brief because of a short consumption time.

Although these models as well as theories do not particularly discuss calories on menus, they can be made use of to help gain an understanding of the elements influencing consumer purchasing" (Williams, 2002).

"These models, especially the analytical ones are based on information searching, and it consists of 5 stages that can help recognize if customers would take advantage of calories on menus. In the hospitality market, pre-purchasing information searching is mostly identified by individual preference, accessibility, and availability of the info (Williams, 2002)".

Additionally, as explained by William, "There are several ways in which information can be utilized to assist the consumer for instance.

1. Consumers may expect to take better decisions after information acquisition and processing.
2. Information is seen to reduce perceived risk
3. Consumers may be more confident in using information
4. Information processing identifies desirable alternatives and rules out undesirable options
5. Information is used as a defence mechanism in justifying a decision after it has been made (Williams, 2002)".

"With calorie labelling being introduced to help inform the customers, the 5 points made from information searching can aid describe exactly how this could improve consumer buying choice. The five factors demonstrate the more information the customer has, the better their decision will be as well as by highlighting the different calorific material of food can assist provide customers with an option that could be more useful for them. Expanding on customer behaviour an additional issue that needs to be dealt with is what inspires consumers to visit specific hospitality outlets? To comprehend what

consumers are searching for the understanding of what encourages them is required. Consequently, looking at motivational theories such as Hierarchy of needs it provides a spherical view of what affects the customers". "He also has already specified that consumer behaviour models deal with customers carry out a pecking order of requirements as well as assumptions" (Williams, 2002)".

**Figure 5: Maslow's Hierarchy of needs
(Research History, 2012)**

Figure 5

Maslow's Hierarchy of needs

"One of the most popular theories of human motivation was formulated by Abraham H. Maslow in 1943. Maslow's 1943 theory is based on the following propositions:

- 1- Man's needs are arranged in a hierarchy of importance, ranging from the lowest need Physiological to safety, love (social), esteem (ego), and self-actualization. This hierarchy of 'pre-potency' or urgency of satisfaction means that the most urgent need will monopolize the individual's attention while less prominent needs are minimized, even forgotten.
- 2- Man is continually wanting; therefore, all needs are never fully satisfied. As soon as one need is satisfied, its pre-potency diminishes, and another need emerges to replace it. This is a never-ending process which serves to motivate man to strive to satisfy his

needs. A later writing by Maslow modifies this concept of pre-potency for people who are predominantly growth motivated.

- 3- Once a need is fairly well satisfied, it no longer motivates behaviour. Man is then motivated by the next higher level of unsatisfied need but can be motivated in a reverse direction if a lower-level need is threatened. For a man who sleeps regularly and adequately, sleep ceases to be a motivator. But if a person has not slept for two days, his needs for companionship, self-esteem, and recognition are at a minimum and his need for rest is his primary motivation.
4. The needs are interdependent and overlapping. Since one need does not disappear when another emerges, all needs tend to be partially satisfied in each area.

In such people gratification breeds increased rather than decreased motivation, heightened rather than lessened excitement. The appetites become intensified and heightened. They grow upon themselves and instead of wanting less and less, such a person wants more and more. The person rather than coming to rest becomes more active. The appetite for growth (Maslow, 1943).

Physiological Needs

As mentioned before, physiological needs must be satisfied in order to sustain life. Included on this level are air, food, water, sleep, elimination, mating, and temperature regulation. These needs take precedence over other needs when they are not gratified. A person who lacks food, safety, love, and esteem would probably seek food more strongly than anything else. When a man is dominated by a certain need, his thoughts for the future also tend to change. For an extremely cold man, his ideal can be defined as a place that is warm.

He thinks he would be perfectly happy and never want anything else if he were guaranteed warmth for the rest of his life. He defines life itself in terms of warmth. Everything else is considered unimportant.

Physiological needs have certain characteristics in common:

- 1- They are relatively independent of each other.
- 2- They can usually be identified with a specific location in the body (for example, thirst can be identified with the throat).
- 3- In an affluent society such as ours, these needs are unusual rather than typical motivators.

- 4- In order to remain satisfied, they must be met repeatedly within relatively short periods of time(a person's drive for oxygen must be met at least twelve times minute).
- 5- They require some conscious provision for their future satisfaction.

Safety Needs

When physiological needs are relatively well satisfied, needs at the next higher level emerge to dominate man's behaviour? These are the safety needs, expressed as desires for protection against danger, threat, and deprivation. What has been said of the physiological needs also holds true for these needs. Since every industrial employee is at least partially dependent upon his employer, safety needs, expressed as desire for security, can also be very important. Desire for security takes the form of quests for economic security (savings account and a job with tenure and protection); preference for the familiar rather than the unfamiliar; desire for an orderly predictable world; and knowledge of the limits of acceptable behaviour.

Social Needs

When physiological and safety needs are relatively satisfied, social needs become the new motivation of man's behaviour. Again, the whole cycle already described will repeat itself with social needs as the new centre. These needs include belonging, association, acceptance by his peers, and giving and receiving friendship and love. In this case, love is not synonymous with sex, which is a purely physiological need.

Man will aspire for a place in his group and will strive to achieve it. Attaining such a place will become the most important thing in the world to him. In spite of knowing of these needs, managers often wrongly assume that these needs and the resulting informal organizations represent a threat to the objectives of the formal organization.

By fearing hostility and opposition from informal organizations, some managers attempt to direct and control employee relationships in ways that frustrate the natural groupings of their employees. These employees may then react by being resistant, antagonistic, and uncooperative, this behaviour is often a consequence, and not a cause of the manager's actions.

Esteem Need

Esteem or ego needs next above the lower-level needs of physiological, safety, and social do not become motivators until the lower-level needs have been reasonably satisfied. Unlike the lower-level needs, these are rarely completely satisfied. But once these needs become important to an individual, he will continually seek satisfaction of them. The problem is that the typical industrial organization offers only limited opportunities for the satisfaction of these needs at the lower levels of employment.

Esteem needs consist of both self-esteem and the esteem of others. Self-esteem needs include self-confidence, self-respect, competence, achievement, and independence and freedom. Satisfaction of these needs leads to a feeling of worth, capability, strength, and of being useful and necessary in the world. Frustrating them leads to feelings of inferiority, weakness, and helplessness. Needs relating to the esteem of others include needs for status, recognition, appreciation, importance, and prestige.

Self-Actualization Needs

The emergence of self-actualization needs comes only after all other needs have been satisfied. These needs include the realisation of one's potentialities, self-fulfilment, continued self-development being creative in the broadest sense of that term. Even if all other needs are satisfied, a person may experience discontent and restlessness if he is not doing what he is best suited for. What a man has the potential to be, he must be.

The form that these needs take varies from person to person just as their human personalities do. Self-actualization needs can be satisfied through one of any combination of athletics, politics, academics, the family, religion, hobbies, or business.

They involve a creative state in the sense that creativeness is realizing one's own potentialities to the fullest degree, whatever they may be. It is a feeling of accomplishment and attainment, and of being satisfied with oneself'. (Cain, 1974)

Calorie Labelling and its Implications

In the past it was not common for fast-food restaurants to provide any type of calorie labels on their products whereas this nutritional information has been available on all the home food products. Therefore, there has been no clarity about this information throughout QSR's

(Belluz, 2017). The lack of openness around the calorific material of food initiated the “Patient Protection” as well as “Affordable Care Act (ACA) 2010” applied by the FDA.

This has made it mandatory for all the QSR’s to either print the calorie labels for each product and stick it on them or they should provide this information on their menu and throughout the restaurants. Focused on QSR’s, it specifies that “restaurants and similar retail food establishments if they are part of a chain of 20 or more locations, doing business under the same name, offering for sale substantially the same menu items and offering for sale restaurant-type foods should reveal their calories on their menus (FDA, 2016)”. This law would allow customers to have a deeper understanding of the calories consist in each fast-food product and helps them to make a more informed decision (Belluz, 2017).

Based on a research by FDA and ACA over-consumption of calories is the number one reason for obesity, therefore they hope that this law would help to bring the rate of obesity down (FDA,2014). “Hence, the new introduction of calorie labelling in restaurants and other food facilities makes it possible for customers to see the nutritional value of the food products and the calorie consumption helping them to make healthier and better-informed dietary choices (Food and Drugs Administered, HHS, 2014)”.

Based on a research in 2008, by providing the menu labelling in only 10% of the major QSR’s it is possible to reduce the annual weight gain by 39% (HER, 2009).

Another research in 2013 revealed that, “consumers underestimated the number of calories and fat content in food products outside of the home and menu labelling reduces the intention to order high calorie labelled foods. (HER, 2013)”

Labelling in the QSR

Today, there is a widespread concerns about calorie labelling in the hospitality industry. However, this study focuses only on the QSR’s since this a huge industry, and it is not possible to cover every sector in just one research. Therefore, future research could be done on other sectors of the hospitality industry regarding the calorie labelling.

The QSR’s has been growing rapidly year by year and a result, after the introduction of the calorie labelling law there has been a massive increase of printing these labels amongst the QSR’s, with restaurants trying to provide the most up to date nutritional and calorie information of their products as well as in the stores (FDA, 2016).

Theory

Since the introduction of the calorie labelling, there has been many studies done on this matter, particularly about the efficiency of this law and whether it has been useful to cut down the obesity rate. These research are done in two ways: one is the lab experimental research which is done in a laboratory and under regulated conditions. And the second one is a field experiment which is done outside in different locations based on the nature of the study. Some of these research and their findings are as follows.

“Harnack et al. (2008) carried out study into whether supplying calorie details at the point-of-purchase on a restaurant menu have an impact on food option as well as consumption amongst adolescents who eat routinely at fast food restaurants. The Laboratory experiments revealed that among the sample utilized calorie labelling of food has no influence on consumption, although after training around calorie labelling the results of the experiment dramatically boosted.

After the research was conducted Harnack et al, (2013) believed that the demand to increase concern about nutrition when eating at fast food restaurants, as factors such as preference and ease seem an even more essential consideration for most customers (Harnack et al., 2013)”.

In another research, “with 303 participants looking at the effect of restaurant menu calorie labels on food choices and consumption. The results from the study showed that on average the participants in the calorie identified group as well as the team with calorie labelling plus information consumed 124 and 203 fewer calories. The impact of calorie labelling was demonstrated when the menus provided both calories and the recommended daily intake.

Finally, the result from this research found that calorie information on restaurant menus lowered the total amount of calories people ordered and consumed for a dish as it enabled individuals to produce a much better estimate on their calorie intake (Roberto et al., 2010)”.

As demonstrated above, these two studies show a contradictory result on the effect of calorie labelling and how customer choose their food based on this information provided to them. In the study by Harnack, it was concluded that “there was no considerable impact on customer consumption when calories were displayed although did find a slight improvement if they were educated on food labelling first (Harnack et al. 2013)”.

And in the other study by Roberto, it can be seen “that calorie labelling helped lower the calorie intake of consumers although this last theory is extremely contrasting to literature around calorie labelling” (Roberto et al. 2010).

Based on these two studies and many more, it is safe to assume that those customers who are very calorie-conscious would benefit from these labels, whereas those who are not calorie-conscious would benefit less from this. Hence, calorie-labelling is not expected to produce instant result in this industry and more should be done to address this issue.

“Deloitte (2012) argue that: healthy eating is a critically important consumer driver, a trend that will have considerable influence over company strategies in the coming years.

Population increases and aging, as well as rising GDP, allows us to assume that this trend will continue to gain importance until 2030”. (Deloitte, 2012)

It is believed that future consumers are going to have a better understanding of eating healthy due to a better education level. Healthy eating and a healthy diet will result in an improvement in the overall well-being. Therefore, the demand for healthy food is going to increase in the coming years and as a result, the customer’s willingness to pay will grow as well (Marette et al, 2008).

Different individuals have different perceptions on risks or health benefits of the food and that is because the education level, skills and experiences are different in everyone. Some may disregard the potential risk because of the food taste and others may consider factors like safety and cost as well (Lin & Milon, 1993).

Likewise, “the effect on buying behaviour may be affected by the level of consumers’ involvement in personal health care and related to other habits. Consumers that are concerned with nutrition and health are more likely to use nutritional labels than those less concerned” (Lin & Milon, 1993).

Conversely, following the dietary plans are sometimes tough to uphold by customers. It is easy to access the information regarding a healthy diet, but not everyone is willing or able to comply with these dietary guidelines (Hamilton et al, 2000).

“Euromonitor International's Annual Study (2011) discovers that, today respondents globally rank good health as the most important determinant of happiness and that consumers both in emerging and developed markets show interest in dieting”.

From this result, we can then argue that “in the 15 leading youth markets, one-third of 16-24-year-olds claim to be trying to lose weight and healthy food was found to be popular worldwide, with 56% of global youth buying healthy products”. (Euromonitor, 2011)

There is an increasing concern about proportions of obese customers in the past few years. This increase can be seen mostly in developed countries which resulted in numerous diseases. Therefore, some researchers argue that a similar trend could occur in developing nations as well if the food consumption improves due to the increase in their GDP.

Based on a report from World Health Organisation, “in 2008, more than 1.4 billion adults, 20 and older, were overweight. Greece, United States, Italy, Mexico, New Zealand, Chile, and the United Kingdom have the highest rates of obese children aged 5-17 where the percentage of obese boys and girls is more than 25% of the whole population. Countries with the highest obesity rates among adults are the United States, Mexico, New Zealand, Chile and Australia where 33.8%, 30%, 26.5%, 25.1%, 24.6%, respectively, are obese”. (W.H.O, 2011). The meat consumption is very high in these nations. Countries such as China and India are also battling with obesity these days, but this was not a concern for them in the past.

Health Claims and Food Decisions

“Complementary food choices are those related to the choice of side beverages or treats purchased complying with one's option of a main course (Dhar and Simonson 1999). Additionally, Existing research has only examined the effects of health claims on the choice and consumption of the advertised food, and its evidence is mixed.

Kozup et al. (2003) found that adding a ‘heart-healthy’ claim to a menu increased consumer’s intentions to order the food. However, Raghunathan, Naylor, and Hoyer (2006) found that labeling food as ‘healthy’ reduced the likelihood that it would be chosen because of negative taste inferences. Various other studies have found that the preference for healthy foods depends on the degree of ego depletion (Baumeister 2002), cognitive load (Shiv and Fedorikhin 1999), guilt and the need for justification (Okada 2005), individual differences in body mass (Wansink and Chandon 2006), comparison frames (Wansink 1994), as well as the accessibility of chronic hedonic goals (Ramanathan and Menon, 2006; Ramanathan and Williams, 2007).

On the other hand, the evidence regarding the results of health claims on corresponding food choices is more consistent. In a collection of vignette research studies, Dhar and Simonson (1999) found that consumers predict that individuals like to balance an unhealthy main dish

with a healthy treat, or a healthy main dish with an unhealthy dessert, instead of choosing two unhealthy or healthy main courses and desserts.

Fishbach and Dhar (2005) found that boosting progress towards the goal of losing weight activates the hedonic taste goals and increases the likelihood that people select a chocolate bar over an apple. Guilt is one of the explanations why consumers tend to balance health and taste goals within a single consumption episode.

Ramanathan and Williams (2007) found that some consumers can launder the guilt created by their choice of an indulgent cookie by choosing the utilitarian option in a subsequent choice. Therefore, it is expected that, once the choice of the main course has been made, consumers will choose side orders, desserts, and beverages containing more calories if the main course is positioned as healthy than if it is not” (Henderson, 2016).

Regulating Factors

“Clearly, not all consumers base their food consumption decisions on health or nutrition considerations. One may anticipate that customers extremely associated with nutrition would be extra well-informed about it and less likely to be affected by health claims (Wansink 2005)”.

“Yet, previous study suggests that nutrition involvement might not regulate the results of health claims. Moorman (1990) concluded that nutrition involvement increases the self-assessed ability to process nutrition information but does not improve nutrition comprehension or the nutrition quality of food choices in two product categories.

Two research studies (Andrews, Burton, and Netemeyer 2000; Andrews et al. 1998) found that objective nutrition knowledge improves the accuracy of some nutrition assessments however does not significantly decrease erroneous inferences across nutrients or the effectiveness of objective nutrient information in reducing these overgeneralizations. Another research studies have discovered that association-based errors, such as those arising from priming, cannot be fixed by boosting motivations and the degree of elaboration (Arkes 1991)”.

Additionally, “Johar (1995) found that highly involved consumers are more likely to be deceived by implied advertising claims because involvement increases the likelihood of making invalid inferences from incomplete comparison claims, such as this brand’s sound quality is better” (Johar, 1995)

“Chapman and Johnson (1999) showed that cognitive elaboration, one of the consequences of involvement, enhances anchoring effects because it facilitates the selective retrieval of anchor-consistent information. For these reasons, it is expected that nutrition involvement increases the overall accuracy of calorie estimations but does not moderate the effects of health claims on calorie estimations and on complementary food decisions.

How can health halos be reduced? If calorie inferences are partly caused by priming and selective activation, one solution is to encourage consumers to question the validity of the health prime. Drawing attention to the priming source reduces priming effect even if the activation of information in memory occurred nonconscious. (Strack et al., 1993).

The efficiency of the debiasing strategy is enhanced if individuals are asked to consider evidence irregular with the prime. Mussweiler, Strack, and Pfeiffer (2000), working on the estimation of the value of a used car, showed that instructing people to consider whether a claim opposite to the one primed may be true increases the accessibility of claim-inconsistent knowledge and therefore reduces selective-accessibility biases” (Henderson, 2016).

As discussed in this section, health concerns over fast foods have increased in the coming years. However, calorie labelling could help to reduce these concerns by educating the customers about the amount of calorie each food contains. Although Subway is among the healthiest fast-food options in the market, health issues still negatively affect the performance of QSR's because the perception of fast-food is generally negative and consumers have become more health conscious in the recent years.

Subway is currently offering calorie labelling in all their branches throughout the UK but as shown in the previous studies, product labelling has very little influence on consumption, though after training around it the results pointedly improved.

Therefore, to tackle this issue it is recommended that Subway should communicate and advertise more frequently about calorie consumption and their effects on our overall health.

Internal and External Pressures

Labour

“Labour is identified by economists as one of the three basic factors of production: land, labour, and capital. It is clearly one of the most basic inputs to any kind of enterprise. Labour costs of the food service and housing industries have undergone seemingly radical change in

recent years and structural developments in the labour market suggest that the pattern of change will not only continue but accelerate. Several factors have bid up the price of labour in recent years. Principal among these is a growing economy coupled with a relatively tight labour market; and the social welfare policy of the state and national governments”.

The Minimum Wage

The minimum wage in the UK is an external pressure enforceable by the government. The set nationwide minimum wage is broken down for different age groups. The rate for the greatest 23 and over has been rebranded as the national living wage. So, on April 1, 2022, the nationwide living wage boosted to £9.50 per hour for people aged 23 and above, this is a 6.6% rise from the previous rate. The government has called it the largest-ever rise to the nationwide living wage-- which has existed in its current form since 2016-- and stated that it would indicate a £1,000 annually pay increase for full time workers. However rising cost of living, as gauged by the Consumer Price Index, leapt to a 30-year high of 6.2% in the year to February 2022, and also got to 7.25% in April 2022, making the minimum wage surge of 2022 below inflation rates.

The national living wage, for any person aged 23 and over, is £9.50. So, for someone working a permanent job at a 35-hour working week, gross income would be at £17,300 per year before tax or pension deductions. These increases have not kept pace with the inflation or increased rent prices in the UK, Housing is considered affordable if it constitutes no greater than a third of an individual's earnings.

With that in mind anybody 23 and over, working full time on the national living wage, will not be able to rent a home for less than a third of their pay in any region of England.

According to current research study by the ONS rental fees in the cheapest location, which is the northeast, averaged at £425, which is still more than a 3rd of a living wage income after-tax deductions. (ONS, 2022)

“Toward the end of the Great Depression of the 30's, the Fair labour Standards Act of 1938 was enacted. The Goals of wage regulation were:

- 1- Elimination of poverty resulting from substandard wages.
- 2- Creation of the necessary purchasing power to maintain high levels of employment and output.

3- Establishment of a floor under wages to prevent repetition of the downward wage spiral experienced during the depression”.

“Overtime penalties pay provisions were clarified and spelled out in considerable detail in this set of amendments. The general trend was clearly raising wages. During the same time, legislation was passed broadening the coverage to include more industries and to include smaller firms.

These tendencies reached the hospitality industries in 1966, when the national minimum wage was raised and food service and housing establishments were brought under FLSA regulation to bring the industry's wage to the national level of by 1971” (FLSA, 2001)

The Rise in Earnings

“Average hourly earnings have risen for hospitality industries, as have hourly earnings of other service employees and other retail employees and indeed, as have wages for all employees.

While the lines representing wages in the various groups are not perfectly parallel, an examination of the figures suggests that the rates of increase experienced by these industries have not been radically different than those of other industries.

Not only hourly income but also the length (e.g., number of hours) of the work week, suggests that hotel and food service employee's weekly earnings have risen at a rate like other employee groups. An interesting development is that unemployment benefits (for all employees) begin to approach the rate of compensation for employees in the food service and housing industries.

Although wages have risen rapidly in our industries, that increase has, in fact, been less rapid than the rise of, wages in the economy in general. Hotel wages rose 70 percent, while wages for the whole economy rose 80 percent. Food service wages rose 30 percent. In the same period, wages for all employees rose 43 percent. On the other hand, the rise in wages in the economy was accompanied by an increase in productivity. Output per man hour rose 12 percent from and 35 percent. Unit labour costs for the entire economy rose 27 percent” (FLSA, 2001).

The Plateau in Productivity

“Although no separate productivity index is available-for food service and housing industries, it is important to notice that most of the workers in these industries are engaged in either personal service work or in manual occupations in which only limited productivity increases are available through mechanization. While wages for hospitality industries rose at slightly slower pace than in the economy, it seems reasonable to assume that productivity in traditional hospitality firms such as hotels and restaurants rose only marginally.

Some increases in productivity might be noted, for instance the trend toward more self-service (the use of buffets, reduction in bell staff services) and limited economies may have been realized from such automated devices as dial switchboards. The basic picture, however, remains one of a labour-intensive, personal service industries.

If this reasoning is correct, it follows that unit labour costs (i.e., the portion of revenue from each cover sold or room rented required to cover labour costs) in the hospitality industries have risen at a substantially higher rate than they have in the economy.

It is instructive to look at the firms in QSR industries which have improved productivity. In fast food, where the number of covers served per employee is surely radically higher than in the more traditional, restaurant setting, what we have is not so much the introduction of automated equipment as the complete redesign of the food service system relying on a drastically simplified menu and self-service, as well as the introduction of industrial engineering techniques accompanied by a certain amount of automation.

As wages rise (along with other costs) the operator has only two choices, aside from going out of business. Those are either to rework the system to eliminate labour (as in fast food, perhaps, by drastically simplifying the system) or to incorporate the ever-higher cost structure in the price offered to the consumer and maintain the traditional level of service. As prices in traditional service settings rise, that increased price structure offers an inducement to innovators to develop new, simplified formats, such as the fast-food operations have done, to compete on a price basis with the traditional establishment” (FLSA, 2001).

Social Policy and Labour Supply

According to Henderson (1965), “for the unskilled 50 to 60 percent of workers at the base of the lodging industry' pyramid, there are few alternatives, and these workers do not have much

opportunity to move into new occupations and industries. It is this lack of mobility that has allowed the industry to continue to pay such low wages to many employees, since it is obvious there has been no need to offer higher wages to attract the requisite number of workers”(Henderson, 1965).

Work vs. Welfare

“It is important to realize that the hotel or restaurant worker of interest is not the tipped worker but the 50 to 60 percent Henderson referred to as unskilled. Thus, understatement of tipped income is not a factor in the comparison. On the other hand, it is perhaps even more important to notice that the welfare benefits are probably a significant understatement of the actual benefits available.

In addition, the income received from AFDC, generally included in those benefits are free medical care, food stamps (and free lunch for school children), and substantial free counselling services on economic, family, and social matters.

As one authority has put it, it is worth pointing out here that a job at the minimum wage yields an equivalent annual income significantly lower than the scheduled welfare budget allowance for a-family of four.

Welfare benefits have increased dramatically in the past thirty years. Durbin, in a study of welfare benefits states that welfare benefits increased more than average wages in manufacturing, more than the minimum wage and more than the average or maximum unemployment compensation benefits. Durbin's study shows average wages rose 13 percent while the minimum wage rose 30 percent and the welfare allowance 40 percent. AFDC expenditures have grown 156 percent. This growth was attributed to increased benefits (52 percent) and increased number of recipients (48 percent)” (Henderson, 1965).

Where Are We?

“At this pointy, for many years QSR industries have been subject to the pressure of rising wage rates. As wage cost has increased, either productivity was increased to offset some or all that cost by redesigning the system, using ever simpler foodservice systems as in fast food, or the price structure of the establishment was changed to pass on to the consumer the increase in the cost of the factors of production.

The climbing price of the products and services of the conventional hotel and restaurant markets has supplied an inducement to innovators to create still more systems which were of lower expense to operate and therefore could be provided to the customer under the umbrella of the price structure of traditional facilities. A creating pattern, nonetheless, in social policy, is the development of numerous welfare revenues to the point where they normally approach and frequently exceed the incomes of those working at the lower end of the wage scale. It ought to be kept in mind that these advantages do not apply to all workers, neither do they apply all the time. Generally, AFDC advantages are limited to females who are heads of households, while unemployment is available only for a period (approximately 26 weeks) following on some work and therefore cannot be sought as a way of life completely. On the other hand, the increasing degree of the basic welfare advantage, a lot more generous standards in the granting of food stamp benefits, and the continuous pressure to elevate the general help recommend that the criteria now set by AFDC may emerge as the set of standards to be related to a broader group of welfare receivers within the foreseeable future” (Henderson, 1965).

Where Do We Go from Here?

“If we encounter a pattern of still steeper wage cost increases coupled with greater scarcity of unskilled and semi-skilled work, what type of effects can we anticipate?

Probably the hardest point for lots of drivers to accept is that severe, basic adjustments in the means we do business are in the offing. Since the hospitality sector have and been anchored in our very own practices, this is hard to approve. It took a Memphis developer Kemmons Wilson, to change the post-World War II lodging sector and a handful of creative food service drivers to establish the fast-food concept.

In the lodging market, several of the problems might be attributable to the splitting up of the driver's knowledge of what should be done from the owner's decision king power by the ignorance of lots of proprietors, informed as they are by a view of the lodging facility as an investment without necessarily appreciating the operating truths which regulate the long term success of that investment. Still, there are enough drivers of a typical cast of minds that they can rarely be excepted from a general statement regarding resistance to change”(Henderson, 1965).

Changed Materials

“If labour comes to be both scarcer and much pricier, the marketplace for ready foods is likely to broaden. Generally, it seems sensible to think that the huge food processor economy of scale benefits will come to be more noticeable as the hospitality industry's wage scale climbs. As is currently the case to a degree, furthermore, lack of availability of inexperienced labour along with its high cost will compel operators to move further toward the ready end of the raw-to-ready range in purchasing.

This larger market might raise the competition in that location, ideally resulting in improved quality as well as variety, and potentially with significant quantity boosts decrease in costs. It is premature to anticipate the growth of the food service facility into service-intensive retail outlet for manufactured good, however this may serve as an approximate description of direction for some sections of the industry.

The boosted use disposable service appears virtually certain, particularly in the light of the improving quality of disposable ware. This development is, nonetheless, clearly bounded by ecological restrictions, both regarding shortage of sources reflected in higher non-reusable ware rates and by disposal problems related to pollution. Increased concern with water quality might, however, operate to the drawback of long-term ware and therefore to the benefit of disposables” (Powers, 1974).

Political/legal

Political factors consist of regulations, that impact and limit companies and individuals in each country. The scopes being evaluated consist of the government perspective to international markets, the security, and financial policies of a nation and federal government bureaucracy. Legal and political forces are highly crucial as they cover lots of facets of organisation plan.

“Government policy affects market with governing bodies such as the Department of the Environment and the Department of Trade and Industry. These bodies create policies on the trading, limitations, and standards within their area. The policies created can influence businesses in different ways; in how their products are produced, promoted, and sold. It is essential for multinational corporations that each country has its own policies and political background. Several former centrally planned economies are still severely protected by the government.

In such an environment, it is more probable that propositions for a joint venture will certainly be accepted. It is said that the lawful ramifications of marketing a product worldwide are very complex. When a business internationalises after that it must keep within these legal systems, each country has their own legal system. The firm's technique might have to be adjusted when it comes to establishing advertising and marketing mix components in foreign markets. The legal setting must be analysed to figure out whether it would certainly affect the launch of a product into a new nation.

In lots of nations, federal government, as well as laws have a straight influence on product design. Regulation typically enforces minimum or special products requirements, which may require the form, kind, components or even the brand name. Federal government regulations and restrictions manage the content of promotion.

The law restricts the marketer's freedom, especially regarding the marketing message as well as visual presentation. Advertising activities likewise may have to be changed, depending upon the nation involved and the lawful systems that they use. For example, in France as well as China, door-to-door selling cannot be utilized as it is prohibited (Vrontis and Vronti, 2004)".

"Moreover, Germany restricts superlatives or relative insurance claims. The words 'better' and 'best' are words to be avoided. Price regulations may be another variable that a business needs to look at when considering internationalisation. In some nation's federal governments might manage the cost that is set for products. As an example, Ghana manages the producers' profit margins, which indirectly controls the cost paid by customers (Muhlbacher et al., 1999)".

"Worldwide fast-food firms should follow country-specific political needs, such as nationwide minimum wage policies, affecting costs. Hygiene as well as quality regulations differ significantly between countries and may affect the quality of items supplied by fast-food outlets (FDA, 2012)". Additionally, "Different countries set varying regulations regarding labelling as well as packaging. For instance, the UK government pressured firms to advertise healthy and balanced eating, and several fast-food firms have voluntarily included the calorie details on their items (BBC, 2011)".

"Worldwide operators must follow country-specific laws and regulation. This consists of opening hours, taxation, and work regulations such as the National Minimum Wage Regulations (1999) in the UK. Companies are frequently called for to satisfy nationwide food

requirements such as the demands laid out by the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA). In addition, authorities are becoming progressively anxious about childhood obesity associated with the industry and have tightened policies regarding targeting kids (WHO, 2012)”.

Economic

“Economic factors include factors that influence customer acquiring power and costs patterns. Economic trends are again, to a big level, bound up in government plan and are an important issue to businesses and marketing professionals due to the way they impact customer spending power. In periods of relative success, a consumer's disposable earnings will certainly be high and, therefore, there is a readiness to invest more money.

Cost becomes a less sensitive issue, and this influences advertising technique itself. During an economic crisis, however, the investing power reduces making the cost more appropriate. The differences that exist in between countries in various stages of economic and industrial advancement have a profound impact on price setting.

Distinctions in income levels may recommend the desirability of organized price variants. It is, consequently, important for fast-food restaurants such as Subway to comprehend that, in less developed countries, it is needed to set a lower price.

The limited buying power in less developed nations, frequently integrated with reduced degrees of literacy, postures issues for marketers on promotion. Although theoretically a business has a broad choice of promotional tools, in practice the choice of efficient tools is rather restricted. For example, in foreign less developed markets, Subway should try to use affordable techniques of promotion, or else the final price would certainly be past the reach of a lot of customers.

Despite the 2008 economic crisis and the decline in consumer confidence across the globe, average consumer fast-food costs have boosted (The Economist, 2010) due to convenience and low-cost. Consumers are still looking for the convenience of eating out but are drawn to the low prices of fast-food over table-service restaurants. (Financial Times, 2009).

Lots of fast-food chains have capitalised upon the economic downturn by introducing new deals along with their discounted food selections. Between 2005 and 2010, Latin America, Asia Pacific, Eastern Europe, and Russia made up to 89% of global development in the fast-food market (Passport, 2012)”.

Technological

“There are numerous research concerning the present technology in QSR and they primarily recommend that the potential for change within the existing technology is substantial. A picture emerges of an innovation that is past standard, ground-breaking research and moving at an accelerating rate into highly specialized applications. Specialised, high volume systems routed at a particular (food) raw materials or group of food are coming into their own, increasing the volume of specific items available, and therefore minimizing prices with economy of scale. Problems of handling particular items are relapsing and significantly the end product is a mix of items which, themselves, are currently highly processed by the time they get to the final processing steps.

A considerable point which arises from a factor to consider of the areas on Food Science and also engineering, which is confirmed-by area observation, is that any product or process advancement that benefits the independent also benefits the larger institutional procedure.

A number of the most current developments in equipment do offer unique benefits to large-scale food service operations and operations that learn to use massive food manufacturing in commissaries and other mass feeding contexts.

Considering that customer's view of restaurant prices are formed by the rate of alternating service, the availability of economies of scale in large-scale food manufacturing facilities, and the consequent capability of such operations to pass on cost savings to the visitors, might well lead the visitor so-to make unfavourable price comparison when dining in restaurants incapable to accomplish such economies.

One way in which some economies are being achieved in chain restaurants is through commissaries. The time might have come when food wholesalers offer the commissary function in abroad and varied prepared line of product, specified to regional preferences. The 'Neff' system developed by Schmidt (1991) certainly appears to offer advantages to those who can use such large food manufacturing systems as commissaries.” (Powers, 1974).

“Technological developments have made worldwide travelling and interactions more accessible to consumers and caused a situation in which social routines and fashions alter much quicker. Moreover, way of lives and attitude changes cause changes in product demands and how these products can be offered to customers.

Technological factors include forces that produce new technologies, developing new products

as well as market opportunities. It is based upon factors to consider regarding whether the local market has adequately established technologies to take full advantage of the product. It should be kept in mind that high technologies are needed to make complete use the variety of promotional techniques making use of alternate marketing media such as tv or internet sites (Vrontis and Vronti, 2004)".

"Subway's effective internationalisation can be partially attributed to the way the business has conquered technological issues. The systematic substitution of equipment for people and the carefully planned use and positioning of technology have helped each franchisee to be of the same high standard"(Subway, 2016).

"As customer experience with new technology raises, QSR's are utilizing channels such as social media networks and web sites to engage with their customers. For instance, McDonald's is the 9th most 'liked' brand on Facebook (CNBC, 2012)". Moreover, "digital displays allow outlets to change their menus efficiently, to suit the time-of-day and self-service ordering points have increased service speed and reduced labour costs"(NRA, 2012).

Socio-cultural

"Changes in spending power are likewise impacted by sociological market patterns. Evaluation of population variation recommends to marketers in which age groups, there is going to be the largest demand for goods. A baby boom, for instance, will certainly boost the need for child products, in recent years, a greater need for toys, academic products and children's clothes and so on.

Another arising trend is the changing family, with the conventional family unit of mother, father and two children in decline. The rise in one person household produces different requirements in residence items as houses require smaller sized products. Adjustments in demographics can, consequently, influence facts such as the growth, developing, packaging and promotion of items. It might likewise shape the organisational setting of techniques and strategic planning. In the case of Subway, several social forces greatly impacted its success in the UK. One aspect was the prevailing family member's structure in the UK and the trend towards a youth-orientated society. In the 1960s as well as the 1970s the decision-making function had transformed to such an extent that kids commonly made the choice of a place to eat. Because the strategy capitalised on these existing social trends, Subway's special emphasis on children and teenagers as advertising targets was largely successful.

Another vital element was that the value that UK society positioned on time favoured the intake of food with minimal time effort. Saving time, as a matter of fact, created the need for food purchased outside the home on an unexpected or impulse basis. The outcome was an expanding need for discounted food that was available at any time and that could be acquired with minimum shopping initiative. Economic factors are important for Subway in determining a customer's capability to purchase. Whether there is a purchase, depends mostly on cultural factors. Therefore, to recognize markets abroad, the business should have a gratitude of buyer behaviour.

Culture could be defined as institutions and other forces that influence a culture's basic values, perceptions, behaviours, and preferences. Culture consists of the entire heritage of a society transferred by word, literature, or any other type. It includes traditions, practices, religion, art, education, family, and language. While satellite TV as well as the global media are diminishing the world and homogenise customer tastes, society remains to pull in the opposite direction. Traditions and faiths run deep and can often conflict with global media messages. When Subway was launched in India, the chain decided not to have its Beef sandwiches as a result of deferring to the Hindu prohibition against beef consumption. The company rather offered chicken, tuna, and veggie sandwiches. In some countries, Subway has been forced to change its cooking techniques also; in Singapore as well as Malaysia, for instance, the beef that goes into sandwiches must be slaughtered according to Muslim law” (Subway, 2015)

“Increasing customer recognition about healthy lifestyles has pushed many fast-food restaurants to supply much healthier options within their food menu (BBC, 2011).

This consists of offering low-calorie options and salads alongside the food, and prominently displaying nutritional content. The fast-food industry has also been heavily criticised for targeting young children by including toys within children's meals (New York Times, 2003). Recently, in the UK, the broadcasting of 'junk food' adverts during commercial breaks in children's programmes has been banned following the increase in childhood obesity (BBC, 2007)”.

Environmental

“The climate and physical terrain of a country are very important ecological conditions which have a substantial effect on the demand and the sort of products offered. Before entering a new market, it is extremely important for Subway to think about the physical terrain and

climate in the appraisal. Elevation, temperatures, and humidity are several of the climatic conditions that can influence products in foreign markets.

Being environmentally friendly is another important concern to consider. Environmental groups for example forced McDonald's and Subway to lower their use of plastic and Styrofoam packaging. While McDonald's and Subway internal marketing research revealed that environmental issues will certainly have no impact on sales, they have agreed to deal with the Environmental Defence Fund, an environmental pressure group, to minimize unnecessary as well as harmful waste. Environmental lobbyists and federal governments are pressing the fast-food firms to become 'greener' (Greenpeace, 2012). Rainforests are being damaged to increase the location land for beef manufacturing to meet the demand for burgers (Kline, 2007)". Moreover, "Recycling is another global concern and in action, McDonald's embraced recyclable packaging. Increased environmental awareness amongst customers provides companies with a significant chance to place them as 'environment-friendly' to amass customer loyalty (National Pollution Prevention Centre for Higher Education, 1995)".

Urban Systems

"Professor Eugene Bazan identifies the effects of demography analysis as well as migration on the demand for food service, indicating the significance of raising urbanization. He examines the effect of lifestyle and outcome changes on the QSR's economic framework and the industry's response especially franchising, in meeting this demand.

These concerns are seen in a context of changing transportation which, subsequently, influences not only demand but the physical distribution systems which serve the food service market. While the techniques Professor Bazan employs in his essay are currently popular to social scientists, they have not been extensively applied in the area of food service. The implications of Dr Bazan's contributions are, for that reason, particularly interesting" (Powers, 1974).

Stakeholders

It is essential that international firms take into consideration and value their general public also known as stakeholders, their employees, suppliers, investors, as well as the consumer itself. How a customer and, the other 'publics' cited, view the company, as well as the products marketed, is very important, first, in order to analyse what market, you are in but, secondly, to assess whether the business image of the company is operating in a favourable

way. Public perception of your product permits it to be placed or rearranged to get to the needed target market and, as a result, to succeed.

“If you view your products as representing a specific image that is at odds with the general public understanding of it, certainly, your marketing approach is not operating properly. Furthermore, if your business itself is viewed in a negative light by actors both inside and outside of the company, it is required to take a few factors into consideration, the layout, quality, advertising, and strategy of what is offered to correct this and as a result, produce a feel-good factor. Having an excellent partnership with all publics is extremely advised for Subway” (Heavens, 2004).

Customer Tastes

“Customer taste is one more essential issue to take into consideration. Every company must carry out market research and should comprehend consumers' wants and needs. Based on that, it should create advertising techniques as well as methods to fulfil the demands and needs of its target audience. This is critical as, by taking on necessary adjustments, the firm can maintain its advertising and marketing alignment and go in line with the marketing concept.

Subway follows internationalisation advertising and marketing method which involves personalizing advertising and marketing techniques (this might additionally include pricing methods) for different areas of the world according to social, regional, and national differences in accordance with local demands. For that reason, the principle of 'Think global, act local' has been plainly adopted by Subway (Vignali, 2001)”

Corporate Management

There is term called corporate management accountability and this means managers are accountable for the overall performance of an organization during a specific time. Therefore, since managers are directing and conducting the business, they should be responsible for the operation outcome.

“Many of the causes for the failing of major firms (such as weak point in financial reporting system, middle management misconduct, environmental disaster, etc.) are simply the symptoms of what is perceived be the actual source of the issue that is failure of the corporate management accountability process. This failing may either originate from the inability to hold management to account, or the insufficiency of the management accountability process

that has failed to generate timely understanding into the actual operational status, directing concerned parties to embrace timely measures against undesirable scenarios” (Peter Drucker, 1985).

Corporate management accountability should assess these matters as:

- 1- The stakeholder’s desires and how they communicate with management
- 2- Delegating responsibilities amongst different management levels
- 3- Creating vision, mission, objectives, and goals from stakeholder’s expectations
- 4- Evaluating the management based on their authorities after 1 year
- 5- Performance evaluation and explanation
- 6- Correct the strategic mistakes after evaluation

Objectives of Corporate Management Accountability

Stakeholders can evaluate the performance of management and hold them accountable for that. They can firstly rate the performance of the management within the organization and secondly their performance in the industry and with other competitors.

“These two together may further enable the stakeholders to evaluate the firm’s relevant industry performance against the performance of other industries as well as the whole economy in which the business operates. Developing such a profound insight into the corporate management performance as well as the state of the business itself would provide stakeholders the opportunity to adopt adequate remedial, reinforce or strategic measures (decisions and actions), that would address both the past and the future concerns of the business” (Peter Drucker, 1985).

Most of the fast-food restaurants are part of a chain or a franchise so they do not operate individually. Consequently, managers of these QSRs must follow the guidelines and protocols of the franchisor. For example, the franchisor might decide to test a product at a location, even if the manager of that store prefers not to deal with this product.

Competition

“The issue of the competitive environment must possibly be among one of the most important issues. By gathering continuous information about rivals, such as their strategic strengths

and weak points, their goals, approach, methods, as well as response patterns and the sort of advertising and marketing activity/budget, a company can choose its own position in specific terms and plan for what challenges they are encountering in terms of competitor attacks. This info additionally can be used to interpret unexpected moves by competitors as well as just how they respond to a move you are about to take.

Porter (1980) and Doyle (1983) are both supporters of positioning strategy. Porter considers the external factors which impact a firm's competitive positioning. Doyle refers to the selection of the target audience segment which describes the customers. A business will certainly seek to serve and the selection of differential advantage specifying how it will compete with opponents in the sector.

Porter asserts that competition is the essential factor of success or failure of the firm which a successful competitive strategy can establish a profitable and sustainable position in the industry. Porter also claims that there are two essential concerns underlying the selection of a competitive approach: to start with, just how appealing is the industry concerning profitability and second, what are the determinants of a competitive position within an industry.

Porter's Five Forces

According to Porter, there are five competitive forces that will govern the regulations of the competition and these guidelines will dominate in any kind of sector both in domestic and international markets. The 5 forces are:

- 1-The entry of new competition into the market
- 2-The threat of substitutes or replacement products
- 3-The bargaining power of buyers
- 4-The bargaining power of suppliers
- 5-The rivalry between firms of the same sector”

(Porter, 1980)

Competitive Rivalry

Competitive rivalry is strong in this industry. There are many global chains as well as independent restaurants operating within this industry. Therefore, competition is mostly cost-based, and each competitor is focusing and investing on their products and services to cut-down the cost and as a result the final price. Exit cost is very low and the quantity of

restaurants can easily grow since they are mostly franchises. Advertising and branding are essential in this market and big brands like McDonald's and Subway spend huge amount of money for this purpose.

Threat of New Entrants

Threat of new entrants is moderate in this industry. The market is known with a few multinational QSR's like McDonald's, Subway, KFC, and Domino's. Customer loyalty is strong within this industry and brand recognition is well known as well. One of the reasons for this is the key players like Subway and McDonald's have different advertising and marketing campaigns in each country based on the culture and norms within that market. Therefore, new entrants find it difficult to compete with these big players as advertising marketing in general is very costly and without it, they would be unknown by many. Because of the higher spending power of these big players, it is easier for them to offer competitive pricing as well as producing new products in order to eliminate the threat from new entrants. Another fact is new entrants do not enjoy the economies of scale that these big players do hence making it very difficult to compete with them. However, with the rise of internet and social media it is easier for smaller players to have their voices heard by a larger audience at a low cost to attract more customers.

Threat of Substitutions

Threat of substitutions is moderate in this industry. Substitutes are vastly available and accessible for everyone. However, one of the components that reduces this threat is convenience. Food can be cooked at home at a lower cost but today people require the convenience that ready-made foods and QSR's offer. With our busy lifestyle today and being on-the-go all the time, QSR's are the fastest and offers the most value compared to the other options.

Power of Buyers

Power of buyers is moderate in this industry. This market is very price-sensitive and the switching cost is non-existent as a result it increases the buyer power. But the big players are always trying to reduce this threat by offering a wide range of products for different segments rather than one. For instance, Subway and McDonald's offer foods for children as well as a

breakfast menu and take-away options. Additionally, they offer new products and promotions occasionally, to attract even more customer.

Power of Suppliers

Power of suppliers is moderate in this industry. The supply chain within this market is very competitive, and the power for these suppliers is limited. In the UK alone there are over 20,000 farms providing quality ingredients for McDonald's. These farms provide raw resources for QSR's and then they will be transformed into food products. Because there are many suppliers within this market, their bargaining power is very low over the large QSR's.

Coca-Cola and Pepsi have dominated this market with their soft-drink supply. They also provide equipment like fridges and dispensers to the QSR's. This would market their brands and at the same time reduce the cost for these QSR's.

Figure 6: Porter's Five Forces – Fast-food Industry

Figure 6

Competitive Positioning

“Rumelt (1980) states that competitive advantages can generally be discovered in superior resources, superior skills, or a superior position. Resources and abilities enable a firm to do even more or do it better than the competition. Various sources as well as skills will certainly be required depending upon the industry or market section. Positional benefit is how the plan of these resources as well as abilities are utilized to out manoeuvre the competitors.

Positional advantage can be acquired by forward planning, higher skill, as well as resources or luck. When a leading position is acquired, it is tough for the competition to dislodge the incumbent company supplied the merit benefits continuation and that it is extremely pricey for rivals to take over. If environmental pressures stay constant position can remain constant. Positional benefit can take the form of size or scale, differentiation from competitors as well as successful trading names.

To be successful, a company requires to get both its technique and methods working in harmony to provide the optimal return bounded by performance. Both method and techniques must be created after a careful consideration of the situational environment” (Rumelt, 1980).

Marketing Planning

“Strategic marketing planning takes advantage of several analytical models that help to create a calculated view of the business as well as, made use of in decision-making. The Boston Consulting Group (BCG) matrix is just one of these models.

Redacted due to copyright restrictions.

Figure 7: The Boston Consulting Group matrix

Figure 7

Products or services as well as their respective approaches fall under four quadrants of the BCG matrix. The common starting factor for a new business is a question mark. If the product is new, it has no market share, but the predicted growth rate is good.

What commonly happens in an organisation is that administration is faced with a variety of these sorts of products but with a few resources to develop them all. Therefore, the tactical decision-maker must figure out which of the items to attempt to turn into a feasible item as well as which ones to drop from consideration.

Question marks are cash users in the organisation. Early in their life, they add no earnings and call for expenditures for market research, market testing and marketing to construct consumer recognition and awareness. For example, when Subway first introduced Hash Browns in their menu around 2 years ago it wasn't very successful at first but after some time and doing advertisements about it, now it has become one of their top selling snack.

It becomes a BCG matrix star if the appropriate choice is made, and the item chosen accomplishes a high market share. Stars have high market share in high-growth markets. Stars produce huge cash flows for the business but also call for huge mixtures of cash to sustain their development. Stars are typically the targets of big expenditures for advertising

and research and development to enhance the products as well as allowing them to establish a leading position in the industry. For example, Subway is introducing new sandwiches for their menu each year and these new products could become stars and further grow into cash cows.

Cash cows are business units that have high market share in a low-growth market. These are typically products in the maturity stage of the product life cycle. They are typically well-established products with vast consumer approval, so sales are usually high. The technique for such items is to invest a little money to maintain the item and draw away the big revenues created right into products with more long-term earnings potential, like question marks and stars. For example, Subway is very well known for a few of their sandwiches from Italian BMT to Veggie Pattie. These products are already well established and there is not much room for them to grow further but still contribute significantly to sales.

Dogs are businesses with low market share in low-growth markets. These are often cash cows that have shed their market share or question marks that the business has chosen not to grow. The recommended technique for these businesses is to stop investing in them for whatever income they will certainly produce and reinvest the money in more attractive businesses (question marks or stars). For example, often when Subway introduces a new sandwich or snack it doesn't go very well within some markets so then they need to remove that product to cut unnecessary costs.

Having used the Boston Consulting Group matrix above, it should also be noted that the BCG matrix suffers from limited variables on which to base resource allocation decisions among the businesses making up the corporate portfolio. Notice that the only two variables composing the matrix are relative market share and rate of market growth. Now consider how many other factors contribute to business success or failure.

Management talent, employee commitment, industry forces such as buyer and supplier power, environmental sensitive practices, corporate governance, corporate social responsibility, and the introduction of strategically equivalent substitute products or services, changes in consumer preferences and a host of others determine ultimate business viability. (Collins & Montgomery, 2005). The BCG matrix is best used, then, as a beginning point but certainly not as the final determination for resource allocation decisions as it was perhaps originally intended. In other words, just analysing the coordinates of a product into the dog's category would not necessarily mean that it should be singled out for termination. The technological, production and market synergies (with reference to a perceived 'total

offering’) to customers should also be parts of any elimination of ‘Dogs’. (Collins & Montgomery, 2005)

Further, if we consider Subway’s position as third in the market within the ‘restaurant based fast food’ market (this is as opposed to frozen homemade fast-food items) and the relative profits derived from this market, then it becomes clear that they are positioned in the ‘protect position’ quadrant of the Mckinsey matrix. This means that the company should concentrate efforts on maintaining its existing strength by investing to grow at maximum digestible rate.

Redacted due to copyright restrictions.

Figure 8: The Subway Company’s position in the Mckinsey matrix (Mckinsey, 2009)

Figure 8

It is also recommended that they can capitalise on 'first mover' advantage and consequently 'drive' market technology. This mirrors the ideas of the 'inside-out' or competencies-based method or the capabilities-based approach. For example, as a result of their size, Subway can, somewhat, drive the market” (Collins & Montgomery, 2005).

Strategic options

“Markides (1999) states that behind every successful company there is a superior strategy. The firm may have established this strategy via analysis, experimentation, intuition, or just by pure luck. No matter how it was developed, it is the strategy that underpins the success of the firm.

Planners have a remarkable quantity of both latitude and obligation in creating and stabilizing the strategic options of an organisation. The many decisions needed on a day-to-day basis make it frustrating for the managers in this market, taking into consideration the prospective consequences of incorrect decisions. One means to handle this intricacy is via categorisation; one category scheme is to categorize corporate-level strategy choices right into 3 various types or grand strategies (Porter, 1985).

These grand strategies include efforts to increase business operations (growth methods), reduce the range of business procedures (retrenchment strategies) or maintain the status quo (stability techniques).

Much more especially, development strategies are designed to expand an organisation's performance, typically as determined by sales, profits, product mix, market coverage, market share or other accounting and market-based variables. Common growth strategies entail several of the following:

1-With a concentration strategy the company tries to attain better market penetration by being very reliable to service its market with a minimal product (e.g., McDonalds in fast-foods).

2-By utilizing an upright combination strategy, the firm attempts to increase the scope of its current operations by undertaking business tasks previously done among its suppliers (in reverse combination) or by embarking on business tasks performed by a business in its channel of circulation (forward integration).

3-A diversification strategy requires relocating into different markets or adding different products to its mix. The approach is called concentric diversity if the products or markets are associated to existing product or service offerings. If development enjoys services or products not associated to the firm's existing business, the diversification is called conglomerate diversification.

They may decide to use a security strategy when companies are pleased with their present price of development and revenues. This approach is basically a continuation of existing strategies. Such approaches are usually happening in industries having reasonably stable settings. The company is usually making a steady revenue from operating a business that they see no demand or understanding to make the psychological and financial investment needed to undertake a growth approach.

Ultimately, retrenchment strategy entail a reduction in the range of a firm's activities, which also usually demands a reduction in number of staff members, sale of assets related to ceased

product and services lines and, in one of the most extreme cases, liquidation of the company. Nevertheless, Subway is certainly going after a growth approach via its continuous franchising worldwide and domestic developments.

Mintzberg (1994) talks about the principles of strategy as a position and method as a perspective. He keeps in mind, ‘as position, strategy looks down to the ‘x’ that marks the spot where the product meets the customer, and it looks out to the external marketplace. As perspective, in contrast, strategy looks inside the organisation, indeed, inside the head of the collective strategist but it also looks up to the grand vision of the enterprise’. Mintzberg gives an illustration to demonstrate the idea” (Mintzberg, 1994).

Value Chain

Viswanathan and Dickson (2006) give a conceptual three-factor model explaining the best circumstances for the standardisation of product or services for a worldwide organisation. Although it has been said that Subway utilizes a customised strategy for setting up its local strategies in the numerous nations in which it operates, the Viswanathan and Dickson model (Figure 9) encompasses aspects that, if considered by international business, might perhaps be made use of to enable them to capitalise on their experiences in other places for effectively launching as well as handling their expansion.

Redacted due to copyright restrictions.

Figure 9: Standardising global marketing strategy

Figure 9

Using this model helps supervisors and managers to evaluate the problems of the prospective host country regarding being beneficial for the transferability of tried and tested practices. If all 3 problems are not favourable then administration would at least be able to recognize where to concentrate or where new strategies would certainly need to be customised to suit the new situation” (Viswanathan and Dickson, 2006).

VRIO Analysis

Figure 10: VRIO model

Figure 10

“VRIO model is a structure (value-rarity-imitability-organisation) that is suitable for the understanding of the connection of competitive advantage. To have a better understanding, specifically for the administration in order to recognize the partnership of the resource and performance as this is just one of the vital to the organisation (Knott, 2015). However, this model does not bring into consideration the quick adjustments or unforeseeable circumstances that can bring about important adjustments in the execution of the policy. It ought to as a result be taken with factor to consider that the request for the analysis of VRIO merely seeks to find variables that have an impact on the competitive advantage of the firm in today state of advancement. Listed below table provided the VRIO analysis of Subway” (Lin et al, 2012).

A large black rectangular area covering the bottom half of the page. In the bottom-left corner of this area, there is a white rectangular box with a red border containing the text "Redacted due to copyright restrictions." in red font.

Table 3

Table 3: VRIO analysis on Subway

“Brand image is describing the customer perceived value of the brand memory itself. According to study from Kuo (2012) consumers with more engagement and experience would certainly be extra aware of the brand. The brand image is not the only element affecting the VRIO; it is a leverage in term of the connectivity of brand awareness, customer satisfaction as well as royalty. The heritage of the branding is among the keys that drive both branding image and loyalty along the road (Wiedmann et al., 2011)”.

“Human resource and culture are just one of the essential aspects throughout the industry consisting of fast-food industry. Human resources are outstanding in regards to their ability for development and their ability to understand and satisfy the limits, to solve prospective or existing problems and needs (Bibu and Munteanu, 2016)”.

Porter’s Generic Strategy

“Generic strategy which could be implemented throughout all markets, kinds, or dimensions of organizations. A competitive approach is an approach and plan that produce sustainable and lucrative calculated position against the forces that force market rivalry (Leitner & Guldenberg, 2010). The generic competitive method for Subway is cost leadership which associates with cost effectiveness.

TOWS Analysis	Strengths 1. Strong market position 2. Localization 3. Robust financial performance 4. Brand loyalty	Weakness 1. Waste control 2. Limited food choices 3. Consumer switching cost 4. Health conscious
Opportunities 1. New product development 2. Potential growth in developing country 3. Globalization	SO S1- O1 S1 -O3 S2- O2 S3- O2	WO W1- O1 W2- O1 W2- O1 W4- O1
Threat 1. Intense competition 2. Healthier lifestyle conscious awareness 3. Environmental concern	ST S1 -T1 S4- T1 S4-T2	WT W1-T3 W2- T1 W4- T2 W1-T3

Table 4

Table 4: TOWS Analysis

It is suggested that efficient advertising techniques and strategies cannot be created without first, analysing the environment in which the business operates. Several irrepressible components impact Subway's external as well as internal approaches and tactical implementation. These groups of elements include the PESTLE (political, financial, social, technical, legal, and ecological), framework of the market and competition being encountered (Porter, 1980), evaluation of its stakeholders, customers, as well as product adjustment within its internationalisation method, BCG matrix, Value Chain and VIRO evaluation.

All these elements are critical to a business's tactical decision making. The level of comprehending that exists in these connections will certainly determine the success of a business” (Porter, 1980).

The fast-food sector is identified as an inexpensive, high-turnover market with strong competitive rivalry. After a complete market analysis, Subway is identified as one of the key players in this industry but not the market leader as they desire.

Employee Turnover

There is a myth that people holding managerial positions in the hospitality industry do not need formal education in hospitality management to achieve career success. Many believe that running a restaurant requires only money, experience, and a cook. When recruiting for a managerial position, some personnel or human resource staff executives consider it better and easier to hire, train, and satisfy a person who had no college degree in hospitality management, than reforming a person who graduated with what they consider unrealistic ideas taught by his or her university professors in their ivory tower.

In addition, the hospitality industry has an image problem; many people do not consider a hospitality manager as a professional like a lawyer, doctor, or engineer. Consequently, some people have doubts about hospitality management education and the difference it could make in professional development.

This is the most important part of this thesis as there is substantial evidence that employee turnover is highly related to job satisfaction and performance, therefore, employee turnover research is highly prioritised by this study and more work has been done to address this issue including a separate survey on this matter.

As this is and has been an ongoing issue within this industry, the desirability of examining and evaluating previous evidence becomes more apparent. However, with approximately 100 years of research to consider, a typical literature review presented certain practical constraints, especially about reconciling controversies and reduction of such a mass of information to manageable proportions. Further, several such reviews have already been accomplished. Consequently, some approach other than the usual literature review seemed advisable.

This section presents reviews of five major approaches to the study of work motivation/satisfaction. The approaches to be discussed are:

1. Two-Factor Theory
2. Equity Theory
3. Instrumentality-Expectancy Theories,
4. Cornell Studies in Satisfaction, and
5. Need-Fulfilment Theories.

Although there are other theories of work motivation such as Korman's (1970) "balance" theory and Locke's (1968,1969)goal-oriented theory, the theories selected for discussion were believed to be the major theories in terms of the amount of research devoted to them and in terms of potential implications for the QSR research. The discussion of each of the five major approaches has three objectives:

1. The discussion attempts to clearly describe the basic concepts of each approach
2. Major modifications of the basic approach, if any, are discussed
3. A brief assessment of the relative strengths and weaknesses of each approach is presented

From the review and implications certain conclusions were drawn which appear relevant to QSR's satisfaction/retention research and its relationship with performance within this industry. These are as follows:

QSR's have made some use of theories in job satisfaction/retention research. Two-factor and need-fulfilment theories have been used most frequently, but there are indications of increasing use of more recent theoretical developments. An eclectic theoretical orientation for QSR appears desirable at present.

An important first step for QSR's is the definition of job satisfaction in this industry. Such an effort should determine the relevant dimensions of job satisfaction from the point of view of both employees and customers.

Certain sets of variables that may produce satisfaction/dissatisfaction were considered. The variables which appear to warrant further systematic investigation were categorized as individual, situational, individual-situational, and output variables. A suggested sequence for studying these variables and certain measurement problems were examined.

“A common definition of turnover in the hospitality industry is when an employee leaves the organization and must be replaced. This can be voluntary and/or involuntary. In either case, the bottom line is that the employee must be replaced, and costs will be incurred as a result of turnover (Eisen, 1982)”.

Turnover becomes a problem if the turnover rate in an organization is too high. The turnover rate is usually determined by dividing the number of employee separations during a period (month, year) by the average number of employees during the same period, then multiplying this value by 100 to obtain a percentage of the turnover rate.

Labour turnover costs have a substantial influence on profit performance. The area of human resource accounting has established considerably today and has the potential to help in measuring turnover costs. There are primarily two major categories, namely, tangible (measurable) and intangible (immeasurable) costs.

Tangible Cost Factors

This category includes expenses for employment performance, breaking in, training, separation, and additional costs for social security tax and unemployment insurance. Employment expenses include direct and indirect costs associated with hiring new employees. Performance costs are the costs of substandard work performance by a new employee. Performance costs continue until the employee's productivity reaches the average employee output for the same job.

Breaking-in costs include all expenses for supervisory and non-supervisory personnel in connection with on-the-job training of a new employee, while training costs include any formal training program expenses that are not accounted for under breaking-in costs.

Separation costs include cost incurred as a direct result of an employee's separation from the

organization, for instance, lost production. A more recent statistic indicates that job turnover costs 1/12 of the annual salary of the job (Vallen and Abbey, 2018).

Intangible Cost Factors

Turnover can negatively influence employees who stay on the job. It can result in lower morale, higher chances of accidents and absenteeism, lower management efficiency and effectiveness, and poor public relations. Although no formulas can be provided to measure these costs, they are no doubt potential threats to the profit of an organization.

UK Restaurants

“The Restaurant industry is characterised by a reasonably high proportion of franchises. Brand names such as McDonalds, Burger King as well as Subway utilize this model.

McDonalds, for instance, has over 1,250 restaurants in the UK of which roughly 70 per cent are operated by franchisees, as well as approximately 120,000 people are employed by McDonalds UK. These brand names run along with smaller proportions of independent restaurants.

Over the medium and longer-term, development in the variety of restaurants and take-away establishments has been driven by customer and demographic trends, with people (especially youngsters) eating outside of the house a lot more regularly. In this context essential brands have raised their market share. Office for National Statistics data on employment and turnover or in short VAT and/or PAYE based enterprises in the accommodation and food services industry in the UK reveals that complying with a decrease in both work and turnover between the year ending March 2010 to the year ending March 2011, work has raised by 19 percent from 1.74 million in 2011 to 2.17 million in 2016 while turnover raised by a similar percentage.

Throughout the market, the total variety of facilities expanded from over 114,500 to over 135,600 between 2010 and 2018 (a boost of 18%). The variety of restaurants grew by 40%, so demonstrating significant development also within an extremely competitive, low pay and enhancing cost environment. Nonetheless, growth patterns varied by the size of the company, while the varieties of facilities enhanced in each sub-sector and size band, the rate of increase differed.

For instance, while the number of micro-organisations increased from simply over 95,000 to just over 104,000 from 2010-2018 (a rise of just under 10%), the share of micro-organisations

fell from 83% to 77%. The share of small organisations across all 3 sub-sectors expanded (from 16% to 21%), and the share of medium-sized organisations, utilizing 50 to 249 of personnel, also enhanced (from 1% to 1.4% of the total).

While the variety of establishments in the restaurants as well as event catering sub-sectors grew at every size band, the result for beverage serving activities was much more mixed. There are contrasting patterns in terms of expanding varieties of small (e.g.) cafe, but a marked decline in the variety of small public houses in less flourishing areas and a development in larger pubs (mostly offering food) in even more thriving localities.

The number of establishments declined from over 45,600 in 2010 to 37,800 in 2018, with a significant decrease in the variety of micro-businesses only partially offset by a small boost in the various other establishment size bands” (IFF Research, 2019).

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**Figure 11: Number of enterprises by employment size
(IFF Research, 2019)**

Figure 11

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Figure 12: Number of enterprises by turnover
(IFF Research, 2019)

Figure 12

Figure 13 shows that “productivity (measured as output per hr in current prices) in the market raised progressively over the period 1997 to 2018. In 2018, the average outcome per hour was £17.37, which is twice of what it was in 1997 (£8.42). The economic crisis of 2008/9 appears to have had very little influence on market productivity” (IFF research, 2019).

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Figure 13: Labour productivity in the Food and Beverage Services division, 1997-2019
(IFF research, 2019)

Figure 13

Satisfaction and Retention Relationship

Job satisfaction has been a popular subject of research in industrial psychology since the appearance of Hoppock's (1935) book on the topic almost four decades ago. One of the few consistent findings during this period of research has been the relationship between satisfaction on the job and the decision to remaining or depart from the work situation. “Brayfield and Crockett (1955) in a landmark review of satisfaction research, concluded that there is some evidence to support a positive relationship between employee attitudes and employment stability”.

Additionally, “Vroom (1964) concludes that the evidence points to a consistent negative relationship between satisfaction and the probability of resignation. He also cited studies which indicated that turnover is highest during periods of low unemployment”.

In a review of eight studies which investigated the satisfaction-tenure relationship, Schuh (1967) found positive relationships between satisfaction and tenure. A more recent review (Porter & Steers, 1972) shows that the results of 13 out of 14 studies revealed significant negative relationship between satisfaction and turnover. Porter and Steers (1972) concluded that the data support a model which argues that turnover is a function of the extent to which the work situation meets the expectations of workers in terms of rewards.

Although the satisfaction-tenure relationship has received consistent support, the strength of the reported relationships has varied considerably from situation to situation. The reported correlations in the Schuh (1967) review ranged from .20 to .42. Commenting on similar sized correlations, Vroom (1964) points out that the typical study omits an important variable or set of variables. Since the individual who leaves, an organization is usually moving to some other organization, the analysis should take this into account. Thus, satisfaction with the old organization as well as anticipated satisfaction with the new organization affects the decision.

Nevertheless, the research evidence points to the existence of a consistent relationship between satisfaction and tenure in organizations’ possible that stronger relationships can be demonstrated between satisfaction and tenure if the attractiveness of alternatives is considered as well as the attractiveness of one's present situation.

Justification for Job Satisfaction Research in the QSR

Based on the foregoing statements there appear to be two closely related reasons for the QSR to be concerned with the job satisfaction of its employees. First, in a time when individuals are demanding more of a job than economic return, the QSR should provide more satisfying work in order to be able to compete in the labour market. Second, if the QSR expects to retain those employees who enlist, individuals should be afforded the opportunity to make use of their talents and training and perceive the QSR as an environment conducive to personal growth and development.

The matter of performance effectiveness and productivity may offer still another reason for QSR concern regarding job satisfaction. Although there is substantial agreement regarding the satisfaction-retention relationship, considerable controversy exists regarding the strength of any performance-satisfaction relationship (Kuhn, Slocum, & Chase, 1971; Lawler, 1968a). An earlier review (Brayfield & Crockett, 1955) indicated a limited relationship between satisfaction and performance, whereas Herzberg, Mausner, and Snyderman (1959) concluded there was frequent evidence that positive job attitudes are favourable to increased productivity. Conversely, Lawler and Porter (1967b) opposed the common assumption that employee satisfaction affects performance. Perhaps a reasonable assessment of the current status of this controversy from job enrichment research is that at least the two variables go together in some manner. Regardless of the view taken, better understanding of the nature of the existence of such a relationship should provide additional justification for the study of job satisfaction.

Herzberg Two-Factor Theory

Basic Concepts and Modifications

The approach which has probably generated the most research and certainly the most controversy is Herzberg's two factor theory (Herzberg et al., 1959; Herzberg, 1966). Herzberg's (1959, 1966) work broke with some of the traditional experimental approaches to job satisfaction. His data collection techniques emphasized structured, in-depth interviews of job incumbents, and attempted to determine what job incidents or events were associated in the past with high satisfaction and what incidents or events were associated with high dissatisfaction.

These responses were subjected to content analyses and various factors or commonalities in the sequences were identified. Based on such analyses, Herzberg, and his associates (1959) concluded that certain types of incidents were frequently associated with feelings of satisfaction on the part of the workers, and certain qualitatively different types of factors were regularly associated with dissatisfaction.

“The ‘satisfiers,’ or ‘motivates’ as they came to be called, included job content factors such as Achievement, Recognition, Advancement, Responsibility, and Work Itself. The ‘dissatisfiers’ or ‘hygiene’s’ were context-type factors such as Company Policies and Practices, Interpersonal Relations with Co-Workers, Interpersonal Relations with Supervisors, Technical Aspects of Supervision, Salary, and Working Conditions(Herzberg et al., 1959)”. He postulated that “satisfaction is a function of both the ‘satisfiers’ and the ‘dissatisfiers’. If the positive aspects of both the ‘satisfiers’ and ‘dissatisfiers’ are present at sufficient levels, then satisfaction will be high. However, if the satisfiers are removed, indifference but not dissatisfaction will result. Dissatisfaction will occur only when the negative aspects of the dissatisfies are present.

Thus, the positive aspects of these dissatisfiers constitute necessary but not sufficient conditions for satisfaction” (Herzberg et al., 1959). Job satisfaction is seen as being a two-dimensional construct; hence, the label, "two-factor theory."

The original study from which the theory was "induced" was based on interviews with approximately 203 engineers and accountants in the Pittsburgh area. Subsequent research reported by Herzberg (1966) tested the theory with 15 groups of employees, including both males and females, hourly and salaried groups, United States, and foreign workers.

Herzberg (1966) claims that predictions from the theory were supported by the data from these groups (total N = 1017) in 97 percent of the cases. In all these studies the original Herzberg (1959) methodology, or a slight variation of it, was employed.

Several writers have cited evidence interpreted as critical of the two-factor theory (Ewen, 1964; Ewen, Smith, Hu lin, & Locke, 1966; Friedlander, 1963; Graen, 1966, 1968; Hu lin & Smith, 1967). Other writers have criticized the research supporting the theory on methodological grounds (Burke, 1966; Dunnette, 1965; House & Wigdor, 1967; Lindsay, Marks, & Gorlow, 1967; Malinovsky & Barry, 1965; Vroom, 1964).

The critics were the subject of some counter attacks (Herzberg, 1966; Whitsett & Winslow, 1967; Winslow & Whitsett, 1968). Even though this often-heated controversy has raged for over 10 years, the basic question of the status of the two-factor theory has not been settled. The following assessment by Dunnette, Campbell & Hakel (1967), repeated by House & Wigdor (1967), seems appropriate: "the Two-Factor theory is an oversimplification of the relationships between motivation and satisfaction, and the sources of job satisfaction and dissatisfaction."

Although this observation seems appropriate considering the conflicting evidence, it could also be said about any other theory of work motivation currently in existence. Perhaps the Herzberg (1966) theory is more of an oversimplification than other theories. However, a more basic flaw seems to be the ambiguity with which its proponents have stated it. Much of the controversy seems to be the result of differing views of what is the "two-factor theory" (King, 1970 and Lindsay et al., 1967).

Lindsay et al, (1967) state: "It seems apparent that part of the ambiguity surrounding the Herzberg theory might be attributable to methodological inconsistencies and the lack of a formal and logically consistent statement of the relations among title variables of interest (p. 330)".

In another study, King (1970) attempted to reduce the ambiguity surrounding the two-factor theory by formally stating five versions of the theory that "have been stated or implied by various researchers (p.19)." These five versions represent varying degrees of strength. The five versions defined by King (1970). are summarized below.

- 1- "All motivators (Ms) combined contribute more to job satisfaction (S) than to job dissatisfaction (D), and all hygiene's (Hs) combined contribute more to D than to S.
- 2- All Ms combined contribute more to S than do all Hs combined, and all Hs combined contribute more to D than do all Ms combined. I,
- 3- Each M contributes more to S than to D, and each H contributes more to D than to S.
- 4- Theory III holds, and in addition, each principal M contributes more to S than does any H, and each principal If contributes more to D than does any M.
- 5- Only Ms determine S, and only Hs determine D".

(King, 1970).

In discussing the different versions, King (1970) points out that it is not clear which version of the theory is the "basic" theory according to Herzberg (1966). In various writings, Herzberg (1966) seems to imply at times that version II is "the" theory, and at other times that versions III or V represent the theory.

On the other hand, some critics of the theory do not share a common view of which is the "real" theory. Thus, their attacks are directed toward different versions. For example, "House and Wigdor (1967) apparently acknowledged that replications of the original experiment supported Theory III: however, in secondary analysis of this data they criticised the two-factor theory for failing to meet the requirements of Theory IV (King, 1970)." Lindsay et al., (1967) on the other hand apparently determined that version V represented "the" two-factor theory.

After r. viewing those studies which were determined relevant to one of the versions of the study, King (1970) drew the following conclusions.

"It is concluded that (a) two of these versions are invalid, as they are not supported by any empirical studies, (versions IV and V) ; (b) another version is invalid, as its alleged empirical support merely reflects experimenter coding biases (version III) ; and (c) the validities of the remaining two versions are, at present, indeterminate, as they have not been adequately tested in studies where defensive biases inherent in certain self-report measures are eliminated (versions I and II) (p. 181)."

King's (1970) analysis of the two-factor controversy seems to shed considerable light on the problems inherent in the theory which have produced the plethora of conflicting results. Until the proponents clarify their statements of the basic postulates of two-factor theory, it seems likely that the controversy will continue. If the theory is clarified and stated in a testable form, the controversy should begin to produce lighter and less heat.

Assessment of Two-Factor Theory

The emphasis of the Herzberg (1966) theory is on situational variables. The motivators and hygiene are situational characteristics. The theory does not allow for differences in individual responses to situational characteristics. In fact, Herzberg (1966) cites evidence to support his contention that the results (i.e., frequency of incumbent's reports of motivators and hygiene factors) are stable across various subgroups formed based on age, job classification, education, or personality characteristics.

“This conclusion seems to run counter to a considerable amount of evidence in the field of industrial psychology. Evidence from the research of the Work Adjustment Project at the University of Minnesota seems to have established that individuals differ in terms of their preferences for various reinforcers in jobs (Weiss, 1969)”.

Tuttle and Cunningham (1972) demonstrated differences in average interest and need scores of incumbents across occupational clusters. It hardly seems necessary to document dm statement that individuals and occupational groups vary in terms of abilities, benefits, and needs.

The fact that the Herzberg (1966) theory fails to recognize such differences in attempting to account for work motivation seems to be a serious weakness of the theory. Admittedly, life would be much simpler (although rather dull) if all individuals desired the same rewards from a job. The rather simplistic assumption that the way to make people happier and produce more is to fill their job with more motivators, can lead to some unfortunate consequences. It implies that job enrichment (i.e., increasing motivators) is a panacea.

It may be true that, on the average, professional workers are "motivated" more by factors inherent in the job itself than by extrinsic factors. It may even be true for most non-professional workers. However, before a manager jumps to the conclusion that It is "true" for his employees, it would seem prudent to verify the assumption in his situation.

In his latest book, Herzberg (1966), acknowledges the fact that individuals differ in terms of their preferences. He mentions that individuals can be characterized as "motivator seeking," "hygiene seeking," "motivator fulfilled," etc. However, no mechanism is built into the theory to consider individual differences in reactions to work characteristics. Thus, it seems that the two-factor theory lacks comprehensiveness, in addition to its lack of explicitness.

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Figure 14: Theoretical Model: Herzberg's Motivation-Hygiene Theory

Figure 14

Equity Theory

“Basic Concepts and Modifications. Equity theory grew out of early work with the concepts of relative deprivation (Merton & Kitt, 1950; Stouffer, Suchman, DeViney, Star, & Williams, 1949) and distributive justice (Homans, 1950, 1953, 1961; Zalesnik, Christensen Roethlisberger, 1958)”.

Additionally, “The basic assumption of equity theory is that individuals have an expectation of a ‘fair’ or ‘equitable’ rewards level which they should receive from a social exchange. To the extent that this equitable level is not met by the actual rewards, feelings of inequity are generated. It is further assumed that feelings of inequity are unpleasant, and that the individual adopts various strategies to reduce this perceived inequity (Merton & Kitt, 1950; Stouffer, Suchman, DeViney, Star, & Williams, 1949)”.

According to Vroom (1964), “several statements of the theory were made independently (Adams, 1963; Homans, 1961; Patchen, 1961). Since, again according to Vroom (1964), the different statements do not appear to have any testable differences, the statement of the theory by Adams (1965) will be discussed”.

Nature of Inputs and Outcomes. Basic to the theory are the concepts of Input and Outcome. Inputs are those attributes which are brought to the exchange, and which are seen as relevant

for the exchange. An attribute is relevant if the person expects to receive a return. An outcome is an individual's receipt from the exchange.

Outcomes may be positive, i.e., pay, status, good parking place, panelled office, or negative; i.e., monotony, poor working conditions, injury, insecurity. An attribute, or a return, functions as an Input or Outcome only if it is perceived as an Input or Outcome by the person. In addition, an outcome must be perceived as an outcome, and it must have some marginal utility to function as an outcome.

Social Comparison Process. Inherent in equity theory is the notion of social comparison. The social comparison process involves a comparison between the inputs and outcomes of oneself (Person) and the inputs and outcomes of another person (Other).

The reference, Person or Other, is presumed to be chosen by Person and will be someone comparable to Person on one or more attributes. Frequently this reference Person will be a co-worker. In the social comparison, Person develops expectations concerning what is a fair input-outcome ratio based on his own background and a consideration of the perceived input-outcome ratio of the reference Person.

Methods of Reducing Inequity

As mentioned above, the theory assumes that inequity is an unpleasant condition, and that Person will attempt to reduce the feeling of inequity. Adams (1965) mentions six methods which might be employed by Person to reduce inequity. These will be described briefly.

- 1- "Person alters his inputs. Person may affect the perceived ratio by either raising or lowering his inputs. Although some inputs such as age, sex, and race cannot be altered, others, such as the amount of effort expended, can be altered.
- 2- Person alters his outcome & Some outcomes are subject to Person's control or influence. One direct approach to, increasing outcomes is to simply ask for a raise. More indirect methods include complaining to a union representative, seeking more interesting work activities, etc
- 3- Person cognitively distorts input and outcomes. This mechanism is quite like the psycho-analyst's concept of rationalization. It may involve a cognitive distortion of the value, importance, or relevance of inputs or outcomes in order to lower or raise their worth,

- 4- Person may leave the field. This represents a direct approach to reduction of inequity. Person may quit the job or request a transfer.
- 5- Person may act on Other. This strategy involves Person acting directly or indirectly on Other to either raise or lower his Inputs or Outcomes. In an extreme form, Person might sabotage Other's work which would have the effect of lowering Other's inputs. Another approach might attempt to get a 'rate buster' to voluntarily lower his Inputs.
- 6- Person may change his object of comparison. This only applies when Person and Other are in an exchange relationship with a third party, such as an employer. This would require Person to determine some dimensions of non-comparability between himself and Other".

(Adams, 1965).

Adams (1965) sets forth six propositions which attempt to account for the mode of inequity reduction which will be adopted by Person.

- 1- "Person will maximize positively valent outcomes and the valence of outcomes.
- 2- He will minimize increasing inputs that are effortful and costly to change.
- 3- He will resist real and cognitive changes in inputs that are central to his self-concept and to his self-esteem. To the extent that any of Person's outcomes are related to his self-concept and to his self-esteem, this proposition is extended to cover his outcomes.
- 4- He will be more resistant to changing cognitions about his own outcomes and inputs than to changing his cognitions about Other's outcomes and inputs.
- 5- Leaving the field will be resorted to only when the magnitude of inequity experienced is high and other means of reducing it are unavailable. Partial withdrawal, such as absenteeism, will occur more frequently and under conditions of lower inequity.
- 6- Person will be highly resistant to changing the object of his comparisons, Other, once it has stabilized over time and, in effect, has become an anchor"

(Adams, 1965).

Adams (1965) admits that although these propositions are very crude, they provide some basis for predicting the form inequity resolution will take. No basis is given for determining which of the propositions is likely to be dominant.

Extension of Equity Theory. Pritchard (1969) presents a review of some research dealing with equity theory predictions and concludes: "The research supports equity predictions in

the area of underpayment, but the overpayment effects have not been satisfactorily demonstrated (p. 176)."

He proceeds to suggest an elaboration of the theory as proposed by "Adams (1965) in three areas:

1. The determinants of inequity
2. Dissatisfaction resulting from inequity
3. Responses to dissatisfaction"

(Adams, 1965).

Determinants of Inequity. Pritchard (1969) elaborates on the nature of the social comparison process by stating explicitly that Person can serve his own Other. In other words, Person can use himself as the reference Person as well as someone else. Based on one's history and knowledge of market values, he has developed internal standards which allow him to determine the fairness of his outcome/input ratio. Pritchard (1969) hypothesizes that feelings of inequity arise first and foremost from the correspondence between Person's own inputs and outcomes. If his inputs exceed outcomes, he will experience feelings of inequity apart from the outcome/input ratio of anyone else.

Pritchard (1969) accepts Adams' (1965) proposition regarding the Person's attempt to maximize positively valent outcomes. By Adams' (1965) formulation, this maximization process is bounded by the equity situation, i.e., Person will maximize outcomes until he reaches or approaches a state of inequity compared to the reference person.

Pritchard (1969) adds to this process the concept of psychological distance between participants in the exchange relationship. This concept assumes that exchange relationships can be ordered on a continuum ranging from very intimate relationships, which are characterized by a high amount of psychological contact to highly distant relationships which have a minimum amount of psychological contact.

Given this notion, it is possible to make differential predictions concerning the response to overpayment inequity as a function of the nature of the exchange relationship. Overpayment inequity is expected to be greater as the relationship becomes less distant. An individual overpaid by his employer (an impersonal relationship) would experience less inequity than a person selling his house at a price considerably above the market value to his close friend.

Dissatisfaction Resulting from Inequity

According to Adams (1965), one of the behavioural consequences of inequity is expressed dissatisfaction. As mentioned earlier, inequity can either be from underpayment or overpayment.

If an individual's inputs exceed his outcomes (underpayment), he will experience inequity and, therefore, dissatisfaction. In this case, the dissatisfaction will be directed toward the person, group, organization, or system which is perceived as controlling his outcomes.

In the case of overpayment, Pritchard's (1969) notion of psychological distance alters the predictions. If a person is over-rewarded in a direct exchange relationship, he will experience inequity and, therefore, dissatisfaction with the controller of rewards, himself. If, on the other hand, he is overpaid by.

His employer, he will feel that this is the fault of the system. Since Person is not the controller of rewards, it does not produce feelings of inequity, although he may feel sorry that his co-workers weren't as lucky as he. In this case, Person was over rewarded but did not experience inequity, and therefore would not express dissatisfaction.

Summary of Pritchard's (1969) Extensions

Pritchard's (1969) primary contribution to equity theory as stated by Adams (1965) is an elaboration of the conditions under which Person will experience over-payment inequity. This extension of the theory should help account for some of the difficulty researchers have encountered in attempting to produce overpayment inequity effects.

His other contribution represents mainly a different emphasis from Adams (1965) rather than a modification. Pritchard (1969) allows oneself to be an Other for the comparison process. This can be used to account for inequity in the absence of a comparison person. At the same time, it raises the new issue of the means used by Person to combine the Person-self inequity with the Person "Real Other" inequity to arrive at some "total" amount of inequity.

If a combination is not made, what are the trade-offs between the two sources of inequity? Pritchard (1969) gives some hints in this regard, but the basic question remains. Thus, while this extension offers some clarity, it raises new questions.

Assessment of Equity Theory

“It seems proper to characterize Equity Theory as an interactionist theory. Individuals differ in terms of the relevant Inputs they bring to the work situation. Situations differing terms of the Outcomes they provide. The social aspects of the situation are represented by the concept of the reference person or group. Therefore, it seems that all the ingredients necessary to consider the theory interactionist are present” (Adams, 1965).

There are some distinguishing features, however. One distinguishing feature is the point of view, or frame of reference taken. The theory is very individualistic. The orientation is always through the eyes of the actor. Inputs and Outcomes which are perceived to be functioning by the actor may or may not correspond to the Inputs and Outcomes perceived to be functioning by other parties to the exchange relationship.

Thus, concepts such as the "objective" level of Outcomes or "objective" level of Inputs are irrelevant unless their perceived level corresponds to that objective standard.

The most distinguishing feature of equity theory is the nature of the correspondence function. This function is a ratio of Outcomes to Inputs. To the extent that this value is less than 1, inequity, dissatisfactions, and action to restore the value to 1 are produced. To the extent that the value is greater than 1, the consequences are not clear.

According to Pritchard (1969), a value greater than 1, in a direct exchange relationship, would produce the same results as a value less than 1. However, in an exchange with a third-party, a value greater than 1 would produce satisfaction and no feelings of inequity.

Depending on the specific version of the theory accepted, equity theory postulates a single function for relating Inputs to Outcomes and makes specific predictions.

In most applications of the theory, the range of Inputs has been rather vague. Some experiments are conducted as if the amount of effort expended were the only relevant input (Pritchard, Dunnette, & Jorgenson, 1972). Another investigation considered factors as specific as place of birth (Adams, 1965). Thus, there are few guidelines for defining, much less measuring, the relevant inputs in any situation.

The situation is somewhat better on the Outcomes side. Although equity studies have taken a very narrow approach to the range of relevant Outcomes (money has been the primary concern), there is considerable research from other approaches suggesting several other relevant dimensions of Outcomes. Furthermore, there is some agreement as to what

dimensions are relevant and some measures exist (Smith, Kendall, & Hulin, 1969; Weiss, Dawis, England, & Lofquist, 1967).

The theory itself places no limitations on the Outcome dimensions that are considered relevant. Thus, researchers testing the theory should investigate its relevance in dealing with a wider range of Outcomes than has normally been the case.

Instrumentality Expectancy Theories

Basic Concepts and Modification

Perhaps the most prominent theory among active researchers in the field can be labelled instrumentality or expectancy theory. The ideas which are incorporated into the theory are not new since they borrow from writings of Lewin (1938), Rotter (1955), Atkinson (1958), and Tolmali (1959). The first attempt at an expectancy theory of work motivation was the path-goal model of Georgopolous, Mahoney, and Jones (1957).

The first formal statement of an expectancy theory of work motivation was made by Vroom (1964). Vroom's (1964) work was a significant milestone in the development of a theory of work motivation. He stated a theoretical position and then reviewed a large body of research dealing with various aspects of the motivation literature in terms of his framework. This effort highlighted many of the deficiencies of past research and pointed out vividly some research needs in the field. His work represents a tremendous step toward some order in a field which has known only disarray.

There is some question as to whether Graen's (1969) modification of Vroom's (1964) theory and the Porter and Lawler (1968a) versions should be considered separate or not. Heneman and Schwab (1972) argue that from the standpoint of predicting employee performance, they are essentially the same.

Vroom's (1964) Model

Since Vroom's (1964) model was the starting point, it seems appropriate to begin with a discussion of the concepts of his model. The central concepts were valence, instrumentality, expectancy, and force. Each of these will be discussed in the following paragraphs.

Vroom (1964) begins with the basic assumption that individuals have preferences among various "states of nature". He refers to these states of nature as Outcomes. Preferences among

Outcomes are based on feelings of attraction (positive or negative) or indifference toward these outcomes. Such feelings of positive or negative affect, Vroom (1964) calls valence. Valence is defined as "affective orientations toward particular outcomes (p. 151)".

Since individuals desire to obtain certain outcomes, to avoid others, and are indifferent to still others, it is assumed that valences can take a wide range of positive and negative values. One other point should be mentioned about valence.

Vroom (1964) explicitly distinguishes between valence and value. An Outcome may have high valence (anticipated satisfaction) and low value (realized satisfaction). Thus, valence always refers to the anticipated satisfaction from an Outcome.

Vroom's (1964) use of the term, "Outcome," was somewhat confusing. Galbraith and Cummings (1967) clarified this by suggesting the concepts of "first" and "second" level Outcomes. This is particularly important in discussing the concept of instrumentality.

Using Galbraith and Cummings' (1967) terms, instrumentality can be defined as the likelihood that a first-level Outcome will lead to a particular second-level Outcome. According to Vroom (1964), this is not a probability since it takes values ranging from +1, indicating certainty that a second-level Outcome will follow from the first-level Outcome, to -1, indicating certainty that the first-level Outcome will not lead to a particular second-level Outcome. Instrumentality might be a "perceived correlation" between first and second level Outcomes (Graen, 1969).

Job satisfaction in terms of Vroom's (1964) model can be accounted for with the two concepts of instrumentality and valence. It is defined as "the valence of the job or work role to the person performing it (p. 101)".

A slight rewording of Vroom's (1964) Proposition provides a more formal definition of satisfaction. The valence of a first-level outcome (i.e., job) to the person performing a job is a monotonically increasing function of the algebraic sum of the products of the values of all second-level outcomes and his conceptions of its instrumentality for the attainment of these second-level outcomes.

The remaining concepts in Vroom's (1964) model are expectancy and force. Expectancy is probabilistic concept indicating an individual's subjective probability that performing an act will lead to a particular first-level Outcome. Since it is a probabilistic concept, it takes values

ranging from 0, indicating no probability, to 1, indicating certainty that the act will lead to the Outcome. Force is a motivational concept and involves the concepts of expectancy and valence. It is defined by Vroom's (1964) Proposition 2.

Graen's (1969) test of the theory led to a clarification of the conditions under which expectancy predictions would relate to job satisfaction and performance. The methodology employed in the research allowed the manipulation of an organization climate variable. Three climates were experimentally generated: reciprocating, prompting, and control.

The reciprocating climate made rewards contingent on performance. The prompting climate used extra payment as an inducement for future performance, rather than offer it contingent on past performance. The control climate used no rewards in addition to regular pay. The results suggest that expectancy predictions are consistently supported only for the reciprocating climate.

Another clarification which seems to be even more important to the present discussion is Graen's (1969) discussion of the context in which this conceptual framework is placed. This context is the "work personality - work role system (p. 2)."

"Work personality, is defined, in part, as a person's preferences for various consequences of attaining work roles and his dispositions for perceiving and evaluating various instrumentality and expectancy relationships (p. 2)." On the other hand, "work role, is defined as a set of behaviours expected by the organization and considered appropriate of an incumbent of a position within the organization (p. 2)."

Graen (1969) provides examples of work roles including occupational group member, effective job performer, incumbent in a particular job, team member, and leader.

The expectancy theory, under discussion, views all work behaviours as outputs of this work personality work role system. The basic unit of concern centres around an individual work personality in a work role. In discussing this system, Graen (1969) is giving attention to both individual (work personality) and situational (work role) factors. In this respect, Graen (1969) has explicitly broadened the concern of the theory. However, Graen's (1969) original model, discussed previously, has no mechanism for handling these situational variables.

After conducting an experiment to test various aspects of this expectancy formulation, Graen (1969) suggested additional modifications which add considerable complexity to the model

and allow one to incorporate certain situational variables. These variables fall into the category of perceived external pressures to perform.

“It is important to note that the expectancy model deals with situational variables as they are perceived by the actor rather than variables as they might be ‘objectively’ measured or estimated by someone other than the actor. The model assumes that it is the perceived value of the variable which affects the individual's subsequent attitudes and behaviour (Graen, 1969)

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The implications of these results are interesting. First, it seems to support the idea that the "actual" rewards provided by the job (the "actual" instrumentality) bear a significant relationship to the “perceived” rewards (or "perceived" instrumentalities). If this is the case, it would be possible and, it seems, useful to measure the "actual" instrumentalities associated with various positions for purposes cocounseling, selection and classification, job engineering, etc.

Second, this result can be turned around to say that the extent to which one can demonstrate support for expectancy predictions can be taken as an index of the extent to which the organization has developed a climate where rewards are contingent on performance. In this sense, the expectancy model could be used as a diagnostic tool to "measure" presence of a reciprocating climate. (A similar idea has been presented by Porter and Lawler, 1968a).

The Lawler and Porter (1967a, 1967b) Models

Two other researchers in the area of work motivation and performance currently employing the instrumentality theory approach are Lawler and Porter (1967a, 1967b). In a series of

articles (Lawler & Porter, 1967a, 1967b; Lawler, 1968b; Porter & Lawler, 1968a, 1968b), these authors have presented both theoretical models and research testing their models in a managerial' environment.

Their work has served to extend instrumentality theory and put satisfaction research into a new perspective. Their extension of instrumentality theory attempts to further explain the relationship between motivation and performance.

One of their earlier articles (Lawler & Porter, 1967a), presents a theoretical model relating job attitudes to performance. This model borrows heavily from earlier instrumentality approaches to work motivation, most notably Vroom (1964) and Georgopoulos et al., (1957). The principal attitudinal components of the model are:

1. Value of rewards
2. Effort-rewards probability

Value of rewards is defined as the attractiveness of possible rewards or outcomes to the individual. The second variable, effort-rewards probability, refers to a subjective expectancy that a desired reward will follow from putting forth certain levels of effort. This variable includes Vroom's (1964) concept of expectancy or the probability that performance will lead to rewards, and the probability that performance results from effort.

The concept of effort according to Lawler and Porter (1961a) is the amount of energy an individual expends in a particular situation. The rule explaining how value of rewards and effort-rewards probability interact to produce the level of effort is stated as follows:

- “The greater the value of a set of rewards and the higher the probability that receiving each of these rewards depends upon effort, the greater the effort that will be put forth in each situation (Lawler & Porter, 1967)”.

The remaining two variables in the model, abilities, and role perceptions, which mediate the relationship between effort and performance, consider relatively permanent characteristics of the individual as well as situational aspects of the work environment. Abilities may be considered crudely to be the individual's "power to perform".

Role perceptions refer to the individual's perception of the types of activities and behaviours which he should perform to accomplish his job successfully. Role perceptions maybe accurate or inaccurate depending on how closely they agree with the expectations of those evaluating performance.

Lawler and Porter (1961b) “treat satisfaction somewhat differently as a function of performance. Performance leads to two types of rewards, intrinsic and extrinsic. Extrinsic rewards are seen as imperfectly related to performance due to the difficulty of making rewards such as pay, promotion, status, security, etc., contingent on performance”(Lawler and Porter, 1961b). Since performance, especially for managerial jobs, is difficult to measure, it is difficult for organizations to dispense rewards strictly based on performance.

For intrinsic rewards, however, Lawler and Porter (1967b) contend that the situation is different. These rewards, such as feelings of accomplishment, can be given by the incumbent to himself. Thus, the relationship between intrinsic rewards and performance is seen as more direct. In expectancy theory terms, the instrumentality of performance for intrinsic rewards is higher than it is for extrinsic rewards. Further-more, according to Lawler and Porter (1967b), the individual's satisfaction is assumed to be dependent not only on the amount and type of rewards received for performance, but also on what he perceives as a fair level of rewards.

Comparison of Various Expectancy Models

For the present report, the important comparison between the various models is in terms of their handling of satisfaction. A discussion of the way the Porter and Lawler (1968a) and Vroom (1964) models deal with performance is given in Heneman and Schwab (1972). The present discussion will attempt to point out similarities and differences in the various approaches in explaining satisfaction.

Vroom (1964) and Graen (1969) argue that satisfaction (work role attraction) is a monotonically increasing function of the products of the instrumentality of the work rule for attaining certain role Outcomes and the desirability (valence) of these Outcomes. Porter and Lawler (1968a) contend that satisfaction is a function of performance, rewards, and perceived equitable rewards. One obvious difference between the two formulations is the inclusion of the equity concept in the Porter and Lawler (1968a) formulation. That is, the relationship between rewards and satisfaction is mediated by the individual’s perception of whether the level of rewards meets some internal standard of "equitable" level of rewards.

“A second and primary difference is concerned with the relationship between satisfaction and performance. Lawler and Porter (1967a, 1967b) and Porter and Lawler (1968a) explicitly state that satisfaction is, in part, a function of performance. In other words, satisfaction is an ‘output’ of the model. The Vroom (1964) and Graen (1969) formulations are somewhat

vague on the effects of performance on satisfaction. The emphasis of the model, however, is upon satisfaction as an input to the work performance model. This is stated explicitly in Vroom's (1964) Proposition 2 where the 'valence of a work role' combines with expectancy to predict the probability of an act.

Thus, in one model, Lawler and Porter (1967a, 1967b), considered satisfaction to be an output. In Vroom (1964) and Graen's (1969) formulation, satisfaction is seen to be an input (Vroom, 1964 and Graen's, 1969)".

It is not immediately clear to what extent this represents substantive differences in the models or whether the apparent difference results from a failure to describe both models in "dynamic" terms as opposed to "static" formulations. If a model is conceived as operating through time, it is immediately clear that the outputs at Time 1 will be inputs at Time 2, assuming some sort of feedback mechanism. In this sense, whether something is called an input, or an output is quite arbitrary depending on which phase of the model one observes.

The level of satisfaction combines (in some unspecified way) with value of reward which is an input. To the extent that satisfaction and value of reward are different, the Porter and Lawler (1968) model is different from the Vroom (1964) and Graen (1969) models. However, if satisfaction and value of reward are the same or very highly related, then even though one is an input and the other an output, the models are quite similar.

Thus, the crucial question in comparing the two models concerns a comparison of the way satisfaction is conceptualized by the two models. The question boils down to one of whether the conceptualization of satisfaction as an input in the Vroom (1964) model and as an output in the Porter and Lawler (1968a) model reflect substantive differences. Vroom (1964) and Graen (1969) defined satisfaction with a work role (valence of a work role) as the sum of the products of the valences of the Outcomes of that work role and the instrumentalities of the work role for attaining those Outcomes (see Proposition 1).

Such satisfaction is, as stated explicitly, anticipated rather than realized satisfaction. In Vroom's (1964) model then, satisfaction is future oriented and concerned with fulfilment which is expected. For Porter and Lawler (1968a), on the other hand, satisfaction is defined differently. Satisfaction in this model is a reaction to past events; it is past rather than future oriented. "It is concerned with fulfilment in the past and whether the fulfilment was 'fair' or 'equitable' according to some internal standard.

Thus, it appears that the two conceptualizations of job satisfaction are different, and the differences are primarily in terms of orientation. The Porter and Lawler's (1968a) model is oriented toward the past while Vroom's (1964) and Graen's (1969) models are more future-oriented" (Vroom, 1964 and Graen's, 1969).

This difference would have implications for explaining or predicting relationships between job attitudes and behaviour. The Vroom (1964) model and the Graen (1969) model would predict that an increase in satisfaction would lead to an increase in the force to perform an act if expectancy is unchanged.

Porter and Lawler's (1968a) formulation would predict that an increase in satisfaction would affect performance very indirectly. It would have a significant effect only if it affected the variable "value of rewards". On the other hand, in the Porter and Lawler (1968a) model, a change in performance has the potential for influencing satisfaction assuming that rewards are contingent on performance. The effects of performance on satisfaction in Vroom's (1964) and Graen's (1969) models are not specified.

Heneman and Schwab (1972) conclude that the various versions of expectancy theory are essentially equivalent in terms of their explanation of performance. Based on the foregoing discussion, such a conclusion does not seem warranted in terms of the various models' approaches to satisfaction.

Assessment of Expectancy Theory

Expectancy theory is primarily a theory of the individual and attempts to explain the process factors affecting the individual's choices between alternative acts or behaviours. The theory has undergone several modifications since its original statement by Vroom (1964), including those of Graen (1969). The most comprehensive version is the Porter and Lawler (1968a) statement of the theory.

The expectancy theories presented by the preceding authors provide a useful way of conceptualizing the relationships among several variables affecting work motivation. The theories are perhaps most useful in accounting for the motivation and satisfaction of someone performing in the role of job incumbent. As devices for predicting the level of satisfaction and motivation of prospective job incumbents the theories are less useful.

This is because the expectancy and instrumentality values for prospective incumbents would likely be different from the values for the same individual if he became a job incumbent. Only if the individual were given very detailed and accurate information about the work activities required by the job, the performance reward relationship, and the rewards provided by the job, would the theory accurately predict satisfaction for an individual before he entered the job.

This latter approach would involve using measures with largely untested psychometric characteristics. However, until well developed measures exist, the full utility of expectancy theory will not be known.

A recent article (House & Wahba, 1972) points out that most work dealing with expectancy theory assumes that individuals attempt to maximize positive Outcomes. These authors note that the maximizing criterion is subject to question considering recent research dealing with choice behaviour.

The assumption that individuals attempt to maximize positive Outcomes could also be questioned considering the equity theory considerations previously discussed. Maximization could lead to a state of overpayment inequity which presumably would be dissatisfying to the individual. Since Porter and Lawler (1968a) include equity considerations in their version of the theory this criticism has, to some degree, been satisfied.

Despite the above disadvantages, expectancy theory remains the most explicit, and perhaps the most promising theory of work motivation. It is still evolving as is indicated by the recent work of House and Wahba (1972), among others. As the concepts become more clearly defined, and when adequate measures are developed, this approach will well provide a means for dealing with the complexities of human work motivation.

Cornell Studies of Satisfaction

Basic Concepts

The Cornell Studies of Satisfaction, unlike some of the other approaches discussed, present a "little bit of theory and a great deal of data." The research conducted in this program has been based on a rather general conceptual model and has dealt very systematically and painstakingly with many of the very difficult issues which confront attitude research in general and job attitudes.

The most comprehensive statement of this approach is contained in *The Measurement of Satisfaction in Workhand Retirement* (Smith, Kendall, & Hulin, 1969).

This is the primary source for the discussion which follows, and unlike the other four theories, a description of the different versions and modifications to this theory is not attempted.

The history of this approach is in many ways the history of the development and validation of a measuring instrument the Job Description Inventory (JDI). The discussion that follows will be organized in a manner which reflects that orientation. The first section will deal with the justification for measuring satisfaction. Other sections will include the conceptual model, measurement problems and issues, construction of the JDI, and brief considerations in validation of the JDI.

Why Measure Job Satisfaction. Smith et al., (1969) argue that the study of satisfaction is important for several reasons. First, to understand the sources of satisfaction and dissatisfaction is important in and of itself for humanitarian reasons. Second, it is important because managers and policy makers believe that it is important. Much of the concern of management and unions is with issues which are expected to affect the attitudes of workers. Therefore, they are interested in evaluating the impact of these decisions and programs on expressed attitudes.

Finally, it is important to the theoretician who is interested in the dynamics of human motivation. Thus, study of satisfaction with the job, and the determinants of such attitudes, would be expected to contribute to the broader psychology of attitudes and human motivation.

Each of these might be sufficient justification for studying satisfaction. Each also requires inadequate measure of satisfaction in order to make study of the determinants of job attitudes possible. Smith and her associates (1969) felt that existing measures were inadequate for failing to satisfy one or more criteria of an adequate measuring instrument, such as expense of use, standardization, separation of various facets of satisfaction, reliability, and validity. Therefore, they reasoned that a new inventory should be constructed which hopefully would satisfy these criteria.

Descriptive and Evaluative Measures

Attitude statements can be arrayed along a continuum of objectivity. On one hand are specific statements dealing with observable aspects of the situation, i.e., temperature, humidity, cleanliness, etc. On the other hand, are statements which ask for subjective reactions to the situation. It would be expected, according to Smith et al., (1969) that the latter subjective statements would be most affected by differing frames of reference.

Implications of the Research for Job Satisfaction. It is not correct to refer to the Cornell Studies as providing a theory of job satisfaction. Rather, in the words of Smith et al., (1969), their purpose is to "report a strategy for the study of attitudes (p. 160)".

As a result, those aspects of this strategy which have been supported by the data can be useful to other researchers interested in job satisfaction. Thus, this section will attempt to summarize very briefly various implications of the "strategy".

1. "An adequate model of satisfaction must consider interactive effects among variables.
2. Relationships between satisfaction and overt behaviour vary from situation to situation.
3. Relationships between satisfaction and behaviour cannot be reasonably expected unless the behaviour can be an appropriate means of expressing satisfaction and dissatisfaction.
4. The way questions are asked affects the time perspective of the respondent, and therefore affects the alternatives he considers.
5. Satisfaction is a product of other variables, and it may or may not serve as a cause (Smith et al., 1969, p. 162).
6. There may be a relationship between satisfaction and behaviour since the same variables producing the satisfaction might also produce the behaviour, or changes in behaviour may act to change the situation and, therefore, satisfaction.
7. The relationship between satisfaction and performance will vary depending on the aspect of the job being studied.
8. The importance of each aspect of the job situation influences the individual's feeling of satisfaction. Importance is a function of the discrepancy between the existing situation and the alternatives available.
9. Legitimacy, the group norms defining the legitimate requirements for a job for a specified group, influence the acceptance of a task and the attitude toward it.

10. It is, therefore, the interrelationships of objective factors of the job, of individual capacities, of alternatives available in the company and the community, and of the values of the individual, that can be expected to predict satisfaction and performance (Smith et al., 1969, p. 165)".

Assessment of Cornell Studies

The summary statement, number 10, describes a general "model" which might serve as a useful guide to any job satisfaction theory builder. It is acknowledged that satisfaction and performance are outputs from the interactions among individual and situational variables. Smith and her associates (1969) however, make few generalizations as to the nature of these relationships. Thus, there is no theory which can be ascertained from the Cornell Studies.

“The basic value or contribution of this extensive program of research has been the development of a measuring instrument and the discussion of several complex issues which confront the job satisfaction researcher. Anyone claiming a comprehensive approach must successfully deal with the issues posed by Smith and her associates (1969) in their strategy for the study of attitudes (p. 160)".

Need Fulfilment Theory

Basic Concepts and Modification

This approach to job satisfaction is based on the idea that individuals have certain needs and that jobs satisfy these needs in varying degrees. Satisfaction is synonymous with need fulfilment, much as satisfaction is dealt with by Lawler and Porter (1967b).

Most of the work in this area has concentrated on the needs of the individuals. These include Maslow's (1943) need hierarchy and Alderfer's (1969) Existence, Relatedness, and Growth (E.R.G.) Theory. Neither of these theorists dealt with variations in environments in terms of the opportunity for need fulfilment. The focus was on the individual and the hypothesized dynamics of his need system.

One program of research, however, has considered both the needs of the individual and the “reinforcers” in the work environment. This work based on the Theory of Work Adjustment (Dawis, England, & Lofquist, 1964; Dawis, Lofquist, & Weiss, 1968) makes considerable use of the concept of individual-environment fit. As such it represents one of the few attempts to deal with both individual and situational variables.

Maslow's (1943) Need Hierarchy Theory

“Maslow (1943) proposed a theory of motivation which also incorporated a taxonomy of needs, namely: (a) physiological, (b) safety, (c) love, (d) esteem, and (e) self-actualization.

These ‘basic’ needs are related to one another, according to Maslow (1943), in a hierarchical fashion with self-actualization at the top of the hierarchy and the physiological needs at the bottom, or most basic, level. Maslow (1943) posits the idea of pre-potency, which says that the most basic unsatisfied need will be prepotent, i.e., will dominate the individual's attention and prevent the emergence of the ‘higher’ needs. In other words, man lives by bread alone when there is no bread (Maslow, 1943,p. 375)".

“The goal of man according to Maslow (1943) is self-actualization. However, because of the hierarchical arrangement of needs, self-actualization can occur only after the ‘lower-order’ needs have been relatively well satisfied” (Maslow, 1943).

Several studies have been conducted which have applied Maslow's (1943) concept of need hierarchy to work motivation. In a series of studies, Porter (1961, 1962, 1963a, 1963b, 1963c), concerned with need satisfaction of managers, found evidence that need satisfaction varied as a function of position level.

In the third study in the series, Porter (1963a) found that higher level managers placed more importance on self-actualization than did lower-level managers. This seems to indicate support for Maslow's (1943) assertion of the hierarchical arrangement of needs, if one assumes that higher level managers have greater satisfaction of the basic or lower-order needs.

Due to the cross-sectional nature of Porter's (1961,1962,1963a,1963b, 1963c) work, his results did not provide conclusive support for Maslow's (1943) position, since his research design did not rule out the possible explanation that the need patterns existed prior to the manager's promotion to high management positions. Thus, the greater importance attributed to self-actualization may have been a cause rather than a result of their promotion.

Recognizing this design deficiency, Hall and Nougaim (1968) tested predictions from the Maslow (1943) model in a longitudinal study employing data from management trainees over a five-year period. The specific hypotheses tested in the study were as follows:

“Hypothesis 1: Within a given year, the satisfaction of a given level of needs will be positively correlated with the strength of the needs at the next higher level (static analysis).

Hypothesis 2: From one year to the next, changes in the satisfaction of a given level of needs will be positively correlated with changes in the strength of the needs at the next-higher level (change analysis).

Hypothesis 3: After five years of employment, successful managers will show lower need strength and higher satisfaction in the safety needs than will their less successful colleagues. Thus, they will show higher achievement and self-actualization need strength than will the less successful group (success analysis)”(Hall & Nougaim, 1968).

The results indicate that in neither the static nor change analysis were there any substantial correlations between need satisfaction and need strength at the next level. The highest correlation was .23 between Affiliation satisfaction and the strength at the next higher level (Achievement and Esteem).

Thus, Hall and Nougaim (1968) conclude that their data provide no evidence to support the notion of a need hierarchy. Even when they collapsed the three higher levels into a single level yielding a two-stage model, the hierarchy notion was not supported. Based on their data, the authors suggest an alternative model which they call a career stage model.

According to this model, an individual moves through various stages of career development, and each stage carries with it a concern for various types of need satisfaction. These stages might be described in terms of such primary concerns as: (a) concern for security, (b) concern for promotion and achievement, and (c) higher-order concerns related to actualization.

“The difference between the career stage and the hierarchy model is that career passage occurs not because of satisfaction at lower levels, but as a result of regular status passages which are facilitated by both the environment (i.e., role factors) and the individual (i.e., developmental life stages).

And these status passages can occur largely independent of the man's degree of perceived success in satisfying the concerns he experienced at the earlier stages” (Hall & Nougaim, 1968, p. 29).

The authors' evidence supports this view since both high and low success managers (as measured by advancement) showed similar patterns of need changes during the five-year period of the study.

Alderfer's (1969) E.R.G. Theory

“An alternative theory of human needs has been proposed by Alderfer (1969). Alderfer (1969) postulates three categories of needs:

1. Existence
2. Relatedness
3. Growth”

(Alderfer, 1969).

Although these needs are assumed to be arranged in a hierarchy, this does not seem to be a strictly ordered hierarchy. According to Alderfer (1969), this means that lower-order gratification is not prerequisite for the emergence of the higher-order needs.

“Existence needs are those which deal with material and physiological desires. Their objectives can be reduced to material substances or physical states. The satisfiers of existence needs are usually characterized by the condition that, when resources are limited, one person’s gain is another person's loss; that is, the food eaten by Person A is not available for Person B” (Alderfer, 1969).

“Relatedness needs are those needs for social relationships with significant others. Basic to relatedness-need satisfaction is the idea of sharing or mutuality. The satisfaction of relatedness needs may not always result in a positive affective state for all parties involved. It may include the exchange or expression of anger or hostility, as well as the exchange or expression of love or friendship” (Alderfer, 1969).

"Growth needs include all the needs which involve a person making creative or productive effects on himself and the environment (Alderfer, 1969). Satisfaction of growth needs results for engaging in activities which require an individual to utilize his capabilities and develop new abilities. Involved ingrowth needs is the striving on the part of the individual to become what he can become” (Alderfer, 1969).

Alderfer's (1969) Existence includes Maslow's (1943) physiological needs plus those needs related to physical safety. Relatedness includes the need for security, love needs, and the need

for self-esteem which, in turn, depends upon regard from others. Finally, self-esteem deriving from the individual's self-awareness and self-actualization are included in the Growth needs.

Alderfer (1969) states that this categorization, in contrast to Maslow's (1943) formulation, makes not strictly ordered, hierarchical assumption. If the categories do lie on a dimension, it might be considered a dimension of concreteness-abstractness with Existence being the most concrete and Growth the least concrete of the needs.

Alderfer (1969) states seven propositions which explain the functioning of the need system. In some of these propositions we see influences from Maslow's (1943) hierarchy; notably, Propositions 3 and 6. In addition to this, Alderfer (1969) incorporates into Propositions 2 and 5 the frustration- regression hypothesis, which states that frustration of need satisfaction at one level will lead to regression to seek satisfaction at a more concrete level.

Propositions 1 and 4 are derived from the simple frustration hypothesis indicating that the more something is denied, the more it is desired. Finally, Proposition 7 follows from research on aspiration level, which has shown that when one attains a certain level of growth, he sets a higher goal. "The seven propositions are as follows:

- 1- The less existence needs are satisfied, the more they will be desired.
- 2- The less relatedness needs are satisfied, the more existence needs will be desired.
- 3- The more existence needs are satisfied, the more relatedness needs will be desired.
- 4- The less relatedness needs are satisfied, the more they will be desired.
- 5- The less growth needs are satisfied, the more relatedness needs will be desired.
- 6- The more relatedness needs are satisfied, the more growth needs will be desired.
- 7- The more growth needs are satisfied, the more they will be desired"

(Alderfer, 1969)

Alderfer (1969) points out the similarities and differences between his E.R.G. theory and the Maslow (1943) theory. Propositions 2 and 5 represent departures from Maslow (1943). Both propositions are concerned with the increased desire for lower-order, previously satisfied needs as a result of lack of satisfaction for the next higher level of needs. Maslow's (1943) model maintains that satisfied needs lose their determining or organizing role.

Proposition 7 is another departure from the notion that satisfied needs are no longer motivators. This proposition is a departure from Maslow's (1943) original ideas but in

agreement with his later statement that "Growth is instead a continued, more or less steady upward or forward development (1968)."

Another departure from Maslow (1943) results from the classification of needs into three rather than five categories. Since Maslow's (1943) security needs and esteem needs fall into separate E.R.G. categories, different predictions are made for these two needs.

Alderfer's (1969) study tested 21 hypotheses. Three of these were derived exclusively from Maslow(1943), ten exclusively from the E.R.G., and the remaining eight from a combination of E.R.G. and Maslow (1943) needs in E.R.G. Proposition 4. Thus, support for the two models can be compared. If the cross-theory predictions are supported, they can be taken as support for the E.R.G. theory since the study utilized a proposition from E.R.G. theory to make the predictions.

Although the results showed support for one of the three Maslow (1943) predictions, this support was based on only one correlation of .15 ($p < .05$). On the other hand, eight of the ten hypotheses derived from the Alderfer (1969) model were supported by significant correlations ranging from .15 to .49, with several reaching the .995 confidence level.

The results from the cross-theory predictions showed some support for four predictions and strong support for one, thus giving some support for five out of eight predictions. This, as mentioned earlier, represents support for the E.R.G. model since the predictions were made using E.R.G. and Maslow's (1943) needs in E.R.G. Proposition4. In essence, these results show that predictions involving Maslow's (1943) needs received greater support when generated from the E.R.G. theory than when derived from Maslow's (1943) theory.

Alderfer (1969) qualified his results by stating that the lack of support for the Maslow (1943) predictions may have been due to the measures used. The measures used for the Maslow (1943) needs were less reliable than those used for the E.R.G. needs, possibly because Alderfer (1969) relied on measures developed by others for the Maslow (1943) needs to avoid introducing his own bias into the instrument construction. Furthermore, it may have been more difficult to operationalize the Maslow (1943) needs, which are more difficult to separate conceptually, than the E.R.G. needs.

Even with these qualifications, the results of Alderfer's (1969) study together with those of Hall and Nougaim (1968) raise some question concerning the utility of the Maslow (1943) theory as an explanatory device. Perhaps the idea that needs appear in a strictly ordered

hierarchy, with higher order needs becoming more important a slower order needs are satisfied, is an over simplified notion. These results suggest that more research using a relatively complex theory, such as E.R.G., is required.

Work Adjustment

The Work Adjustment Project at the University of Minnesota represents a careful, systematic effort to study and explain the process through which individuals adapt to the world of work. One purpose of this project is to facilitate the practice of vocational counselling by providing conceptual and concrete tools for intervention into the process of work adjustment. The work of the project is based on the Theory of Work Adjustment (Dawis et al., 1964, 1968).

The theory assumes that "each individual seeks to achieve and maintain correspondence with his environment (Dawis et al., 1968)". This correspondence is defined in terms of the relationships between the work personality and the work environment. Work personality can be thought of as a set of work-relevant dimensions along which people vary. The dimensions with which the theory deals are skills and needs. Work environment represents a set of dimensions along which jobs can vary. These include skill requirements and rewards.

The concept of correspondence can be described in terms of these dimensions. The worker brings his individual work personality to the work environment. His work personality consists of several skills and a set of needs. A particular work environment, or position, requires certain skills on the part of the worker and, in turn, provides the worker certain rewards. "Correspondence can be described in terms of the individual fulfilling the requirements of the work environment, and the work environment fulfilling the requirements of the individual (Dawis et al., 1968)".

There are ways in which the goodness of fit, or correspondence, can be evaluated. The most basic indicator of correspondence is tenure which refers to the length of time a person remains in a particular position. It is assumed by the theory to be a function of the correspondence between the individual and the work environment.

The above definition of correspondence makes use of two separate criteria

1. The individual satisfying the requirements of the position
2. The position satisfying the requirements of the individual

The terms used by the theory to refer to these two conditions are "satisfactoriness" and "satisfaction". Satisfactoriness represents the extent to which the individual is judged by the organization to be a satisfactory worker. An individual's satisfaction is assumed to reflect the extent to which the organization meets his needs.

This formulation of the theory makes it possible to describe the work personality and the work environment on comparable dimensions. As mentioned above, the work personality can be defined in terms of skills and needs; work environments may be defined in terms of skill requirements and reinforcers.

"With the above assumptions and concepts identified, the theory may be stated more formally in terms of the following propositions and corollaries.

- 1- Proposition I. An individual's work adjustment at any point in time is indicated by his concurrent levels of satisfactoriness and satisfaction.
- 2- Proposition II. Satisfactoriness is a function of the correspondence between an individual's abilities and the ability requirements of the work environment, provided that the individual's needs correspond with the reinforce system of the work environment. Corollary IIa. Knowledge of an individual's abilities and of his satisfactoriness permits the determination of the effective ability requirements of the work environment. Corollary IIb. Knowledge of the ability requirements of the work environment and of an individual's satisfactoriness permits the inference of an individual's abilities.
- 3- Proposition III. Satisfaction is a function of the correspondence between the reinforce system of the work environment and the individual's needs, provided that the individual's abilities correspond with the ability requirements of the work environment. Corollary IIIa. Knowledge of an individual's needs and of his satisfaction permits the determination of the effective reinforce system of the work environment for the individual. Corollary IIIb. Knowledge of the reinforce system of the work environment and of an individual's satisfaction permits the inference of an individual's needs.
- 4- Proposition IV. Satisfaction moderates the functional relationship between satisfactoriness and ability-requirement correspondence.
- 5- Proposition V. Satisfactoriness moderates the functional relationship between satisfaction and need-reinforce correspondence.

- 6- Proposition VI. The probability of an individual being forced out of the work environment is inversely related to his satisfactoriness.
- 7- Proposition VII. The probability of an individual voluntarily leaving the work environment is inversely related to his satisfaction”

(Dawis et al., 1968).

Assessment of Need Fulfilment Theory

The Theory of Work Adjustment provides the best example, from those considered, of a theory which has been operationalized. Well-developed measures of needs, reinforcers, satisfaction, and satisfactoriness exist. As such it has been possible to test and to verify many of the predictions made by the Theory of Work Adjustment. Support for its predictions involving job satisfaction has been quite consistent.

One weakness of the approach lies in the range of variables considered. The Theory of Work Adjustment assumes that the work personality is composed of two sets of variables; needs, and abilities. Undoubtedly, there are other sets of variables which could profitably be included such as interest and life history variables. The basic model, however, could be expanded to include other variables such as those mentioned.

A second weakness lies in the lack of an adequate definition of "correspondence". A basic proposition of the theory is that satisfaction is a function of the "correspondence" between the reinforcers of the work environment and the individual's needs. The exact nature of this correspondence, however, is never specified. Various indices of correspondence were tested in a study by Betz (1971), but the issue remains unresolved. Presumably the most satisfactory index is a simple difference measure, but more work directed toward this issue is needed.

Time wise, the earlier studies which first appeared around 1960 (e.g., Whitlock, 1960) were mainly literature reviews of motivation and satisfaction which included some theory citations. In the mid-1960's, more specific studies involving need-fulfilment, particularly need hierarchy and two-factor theories, began to appear.

Later (circa late 1960's and early 1970's), there was an increase in both number of studies and variety with several expectancy theories, a few equity theories, the Cornell Studies, and Alderfer's (1969) need-oriented studies, being published. However, there was still considerable interest in two-factor theory during the more recent period. Generally, across all

services, two-factor theory followed closely by need-fulfilment theories were used most frequently.

Because it was one of the first theories developed, the Herzberg et al., (1959) two-factor theory has been predominant. However, there is a definite trend toward more use of expectancy, equity, and other theories such as the Theory of Work Adjustment (Dawis et al., 1964).

Hofstede Cultural Model

It is commonly needed for businesses to constantly evaluate and in some cases change their advertising techniques based on the customer demand within a regional culture. “The Hofstede model of national culture” is designed to help multinational businesses and organizations like Subway to understand the diverse cultures of the countries better. This cultural model is also very useful for managers at Subway stores because many employees working there come from different backgrounds and their culture must be treated with respect.

There are six factors in this model which is designed to outline strategies for organisations to gain more from their advertising and marketing campaign. Subway should certainly use this model since it's a multinational brand and it needs to understand the culture of each country, they do business in. By using this model, Subway would be able to adjust its marketing approach and projects to fulfil the values and standards of that specific country.

Hofstede model of national culture

Subway should regularly use this model before and after they enter a new market and the organisational culture at Subway must mirror the more comprehensive global society followed by the firm.

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Figure 25: Hofstede cultural dimensions

Figure 15

Power Distance Index

This index describes the strength and the degree of equality and inequality between individuals and different groups of people in the company based on their power within that space. Subway in this matter has a low power distance culture.

Hierarchy Within the Organisation

Based on this model, Subway has a flatter hierarchy. One of the benefits of this is simpler accessibility to the administration which normally results in having a sense of belonging and trust in the employees and motivates them perform better within the organisation. This also creates a sense of authority among the employees that would result in even higher motivation for them to address the more challenging tasks on a day-to-day basis.

Organizational Decision-Making

Subway uses the decentralized decision-making method. This would allow the employees to have authorities while they are at work and as a result the possibility of a faster and more efficient problem-solving within themselves if it does not contradict with the company's values. In a larger scale, this would allow the head of branches in different countries to develop their own strategy based on the needs and wants of that specific market. However, all the major policies are still communicated to the stores from the headquarters to avoid any flaws and misunderstanding in the business.

Compensation Bands

Based on the Hofstede model the compensation bands are not supposed to be distant from one another. Instead, the bands and pay-scales overlap based on the duties and job descriptions. However, the compensation is mainly related to pay-bands which requires the flatter power structure and offers alternatives for employees to have better settlements.

Power Delegation

Due to the low power distance of Subway, the company and its managers can delegate power without restrictions. This delegation enhances the employee involvement within the

organisation and as a result a better performance is expected. Additionally, delegation creates a sense of belonging and ownership among workers within businesses.

Leadership

Multinational organisations use different leadership styles based on the circumstances in the location they operate in. However, Subway normally uses a charismatic style of leadership in most of their branches. These leaders encourage employees by giving them a sense of appreciation and belief. A charismatic leader would collaborate with staff members directly in order to help them grow and achieve higher business development. Leaders and managers play an important role in this market because of the constant change in the policies and guidelines so it is the responsibility of these leaders to communicate the changes to their employees and make sure that they would follow them at all times.

Supervisory Staff

Because of the low power distance of Subway, the need for supervision is minimal. However, this does not mean that there is no need for managers to supervise the day-to-day business. Based on this culture, staff members have their own responsibilities and can set their own goals. This would motivate them accomplish their tasks better and lowers the need for a constant supervision for them. In order to make sure that the employees are up to date about the guidelines, Subway has created its own online university where all the staff members should join and learn about the latest changes applied by the headquarters. It is the responsibility of the managers and supervisors to make sure that all the employees within their stores have joined and completed all the courses provided by the online Subway University.

Individualism VS. Collectivism

These are the most popular activities within organisations. Whereas individualists mostly emphasise on individual accomplishments and employees normally choose to work on their own or a small group of people toward completion of tasks within the organisation. On the other hand, collectivists prefer to work in large groups and believe that this would result in a better outcome. Subway is having a healthy mix between these two activities; they encourage their employees to be individualistic when needed but also promotes collectivism for the more difficult tasks.

Time

Time is an important matter in every workplace. Subway must value the time of its staff members and the managers in their stores should plan the work in a way that does not impact the employee's personal life negatively. This is necessary for the physical and emotional well-being of the staff members and by doing that it would give them a sense of value.

Challenging Tasks

Subway needs to involve its employees frequently and more often with challenging tasks. The reason for this is to involve the workers in the job and would encourage them to execute these tasks better. Subway should make sure that all its staff members are challenged so that they do not deal with discontentment from their job.

Individual Accomplishments

Individual accomplishments at Subway ought to be celebrated. Staff members must be acknowledged for their performance and success professionally as well as individually. The gratitude and celebration must be in a form of intrinsic and extrinsic benefits which aids to increase the motivation of staff members toward enhancement. Benefits are one of the most important forces of motivation in this industry.

Work-life VS. Social life

Subway should keep a clear separation between staff member's social and work life. They should make sure that the work life of the employees does not interfere with their personal life. They should also encourage the employees to have a more active social life and promote it within the organisation. A healthier lifestyle would lead to a better performance by the employees.

Creativity

Creativity is an important part of the human beings; we all have different abilities and skills which could be useful in our jobs. Therefore, Subway needs to encourage its employees to be creative in the workforce and avoid setting strict outlines within the organisation. Employees should be regularly encouraged to engage in challenging tasks and as a result increase their creativity. This might even lead to new accomplishments and findings by the employees which could be useful for the whole organisation.

Merit

At Subway, all the promotions, in addition to settlement monitoring tasks, are governed on rules of quality and are strictly based on employee performance. Thus, Subway discovered it's only fair to utilize these standards to help with employee growth along with a culture of sincerity and transparency within the company to stay clear from problem.

Masculinity VS. Femininity

This activity is about the roles that is distributed among male and female employees within the organisation. Subway has a low rate of masculinity vs. femininity (MAS), meaning that the tasks are distributed evenly between all genders and there is no discrimination or stereotype in the job description.

Egoism

Subway should promote a less egoistic culture in the organisation. Women are a huge part of this business, and their success must be celebrated just like men. This would certainly benefit the company since it allows skilful women to take part in the company and help boost its success. It also creates a better image of the company and could result in an increase in performance.

Motivation Factors

Subway should always motivate its employees in the workplace, but this encouragement should not hurt the employees emotionally or physically. The company should promote a healthy balance between work and the personal life of the employees.

Gender Role Differentiation

Subway should not have any type of stereotyping or discrimination in their job description. Every task at Subway must be developed to be equally designated and to motivate workplace equal rights in between males and females. Furthermore, Subway likewise ought to be an equal-opportunity company and offers males and females with equal possibilities of development in the company.

Uncertainty Avoidance Index

Having a high Uncertainty Avoidance Index (UAI) would mean that the company wants to be in control of everything within the business. They require control in every section of the company and demands that everyone must follow the guidelines set by them. This would discourage employees to be creative and innovative but reduces the risks threatening the company. Subway in this context uses a mixed method where they don't require a high UAI but still demand a certain level of it.

Open to change

Every organisation should be opened to change if the circumstances demand it and Subway is no exception from that. The firm should often participate in adjustment monitoring programs to boost its procedures, cultures, in addition to work activities via group building tasks. The frequent modifications would certainly permit the company to become more versatile to changes in the external as well as internal environments without influencing the performance of workers. Additionally, this would motivate development in the company.

Risk Taking

Subway in general is known for its risk-taking approach. This means that the company is willing to take higher risks in return to explore new opportunities. The company faced some challenges due to this approach in the past but have not stopped exploring new markets.

Flexibility

Flexibility is another important factor in multinational organisations. It would allow them to adjust faster in new markets and be able to satisfy the needs of that specific country. Subway is very flexible with their strategies and should continue to do so.

Job Satisfaction Survey

“The development of the Job Satisfaction Survey (JSS), a nine-subscale measure of employee job satisfaction applicable specifically to human service, public, and nonprofit sector organizations, is described. The item selection, item analysis, and determination of the final 36-item scale are also described, and data on reliability and validity and the instrument's norms are summarized. Included are a multi-trait multi-method analysis of the JSS and the Job Descriptive Index (JDI), factor analysis of the JSS, and scale intercorrelations.

Correlation of JSS scores with criteria of employee perceptions and behaviors for multiple samples were consistent with findings involving other satisfaction scales and with findings from the private sector. The strongest correlations were with perceptions of the job and supervisor, intention of quitting, and organizational commitment. More modest correlations were found with salary, age, level, absenteeism, and turnover” (Spector, 1983)

“Job satisfaction of employees is a topic that has received considerable attention by researchers and practitioners alike. In all these writings, relatively little can be found about the human service employee. Sarata (1974) was able to find fewer than 20 studies concerned with human services, mostly with nurses.

Several years later Dehlinger and Perlman (1978) could find only a few others and called human service employees ‘industry's forgotten staff’, at least as far as their job satisfaction is concerned. During the late 1970s interest in human service workers' job satisfaction began to increase with research concerned with comparisons to industrial workers (e.g., Cherniss & Egnatios, 1978; Frontz, 1978; Zaharia & Baumeister, 1979) and causes of satisfaction (e.g., Dorr, Honea, & Pozner, 1980; Folkins, O'Reilly, Roberts, & Miller, 1977; Sarata, 1977; Spector & Marlowe, 1983).

Despite the increased attention to job satisfaction in human service organizations, generalizations must still be made from industrial findings in many areas. Norms for existing job satisfaction scales do not reflect human services, making it impossible to compare a given human service organization to human service organizations in general. Cherniss and Egnatios (1978) and Zaharia and Baumeister (1979) using the Job Descriptive Index, JDI (Smith, Kendall, & Hulin, 1969), and Frontz (1978) using the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (Weiss, Davis, England, & Lofquist, 1967) found lower satisfaction in their human service samples than the norms of the instruments, but it is difficult to know how typical these results might be.

Furthermore, with many variables studied in industrial organizations, it is unclear how well results generalize to human services. For example, it is a widely held conclusion based on available evidence that job satisfaction is not consistently associated with job performance (e.g., Locke, 1976; Vroom, 1964).

In human services, however, there is evidence that satisfaction is associated with employee performance (Wiggins & Moody, 1983) and client outcomes (Buffum & Konick, 1982;

Schwartz & Will, 1961). It is indeed possible that findings with other variables will also be found to differ with human services” (Spector, 1983).

“To fill the need for an instrument for human services, a new job satisfaction instrument, the Job Satisfaction Survey (JSS) was developed. This scale measures nine aspects of job satisfaction, which were chosen from a review of the literature on job satisfaction dimensions. It was designed specifically for human service, public, and nonprofit sector organizations, although it may be applicable to others as well.

Although an existing scale might have been used in this research, a new scale was developed for three reasons.

First, it was intended that the content of the items should be applicable specifically to human services. Most existing scales were developed in other types of organizations, and some items may not be directly applicable. The current author has encountered difficulties of this type with the widely used JDI a problem also noted by Buffum and Konick (1982).

Second, the scale was intended to cover the major aspects of job satisfaction, with subscales that were clearly distinct in their content. Existing scales did not adequately cover all the areas of interest; for example, the JDI covers five that are included in the JSS but fails to cover four others. Finally, the length of the scale was a concern, and it was decided to keep the JSS under 40 items.

In the literature, job satisfaction is typically referred to as an emotional affective response to a job or specific aspects of a job (Locke, 1976; Smith et al., 1969). Smith et al. postulated that satisfaction with various job aspects is derived from a cognitive process of comparing the existing job aspect with an individual's frame of reference. Locke (1976) distinguished three major approaches to the causes of job attitudes.

They can derive from discrepancies between what the job offers and what the person expects, from the degree to which jobs fulfill individual needs, or from the degree to which individual values (desires or wants) are fulfilled. Regardless of the exact causal mechanism, job attitudes arise from an interaction certain aspect of jobs should lead to satisfaction of job aspects. For example, level of pay should be related to satisfaction with pay, job scope should be related to satisfaction with the job itself” (Spector, 1983).

“The attitudinal nature of satisfaction implies that an individual would tend to approach (or stay with) a satisfying job and avoid (or quit) a dissatisfying job. In the general attitudinal literature, attitudes have shown to relate to behavior, although correlations are typically modest. Withdrawal behavior, turnover and absenteeism, and withdrawal intentions are expected to correlate with satisfaction (Hom, Katerberg, & Hulin, 1979)”.

“In the current research, job satisfaction was assumed to represent a cluster of evaluative feelings about the job, and the JSS was designed to measure them, individually. It was also designed to give an overall attitude score as a combination of individual facets. Although it is not universally accepted that the overall attitude about a job is a combination of specific aspect attitudes, there is considerable empirical evidence that a linear combination of satisfaction aspects is an adequate overall satisfaction measure (Aldag & Brief, 1978; Quinn & Mangione, 1973; Wanous & Lawler, 1972)”.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Introduction

The research methodology section is designed to elaborate the layout of the research setting and its considerations. This chapter explains the decisions made by the researcher in terms of the approaches taken and discusses the advantages and disadvantages of these approaches.

The chapter starts with the research philosophy and continues with research approach and its rationale, research methods, data collection techniques, research design, data collection, sample size, researcher's bias and concludes the chapter with the ethical considerations.

Research Philosophy

“A research philosophy is a belief about the way in which data about a phenomenon should be gathered, analysed, and used. The term epistemology (what is known to be true), as opposed to doxology (what is believed to be true), encompasses the various philosophies of research approach.

The purpose of science, then, is the process of transforming things believed into things known: doxa to episteme. Two major research philosophies have been identified in the Western tradition of science, namely positivist and interpretivist (Galliers, 1991)”.

“As a philosophy, positivism is a view that only “factual” knowledge gained through observation, including measurement, is trustworthy. In positivism studies the role of the researcher is limited to data collection and interpretation in an objective way. In other words, the researcher is an objective analyst, and distances himself or herself from personal values in conducting the study. In these types of studies research findings are usually observable and quantifiable. Moreover, in positivism studies the researcher is independent from the study and there are no provisions for human interests within the study. As a general rule, positivist studies usually adopt deductive approach, whereas inductive research approach is usually associated with an interpretivism philosophy. Moreover, positivism relates to the viewpoint that researcher needs to concentrate on facts, whereas interpretivism concentrates on the meaning and has provision for human interest” (BRM, 2009)

A positivist approach has been chosen for this study, because it is the researcher's belief that he is independent of the study and the research can be purely objective. Independent means that the researcher maintain minimal interaction with participants when carrying out the research. In other words, studies with positivist paradigm are based purely on facts and consider the world to be external and objective. "Positivism often involves the use of existing theory to develop hypotheses to be tested during the research process. Positivist researchers tend to use highly structured research methodology in order to allow the replication of the same study in the future. Science can be specified as a foundation in positivism research philosophy.

However, Positivism is associated with some set of disadvantages:

Firstly, positivism relies on experience as a valid source of knowledge. However, a wide range of basic and important concepts such as cause, time and space are not based on experience. There might be many additional factors that have impacted research findings and positivism research philosophy fails to acknowledge the effect of these factors.

Secondly, positivism assumes that all types of processes can be perceived as a certain variation of actions of individuals or relationships between individuals.

Thirdly, adoption of positivism in business studies and other studies can be criticised for reliance on existing state of affairs. In other words, research findings in positivism studies are only descriptive, thus they lack insight into in-depth issues" (BRM, 2009)

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Table 5

Table 5: Research philosophies (Saunders, 2016)

Research Approach

“It is believed by the positivist that reality is observable and can be explained from the viewpoint of an object” (Levin, 1988).

“This often involves manipulation of reality with variations in only a single independent variable to identify regularities in and to form relationships between, some of the constituent elements of the social world.

Predictions can be made based on the previously observed and explained realities and their inter-relationships. Positivism has a long and rich historical tradition. It is so embedded in our society that knowledge claims not grounded in positivist thought are simply dismissed as a scientific and therefore invalid (Hirschheim, 1985)”.

Therefore, this study uses the deductive approach because it is compatible with positivism and in this approach theoretical assumptions are tested by using the empirical analysis. There are several studies done on the performance in retail market and this allows the researcher to use those literatures in order to create and test his hypotheses.

Additionally, this approach is vastly used to analyse the cause-and-effect relationship between different variables which in this case the variables are Consumer Preference, Health Issues, Internal and External pressures, Employee Turnover, and their relationship with the Performance of Subway within the retail industry.

Rationale

To complete this study, numerical data is required to compare large groups within society. Factors like consumer preferences, health issues and managing employees need direct access to Subway customers and its employees.

Numerical data makes the comparison easier by allowing the researcher to create graphs and charts and therefore enabling him to identify the relationship between these variables and the performance of Subway.

This study consists of two separate surveys aimed at different segments. Based on the researcher's theoretical framework there are four variables discussed in this research that affects the performance of quick service restaurants.

Two variables are external factors which are 'Consumer Preferences' and 'Health Issues'. These factors are mostly not within the direct control of the business and therefore, the first survey was distributed to the fast-food customers in order to collect data on those variables.

The other two variables are internal factors and mostly are under the control of the business and they are 'Internal and External Pressures' and 'Employee Turnover' thus, the second survey was distributed to the employees of Subway stores throughout the Greater London area. The populace was hired using a purposive non-probabilistic sampling method, in which the individuals were particularly and non-randomly chosen.

According to the ethical guidelines of the university, the researcher was responsible to acquire the participant's consent prior to the survey as well as communication their rights to opt-out during the process if the desire to. The anonymity of the participants was at an utmost importance to the researcher and all the data collected was kept safe throughout this study.

Research Methods

"The next issue is for the researcher to select whether quantitative or qualitative procedures and techniques should be employed for data collection and analysis (Saunders et al., 2016)".

In this study, the original plan was to use both, but unfortunately due to the Covid-19 pandemic and its vast effect on businesses around the world and specially in the UK and despite a tremendous effort made, the researcher was unable to conduct interviews with multi-unit managers and owners of Subway due to the limitations placed by the UK

government during the research phase and the fact that these managers were furloughed and not available, therefore only quantitative approach has been used in this research.

Mixed methods were initially chosen for this research study because “it contributes to the validity and reliability of the study results given that the weak points of one method can be offset by the other (Easterby-Smith et al., 2012)”. “This is since making use of both qualitative and quantitative data permits methodological triangulation and therefore it is possible to clarify the complex relationship between the performance and variables affecting it” (Johnson et al., 2007).

“Nonetheless, there are constraints of using this approach that should be considered. For one, the adoption of a mixed method strategy may result in the production and multiplication of unforeseen results (Coghlan and Brannick, 2014)”.

And according to Bryman (2006), in order to use the mixed method, it is essential that the researcher is extremely experienced in this field because conducting and analysing both the quantitate and qualitative requires a highly developed skill. Limited knowledge in this area would result in having difficulties to interpret the data and might lead to wrong or inadequate data analysis.

Data Collection Techniques

This study consists of two major methods of data collection which are the primary and secondary data collection. The primary data was collected from two separate self-administered questionnaires aimed at different target audiences and the secondary data was collected from company reports, articles, and other reliable online sources. the use of these two methods of data collection enhances the reliability of this research. Tertiary sources were not used in this study as there is a high risk that the data might either be wrong or misinterpreted.

Survey was used to collect quantitative data. These self-administered questionnaires include structured and close-ended questions. The questions of this survey were structured in accordance with the literature review of this study.

This survey was pilot tested to evaluate its simplicity and reliability. It was then distributed online with the help of Google forms and Survey Monkey as well as Subway stores throughout the Greater London area.

There are many advantages in using surveys but perhaps the most important one is that the respondents stay anonymous which inspires them to answer the questions honestly (O’Leary, 2010). In addition, online surveying tools such as Google form and Survey Monkey are very helpful in reaching many respondents in a short amount of time.

Research Design

A conclusive research design was selected and used in this study because a quantitative method of data collection and use of existing theories are required for this study.

The causal research design is one of the categories of conclusive research. This type of research is useful for comparing the cause-and-effect relationship. Therefore, making it suitable for this study to demonstrate the relationship between different variables and the performance of Subway.

Quantitative research design has been used in this research because the aim and objectives of this study is to measure the factors that are essential to customers. Therefore, quantitative research that requires numerical data would be the best approach for this study. The data was collected in a standardized way and then analysed statistically.

Nykiel (2007) explains “the adoption of quantitative design and claims that it is the most useful approach from a marketing perspective since it allows collecting measurable information that can be tracked over time (p.55)”.

In addition, in order to make the responses from participants more measurable, 5-point Likert scale methodology was designed in both questionnaires. This methodology allows the researcher to have a deeper understanding of the responses from participants and the data collected from this method is easily comparable.

Data Collection

This study contains two major methods of data collection which are the “primary and secondary”. The primary data was collected from the surveys and the secondary was collected from company reports, articles, and other reliable online sources. the use of these two methods of data collection enhances the reliability of the research. Tertiary sources were not used in this study as there is a high risk that the data might either be wrong or misinterpreted.

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Sample Size

“Sampling and sample size are crucial issues in pieces of quantitative research, which seek to make statistically based generalisations from the study results to the wider world. To generalise in this way, it is essential that both the sampling method used, and the sample size are appropriate, such that the results are representative, and that the statistics can discern associations or differences within the results of a study” (O’Leary, 2010).

The population size for this study is the number of Subway franchise outlets throughout the Greater London area, which is roughly around 490 stores as of 2019, and the average employee of 4 in each store, the confidence level of 95% and the margin of error is 5%.

Therefore, with the use of a sample size calculator the ideal sample size for the research would be 322 participants. However, as this survey had to be conducted during the Covid-19 pandemic and despite the effort of the researcher, only 247 participants in total have responded.

Calculate representative sample size

Sample size

Population size:	<input type="text" value="1960"/>	How many people are in the group your sample represents? (The sample size does not change much for populations larger than 20,000.)
Margin of error:	<input type="text" value="5%"/>	This is the plus-or-minus figure usually reported in newspaper or television opinion poll results. For example, if you use a margin of error of 4% and 47% percent of your sample picks an answer, you can be "sure" that if you had asked the question to the entire population, between 43% (47-4) and 51% (47+4) would have picked that answer.
Confidence level:	<input type="text" value="95%"/>	This tells you how sure you can be of the margin of error. It is expressed as a percentage and represents how often the true percentage of the population who would pick an answer lies within the margin of error.

Required sample size: **322** Number of respondents needed

Figure 16: Sample Size Calculation

Figure 16

Researcher's Bias

“Smart & Paulsen (2011) argue that the researcher’s bias needs to be confronted before claiming to make valid research (p. 61)”. The researcher bias was largely reduced by using the online survey as a data collection tool in order to have minimal interaction between the researcher and the respondent, However the questionnaire was also distributed in stores among customers and employees.

“Crooks & Baur (2016) claim that filling out a form affords greater anonymity than facing an interviewer, subjects might be considerably more likely to answer questions honestly, with minimal distortion. Finally, because most written questionnaires can be evaluated objectively, their data are less subjected to researcher bias than are data from interviews”.

To improve the reliability of this research, the survey was not conducted on the same day and same time and was not distributed at the same location. In addition, to guarantee the random selection of respondents, the researcher approached consumers waiting to order food on the queue line as well as those who already purchased their food.

Access and ethical issues

Prior to performing the research, the researcher applied and received ethical clearance from the University of the West of Scotland research ethics board. “Because there is a very high

involvement in conducting these types of research, ethical issues were the main concern of the researcher. Respondent security and safety should be the primary issues to the researcher” (Saunders, 2012). Along with receiving ethical clearance from the University’s ethical clearance board, participants were informed about the ability to withdraw from the research study at any time.

“Throughout the questionnaire design phase, it was essential to make certain that risks to individuals associated with their financial and personal safety and security were reduced or avoided altogether. For this purpose, no delicate data was accumulated from participants, including participants' citizenship, addresses and telephone numbers. Additionally, the process was anonymised, indicating that the set of questions participants were not asked to report their names” (Saunders, 2012).

The researcher guarantees the complete confidentiality of the participants. They also will be assured that no information will be shared with those who are not directly involved in this research. In some cases, the researcher will also guarantee the anonymity of the participants, meaning they will be anonymous during the study even to the researcher himself.

“Considering the complete target populace, the confidence interval for this sample is equal to 10% and the confidence level is 95%. A 95% confidence level and +/- 5% confidence intervals or margin of error show that if the same survey is repeated 100 times under the exact same conditions, 95 out of 100 times, the responses would deviate only by +/- 5% from this questionnaire.

Additional constraint of this study concerns the variety of stores that could be analysed. Just stores in the Greater London area were included in the sample. This choice is justified by their reasonably easy access. However, there are numerous shops around the world that could be made use of in this study. It needs to be critically remarked, however, that by enhancing the sample, the researcher might face substantial difficulties in getting access to these stores” (Saunders, 2012).

The participants must not be forced into joining this study as the principle of volunteer engagement requires that. The researcher has ensured that the individuals are fully informed regarding the process as well as the possible risks involved in taking part in this research, therefore, their consent was given before they begin filling out the survey. Individuals of this research was not placed in any situation where they might be in harm either physically or psychologically.

Chapter : DATA ANALYSIS

Internal Factors

This chapter and the data analysis done is based on a work satisfaction survey. The purpose of this survey was to find out how satisfied employees were at their job, the reasons why they leave their job and the demographic scale. The researcher then used the multi-regression analysis as well as Pearson correlation efficient in order to identify the relationship between job satisfaction and its factors with employee turnover.

Target population

The targeted populace included fast-food employees throughout the Greater London area. The participants in this study were carefully chosen to satisfy the needs of this research, based on the literature the highest turnover in this industry is among employees in the lower-level management therefore most of the participants were selected from them. This research aims to help managers and supervisors in this industry to minimize the turnover intentions by focusing on issues crucial to the employees in this market.

Role of the Researcher

Recognizing the procedure consisted of meeting the expectations of the University of the West of Scotland's ethics committee, in addition the researcher informed all the participants about the requirements needed to complete the survey as well as explaining about the consent form and why it's required to be filled by them.

For that reason, before distributing the questionnaire I discussed with the managers and supervisors of the outlets about the purpose of the research and what are the rights of the participants during and after completing the questionnaire. Moreover, I have explained my obligation towards protecting their identity and the discretion of it.

The researcher also had made sure that all the participants are selected equally and without prejudice regardless of their ethnics, background, or ability. The participants were only chosen from those who currently work in the fast-food market in London in order to avoid any bias towards this study. The data collection began after the researcher received approval from the ethics board, he then approached the managers of the outlets to get their authorization for the employees to participate in the study.

Correlation Coefficient

“Correlation coefficients are indicators of the strength of the linear relationship between two different variables, x and y . A linear correlation coefficient that is greater than zero indicates a positive relationship. A value that is less than zero signifies a negative relationship. Finally, a value of zero indicates no relationship between the two variables x and y .

The correlation coefficient (ρ) is a measure that determines the degree to which the movement of two different variables is associated. The most common correlation coefficient, generated by the Pearson product-moment correlation, is used to measure the linear relationship between two variables. However, in a non-linear relationship, this correlation coefficient may not always be a suitable measure of dependence.

The possible range of values for the correlation coefficient is -1.0 to 1.0 . In other words, the values cannot exceed 1.0 or be less than -1.0 . A correlation of -1.0 indicates a perfect negative correlation, and a correlation of 1.0 indicates a perfect positive correlation. If the correlation coefficient is greater than zero, it is a positive relationship. Conversely, if the value is less than zero, it is a negative relationship. A value of zero indicates that there is no relationship between the two variables.

If the correlation coefficient of two variables is zero, there is no linear relationship between the variables. However, this is only for a linear relationship. It is possible that the variables have a strong curvilinear relationship.

When the value of ρ is close to zero, generally between -0.1 and $+0.1$, the variables are said to have no linear relationship (or a very weak linear relationship)” (Steven Nickolas, 2021).

Positive Correlation

“A positive correlation—when the correlation coefficient is greater than 0—signifies that both variables move in the same direction. When ρ is $+1$, it signifies that the two variables being compared have a perfect positive relationship; when one variable moves higher or lower, the other variable moves in the same direction with the same magnitude” (Steven Nickolas, 2021).

Negative Correlation

“A negative (inverse) correlation occurs when the correlation coefficient is less than 0. This is an indication that both variables move in the opposite direction. In short, any reading

between 0 and -1 means that the two securities move in opposite directions. When ρ is -1, the relationship is said to be perfectly negatively correlated.

In short, if one variable increases, the other variable decreases with the same magnitude (and vice versa). However, the degree to which two securities are negatively correlated might vary over time (and they are almost never exactly correlated all the time)” (Steven Nickolas, 2021).

The Pearson Coefficient

“Both the Pearson coefficient calculation and basic linear regression are ways to determine how statistical variables are linearly related. However, the two methods do differ. The Pearson coefficient is a measure of the strength and direction of the linear association between two variables with no assumption of causality. The Pearson coefficient shows correlation, not causation. Pearson coefficients range from +1 to -1, with +1 representing a positive correlation, -1 representing a negative correlation, and 0 representing no relationship.

Simple linear regression describes the linear relationship between a response variable (denoted by y) and an explanatory variable (denoted by x) using a statistical model. Statistical models are used to make predictions” (Steven Nickolas, 2021).

Multiple linear regression

“Multiple linear regression (MLR), also known simply as multiple regression, is a statistical technique that uses several explanatory variables to predict the outcome of a response variable.

The goal of multiple linear regression (MLR) is to model the linear relationship between the explanatory (independent) variables and response (dependent) variable. In essence, multiple regression is the extension of ordinary least-squares (OLS) regression because it involves more than one explanatory variable” (Adam Hayes, 2021).

“Simple linear regression is a function that allows an analyst or statistician to make predictions about one variable based on the information that is known about another variable. Linear regression can only be used when one has two continuous variables an independent variable and a dependent variable. The independent variable is the parameter that is used to calculate the dependent variable or outcome. A multiple regression model extends to several explanatory variables” (Adam Hayes, 2021).

“The multiple regression model is based on the following assumptions:

- 1- There is a linear relationship between the dependent variables and the independent variables
- 2- The independent variables are not too highly correlated with each other
- 3- y_i observations are selected independently and randomly from the population
- 4- Residuals should be normally distributed with a mean of 0 and variance σ

The coefficient of determination (R-squared) is a statistical metric that is used to measure how much of the variation in outcome can be explained by the variation in the independent variables. R² always increases as more predictors are added to the MLR model, even though the predictors may not be related to the outcome variable.

R² by itself can't thus be used to identify which predictors should be included in a model and which should be excluded. R² can only be between 0 and 1, where 0 indicates that the outcome cannot be predicted by any of the independent variables and 1 indicates that the outcome can be predicted without error from the independent variables.

When interpreting the results of multiple regression, beta coefficients are valid while holding all other variables constant (all else equal). The output from a multiple regression can be displayed horizontally as an equation, or vertically in table form” (Adam Hayes, 2021).

Demographic questions

These questions are consisting of 7 open ended questions regarding the participant's position in the restaurant, their age, gender, academic background, and the length they have been working in their current role. As explained before these questions are based on a JSS style survey.

“The JSS is a multidimensional instrument that was originally developed for the social service sector. However, Spector (1985) argues that it can be used for other sectors as well. The response format is a six-point Likert scale, ranging from ‘disagree very much’ to ‘agree very much’. Reliability and construct validity: the time interval between the test and retest was 18 months. The stability of some sub-scales was moderate.

The convergent validity was established with the multi-trait multimethod and the JDI was used as validity instrument. Spector (1985) did not mention the total convergent validity score, but only the correlations between the sub-scales of the two instruments. The

discriminant validity among the sub-scales was moderate to low. There was no evidence of responsiveness to change.

Content validity: to test the content validity, the degree of inclusion of work factors in the selected instruments was examined. The JSS includes nine sub-scales: salary, promotion, supervision, fringe benefits, contingent rewards, operating procedures, co-workers, work, and communication. Some of the items categorized as 'operating procedures' refer to workload" (Spector, 1985).

The null hypothesis for this section was, "Employee Turnover negatively affects the performance of Subway because the rate of turnover in this industry is very high." And the other hypothesis was, "Internal and External Pressures exist in every business however, this has a bigger effect on fast food restaurants because they must maintain a very high standard in food quality, customer satisfaction and cost reduction. Therefore, it could negatively affect the performance of the Subway."

IBM SPSS Version 25.0 for Windows is a computer software program that can evaluate the information statistically as well as graphically. SPSS was used because it provides the "multi-regression analysis", "Pearson's correlation coefficient analysis", and "descriptive statistics" to calculate and explain the data graphically.

The multi-regression analysis was conducted to explain the relationship job satisfaction and dissatisfaction factors with employee turnover.

In summary, the result of the survey suggests that satisfaction and dissatisfaction factors had "significant relationship" with the employee turnover. Whereas "employee responsibility" had the greatest relationship with turnover and "quality performance" had the lowest relationship with it.

On the other hand, "company policy" from job dissatisfaction had the greatest relationship with turnover and "working condition" had the lowest relationship with it.

Redacted due to copyright restrictions.

As shown in Table 6, the consistent reliability of JSS survey instrument was .93. Matkar (2012) described psychometric scale reliability higher than .90 is indicative of excellent consistent reliability for a reliable instrument. The coefficient alpha of .93 therefore suggested that scale scores are reliable for participants.

Table 6

Table 6: IRS Data analysis

In addition, the researcher used “descriptive statistics” to establish the “central tendency”.

The purpose of the frequency distribution was to illustrate the distribution of female and male participants participated and completed the survey. Out of the 144 participants, 95 participants were female and 49 participants were male. Figure16 shows the percentage of participants' gender distribution.

Fast food participants' gender distribution (N = 144). The purpose was to illustrate the percentage distribution of female and male participants completed the survey. Women represented 66% of the participants and men represented 34% of the participants.

As shown in Figure16 fast food participants are female and male. One hundred forty-four successfully participated and completed the survey. Out of 144 participants 65.97% were female and 34.03% were male. Female percentage was higher than male percentage.

Figure 17: Gender distribution

Figure 16

Frequency Distribution of Fast Food Participants' Age

		<i>f</i>	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Valid	18-28 years	107	74.3	74.3	74.3
	29-39 years	19	13.2	13.2	87.5
	40-50 years	11	7.6	7.6	95.1
	51-61 years	7	4.9	4.9	100.0
	Total	144	100.0	100.0	

Note. $N = 144$. The *f* column denotes the number of participants with specified age brackets. The percentage column computes using the total of survey responses, $f = 144$, the sum of which is 100%. The valid percent column computes using the 144 participants. The cumulative percent column is the cumulative sum of the *f* column or 144 participants, the total of which is 100%. The sample size $N = 144$, indicates participants who completed the survey with different age category.

In Table 7, age brackets were broken down into 4 categories. Under 18-28, 107 participants participated and completed the survey questionnaire. Nine-teen participants were under 29-39 years old. Under 40-50 years old, only 11 participants participated.

Under 51-61 years old, seven participants accepted the invitation. Overall, the number of participants participated and completed the survey was 144.

Table 7

Table 7: Participant's age

Age

Figure 17 Fast food participants' age distribution ($N = 144$). The age categories of the participants participated and completed the survey invitation. Age was divided into 4 categories: 18-28 years old (74%), 29-39 years old (13%), 40-50 years old (8%), and 51-61 years old (5%).

Figure17 represented the percentage age distribution of the participants based on the 144-sample size. The highest percentage of participation was age 18-28 years old followed by 29-39 years old, 40-50 years old, and 51-61 years old, which was the lowest percentage of participation. In conclusion, majority workers at fast-food restaurants in London were ages 18-28 years old and 51-61 years old were the least workers.

Figure 18: The percentage of participant's age

Figure 17

Frequency Distribution of Fast Food Participants' Educational Attainment

		<i>f</i>	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Valid	Other (please specify)	5	3.5	3.5	3.5
	High school	50	34.7	34.7	38.2
	Vocational	21	14.6	14.6	52.8
	Undergraduate(1-3)	38	26.4	26.4	79.2
	Bachelor degree	29	20.1	20.1	99.3
	Master	1	.7	.7	100.0
	Total	144	100.0	100.0	

Note. $N = 144$. The f column denotes the number of participants with different educational attainment in life. The % column computes using the total of survey responses, $f=144$, the sum of which is 100%. The valid percent column computes using the 144 participants with different educational background. The cumulative percent column is the cumulative sum of the f column or 144 participants, the total of which is 100%. Five participants did not specify the achieved education.

In Table 8 shows different educational background of the participants. Educational level backgrounds of participants are high school, vocational, undergraduate, bachelor, master, and others. Fifty fast-food workers were high school graduate. Twenty-one workers went to vocational school. Thirty-eight workers did not finish bachelor degree. Twenty-nine workers had bachelor degree, and one worker had master degree.

Unfortunately, five participants did not specify the educational attainment. Overall, the highest participants with high school diploma (50), followed by bachelor degree (29), undergraduate (38), vocational (21), and master (1). Only one participant worked at fast-food restaurant with master background.

Table 8

Table 8: The participant's education background

Figure 18 represented the percentage of participants who received high school diploma (35%), vocational course (15%), undergraduate degree (26%), bachelor degree (20%), and master degree (1%). Four participants did not specify the educational attainment (3%). In summary, majority participants had high school background, followed by undergraduate degree, bachelor degree, vocational, and master background, which was the least number of participants.

Figure 19: The percentage of participant’s education background

Figure 19

Frequency Distribution of Fast Food Participants' Job Positions

		<i>f</i>	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Valid	Other (please specify)	4	2.8	2.8	2.8
	Cashier(Drive/Front line)	69	47.9	48.3	51.0
	Runner(Counter and Drive thru)	15	10.4	10.5	61.5
	Fry person	5	3.5	3.5	65.0
	Meats person	7	4.9	4.9	69.9
	Initiator	2	1.4	1.4	71.3
	Assembler	7	4.9	4.9	76.2
	Manager	14	9.7	9.8	86.0
	Assist Manager	6	4.2	4.2	90.2
	Cook	6	4.2	4.2	94.4
	Driver	5	3.5	3.5	97.9
	Server	3	2.1	2.1	100.0
	Total	143	99.3	100.0	
Missing	System	1	.7		
Total		144	100.0		

Note. $N = 144$. The *f* column denotes the number of participants with different job position in the fast food restaurants. The row identified as missing displays the total count of survey response $f=1$. The % column computes using the total of survey responses, $f=144$, the sum of which is 100%. The valid percent column computes using the 144 participants with low-level management position and non-managerial position. The cumulative percent column is the cumulative sum of the *f* column or 144 participants, the total of which is 100%.

In Table 9 shows the 144 participants participated in the research study. Only one participant did not answer the job position question and 4 participants did not specify job position.

Participants worked from different job positions under low-level management or nonmanagerial positions. Numbers of participant from different job assignment were as follows: cashier (69 participants), runner (15 participants), fry person (5participants), meats person (7 participants), initiator (2 participants), assembler (7 participants), managers (14 participants), assistant managers (6 participants), cook (6 participants), driver (5 participants), and server (3 participants). Conclusively, the highest participants came from cashier, runner, and manager positions. The least participants were from initiator, server, fry person, and driver.

Table 9

Table 9: The participant's job position

As shown in Figure 19 144 participants responded to the invitation, which represented different jobs of the participants. Participants' job percentages were cashier (48%), runner (10%), fry person (3%), meats person (5%), initiator (1%), assembler (5%), managers (10%), assistant managers (4%), cook (4%), driver (3%), and server (2%). Four participants did not specify job position, which equivalent to 3%. In Conclusion, the highest percentages of participants were from cashier (48%), runner (10%), and managers (10%). The least percentages of participants were from initiator (1%), server (2%), driver (3%), and fry person (3%).

Figure 20: The percentage of participant's job position

Figure 20

Frequency Distribution of Fast Food Participants' Job Classification

	F	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Valid				
Part-time	90	62.5	62.5	62.5
Full-time	54	37.5	37.5	100.0
Total	144	100.0	100.0	

As shown in Table 10 the total number of participants participated and completed the survey was N=144. Participants' job classification is part-time or full-time. Ninety participants classified as part-time employee. Fifty-four classifies as full-time employee.

In conclusion, part-time workers had higher number of participation than full-time workers.

Table 10

Table 10: The participant's job classification

Job Classification

As shown in Figure 20 participants in Fast food restaurants in London, UK classified as part-time and full-time employees. Part-time employees had 62.50% participation and full-time employees had 37.5% participation. In conclusion, part-time employees had higher percentage of participation than full-time employees.

Figure 21: The percentage of participant’s job classification

Figure 21

Frequency Distribution of Fast Food Participants’ Years of Service

		<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Valid %</i>	<i>Cumulative %</i>
Valid	5 years	130	90.3	90.9	90.9
	10 years	10	6.9	7.0	97.9
	15 years	2	1.4	1.4	99.3
	20 years	1	.7	.7	100.0
	Total	143	99.3	100.0	
Missing	System	1	.7		
Total		144	100.0		

Note. *N* = 144. The table represents the frequency distributions of fast food participants in terms of services. The purpose is to illustrate the numbers of participants, percentage of participants, valid percentage, and cumulative percentage of the participants who worked under 5 years, 10 years, 15 years, and 20 years.

In Table 11 years of service categorized as 5 years, 10 years, 15 years, and 20 years. In 5 years, one hundred thirty participants (90.3%) worked under lower-level management or non-managerial position. In 10 years, 10 participants (6.9%) worked in the same level of management. In 15 years, 2 participants (1.4%) and in 20 years, 1 participant (.7%) worked in the same level. One participant missed the question. Conclusively, majority of the participants had 5 years of working services at Fast food restaurants in London, UK. The least number of participants found in 15- and 20-years services.

Table 11

Table 11: The participant’s years of service

In Figure 21 participants' work experiences categorize within 5 years, 10 years, 15 years, and 20 years. Participants worked under lower-level management or nonmanagerial positions at the Fast-food restaurants. Ninety percent of participants worked within 5 years. Seven percent of participants worked for 10 years. One percent of participants worked within 15 years and other 1 percent worked for 20 years already. The remaining 1% of participant did not specify the years of service. In conclusion, majority of participants worked at fast food restaurants within five years. Only 1% of participant worked within 20 years.

Figure 22: The percentage of participant's years of service

Figure 22

Descriptive Statistics for Age and Years of Working Variables

Variables	Minimum	Mean	Maximum	SD
Age	1	1.43	4	0.83
Years of Working	1	1.12	4	0.42

In Table 12 described the participants' age and years of working with fast food restaurants in London, UK. The minimum age of the participants completed the survey was 1 (18-19 years old) and the maximum age was 4 (5-61 years old). The mean age was 1.43 (29-39 years old) with standard deviation of 0.83. The minimum number of years of working was 1 (5 years) and the maximum years was 4 (20 years). The mean years of working was 1.12 (more than 5 years) with 0.42 standard deviation.

Table 12

Table 12: The Descriptive Statistics

Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficients Between Job Satisfaction Factors and Employee Turnover Intentions

Job Satisfaction Factors (Predictor Variables)	Employee Turnover Intentions (Criterion Variable)	Correlations <i>r</i>
Achievement/quality performance	Employee turnover intentions	-0.26
Recognition	Employee turnover intentions	-0.49
Work itself	Employee turnover intentions	-0.51
Responsibility	Employee turnover intentions	-0.52
Advancement and Growth	Employee turnover intentions	-0.37

Note. $N=144$. All correlations were significant at the $p < .001$ level.

A Pearson product-correlation applied to determine whether there was a statistically significant relationship between employee job satisfaction achievement or quality performance and employee turnover intentions.

As shown in Table 13, the resulting correlation coefficient was $r = -.26$ ($p < .001$).

In conclusion, there was a statistically significant relationship between employee job satisfaction achievement or quality performance and employee turnover intentions because the p value was less than .001. The magnitude of the relationship was low. The result showed an inverse relationship. Therefore, the lower scores on employee job satisfaction achievement, the higher scores on employee turnover intentions.

Table 13

Table 13: The correlation coefficient (satisfaction and turnover)

- 1- As demonstrated above there is a significant relationship between turnover with satisfaction and “achievement/quality performance”. As seen above, there is an inverse relationship between the variables and there is a significant relationship between all these variables. It shows that as satisfaction in achievement/quality performance increases, the turnover within that job decreases. This is in line with the Herzberg’s theory (1959), he concluded that as satisfaction factors like achievement/quality performance in the job increases, the turnover within that job decreases.
- 2- As demonstrated above, there is an inverse relationship between the variables. There is a significant relationship between turnover with satisfaction and “recognition”. It shows that as satisfaction in recognition in the job increases, the turnover within that job decreases. This is in line with the Herzberg’s theory (1959), he concluded that as

satisfaction in the job increases, the turnover within that job decreases. He also suggested that getting feedback from the job might help with the “employee recognition”.

- 3- Another analysis was done to establish the relationship between turnover with satisfaction and “work itself”. As seen above, there is an inverse relationship between the variables and there is a significant relationship between all these variables. It shows that as satisfaction in work itself increases, the turnover within that job decreases. This is in line with the Herzberg’s theory (1959), he concluded that as satisfaction factors like work itself in the job increases, the turnover within that job decreases. However, various other researchers did not agree with his viewpoint on this.
- 4- Another analysis was done to determine the relationship between turnover with satisfaction and “responsibility”. As seen above there is a significant relationship between all these variables. It shows that as satisfaction in responsibility increases, the turnover within that job decreases. This is in line with the Herzberg’s theory (1959), he concluded that as satisfaction factors like responsibility in the job increases, the turnover decreases. He also added that employees could accomplish greater tasks when they have authority within the job.
- 5- Another analysis was done to determine the relationship between turnover with satisfaction and “advancement and growth”. As seen above there is a significant relationship between all these variables. It shows that as satisfaction in advancement and growth increases, the turnover within that job decreases. This is in line with the Herzberg’s theory (1959), he concluded that as satisfaction factors like advancement and growth in the job increases, the turnover decreases.

Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficients Between Job Dissatisfaction Factors and Employee Turnover Intentions

Job Dissatisfaction Factors (Predictor Variables)	Employee Turnover Intentions (Criterion Variable)	Correlations <i>r</i>
Company policy	Employee turnover intentions	-0.52
Supervision	Employee turnover intentions	-0.37
Interpersonal relationship	Employee turnover intentions	-0.39
Working conditions	Employee turnover intentions	-0.34
Salary	Employee turnover intentions	-0.42

Note. $N = 144$. All correlations were significant at the $p < .001$ level.

A Pearson product-correlation coefficient applied to determine whether there was a statistically significant relationship between employee job dissatisfaction company policy and employee turnover intentions.

As shown in Table 14 , the resulting correlation coefficient was $r = -.52$ ($p < .001$).

Table 14

Table 14: The correlation coefficient (dissatisfaction and turnover)

- 1- As demonstrated above, there is an inverse relationship between the variables. There is a significant relationship between turnover with dissatisfaction and company policy. It shows that as dissatisfaction in company policy in the job increases, the turnover within that job increases too. This is in line with the Dike's theory (2012), he concluded that as dissatisfaction in the job increases, the turnover within that job increases as well.
- 2- As demonstrated above, there is an inverse relationship between the variables. There is a significant relationship between turnover with dissatisfaction and supervision. It shows that as dissatisfaction in supervision in the job increases, the turnover within that job increases too. This is in line with the Dike's theory (2012), he concluded that as dissatisfaction in supervision in the job increases, the turnover within that job increases too.
- 3- As demonstrated above, there is an inverse relationship between the variables. There is a significant relationship between turnover with dissatisfaction and "interpersonal relationship". It shows that as dissatisfaction in supervision in the job increases, the turnover within that job increases too. This is in line with the Derby-Davis theory

(2014), he concluded that as dissatisfaction in interpersonal relationship in the job increases, the turnover within that job increases too.

- 4- As demonstrated above, there is an inverse relationship between the variables. There is a significant relationship between turnover with dissatisfaction and “working conditions”. It shows that as dissatisfaction in working conditions in the job increases, the turnover within that job increases too. This is in line with the Yang’s theory (2013), he concluded that as dissatisfaction in working conditions in the job increases, the turnover within that job increases too.

- 5- As demonstrated above, there is an inverse relationship between the variables. There is a significant relationship between turnover with dissatisfaction and “salary”. It shows that as dissatisfaction in salary in the job increases, the turnover within that job increases too. This is in line with the Misra’s theory (2013), she concluded that as dissatisfaction in working conditions in the job increases, the turnover within that job increases too.

Multiple Regressions With Linear Combination of Job Satisfaction Factors and Employee Turnover Intentions

	R^2	SE of estimate	F	P
Model 1	0.35	1.83	5, 138=14.72	.000

Note. $R^2 = .35, p < .01$.

As Table 15 shows, the five job satisfaction factors used as predictors and regressed on intention to leave, resulted in an $R^2 = .35$. This process indicates that approximately 35% of the variance in the intention to leave scores by the combined influence of the factors. Further, the ANOVA shows that this value was statistically significant ($p = .000$). Examining in the standardized coefficients is important to assess the relative strengths of the individual contribution of the predictors to the equation.

Table 15

Table 15: The multiple regression (satisfaction and turnover)

Multiple Regressions With Individual Factor of Job Satisfaction and Employee Turnover Intentions

Predictor Variables	B	β	t	Sig (p)
(Constant)	11.268		14.023	
Achievement	.018	.034	.399	.691
Recognition	-.079	-.164	-1.312	.192
Work itself	-.137	-.257	-2.753	.007
Responsibility	-.144	-.275	-2.831	.005*
Career and advancement	-.002	-.003	-.031	.976

Note. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$.

Table 16 also shows the results that only one factor was statistically significant on an individual level, responsibility ($\beta = -.275$, $p = .005$). The other factors (achievement, recognition, work itself, and career advancement and growth) failed to achieve significance. Thus, five factors of the job satisfaction dimension do significantly predict intention to leave, and on an individual basis, a significant negative correlation exists between the responsibility factor and intention to leave. Specifically, higher scores, which indicate greater job satisfaction, predict less intention to leave.

Table 16

Table 16: The multiple regression (individual satisfaction factors and turnover)

Multiple Regressions With Linear Combination of Job Dissatisfaction Factors and Employee Turnover Intentions

	R^2	SE of estimate	F	P
Model 1	0.31	1.88	5, 138=15.50	.000

Note. $R^2 = .31$, $p < .01$.

Table 17 shows the results of the second multiple regressions wherein the five job dissatisfaction factors regressed on the intention to leave scores. The resulting $R^2 = .31$, indicates that approximately 31% of the variance in the intention to leave scores is by the combination of the dissatisfaction scores.

Table 17

Table 17: The multiple regression with Linear Combination (dissatisfaction and turnover)

Multiple Regressions With Individual Factor of Job Dissatisfaction and Employee Turnover Intentions

Predictor Variables	<i>B</i>	β	<i>T</i>	Sig (<i>p</i>)
(Constant)	11.187		11.028	
Company policy	-.206	-.393	-3.939	.000**
Supervision	-.032	-.057	-.612	.542
Interpersonal relationship	.033	.064	.575	.566
Working conditions	-.058	-.088	-1.044	.298
Salary	-.085	-.189	-1.887	.061

Note. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$.

On an individual basis, a review of the standardized coefficients in table 18 reveals that one of the factors had significant contributor, which was company policy ($\beta = -.393$, $p = .000$). The remaining four factors (supervision, interpersonal relationship, working conditions, and salary) were not statistically significant. The five combined factors in the dimension of job dissatisfaction do significantly predict intention to leave. In addition, a negative association exists between intentions to leave and the individual factor of company policy so that lower score on this factor is with higher intention to leave score.

Table 18

Table 18: The multiple regression (individual dissatisfaction factors and turnover)

Second Survey

A second survey was conducted by the researcher as the primary type of data collection. This questionnaire had 11 structured questions and it was designed based on the literature of this study. The questionnaire was pilot tested first to analyse its quality, clarity and consistency before the actual survey was conducted. The questionnaire was then distributed via social media, online survey websites as well as on the spot in fast-food branches within London, United Kingdom.

The survey contained questions about the participant's age, gender, how frequent they visit the fast-food restaurants, how satisfied they are with the food and what their occupation is. Convenience sampling method was used to conduct this survey with a sample size of 114 respondents from customers of fast-food restaurants.

Generalizations

Since this research is about the QSR and all the participants were selected based on their experience with fast-food restaurants it was assumed that all the participants were aware of

what these types of restaurants are and that they have a basic understanding of how they function. London was explicitly and intentionally used for this survey to avoid any bias in the result; therefore, the findings of this research might not be applicable to other hospitality sectors or other areas.

Data Analysis

The analysis of data is based on a quantitative method since the primary source of data comes from a questionnaire. The raw information was analysed by making use of SPSS version 25 program. Data was entered manually into the software and a screen shot of the results is presented in this study.

Additionally, All the data collected either from social media or online survey websites as well as the data collected on the spot from customers are combined in here for evaluation, this means that the data collected was not analysed separately from each other. From one hundred and fourteen sample dimensions just one hundred and three were valid for analysis. 11 questionnaires were disqualified by the researcher because they did not meet the requirements of the survey or/and were answered wrongly.

Limitations

There are a few limitations for this study as it is close to impossible to conduct a research with no limitations at all. Firstly, this study is limited to London only and because of that the findings might not be useful in other cities/countries.

Secondly, the primary data collection for this study was via a questionnaire only with limited number of questions involved, this might not be enough as the findings may not be as specific and accurate due to the nature of this data collection method.

Thirdly, surveys are not a good way to analyse the motives and behaviours of customers. A better way might be to add an additional type of primary data collection like interviews to have a deeper understanding of the issue.

Ethical Considerations

This study was done with the ethical values and principles in mind. All the participants were volunteered, and the questionnaire was done with their consent. Before filling the questionnaire, the researcher explained the topic of the research and they were all

advised that taking part in this survey is optional and they are free to opt-out if they choose to. The participants were given the option to opt-out at any moment with no threat or anxiety of retribution.

No forms of personal information like contact numbers, names or e-mail were collected from the participants of this study. After the data collection all the information were only stored on the researcher's personal computer and was not in any way shared with a third-party.

Anonymity of the participants were maintained the whole time.

Results of the survey

This section explains the findings of this survey and provides graphs and charts to simplify the result. The participants were carefully selected to make sure they all have had an experience with fast-food restaurants in order to understand the frequency of them visiting these outlets, what motivates them to visit these outlets, what are their main attributes and their view of the QSR. The findings revealed the behavioural intention, their perceptions, and the degree of satisfaction they have within this market.

A total number of 114 participants were surveyed in this research, however, 11 questionnaires were disqualified by the researcher because they did not meet the requirements of the survey or/and were answered wrongly.

The Demographics

Demographics		Number of respondents	Percentage %
Gender	Male	56	45.6 %
	Female	47	54.4 %
Age	18-25 years	49	47.6 %
	26-35 years	34	33 %
	36-45 years	13	12.6%
	46+ years	7	6.8 %
Occupation	Student	42	40.8 %
	Full-time employed	28	27.2 %
	Part-time employed	23	22.3 %
	Unemployed	9	8.7 %
	Pensioner	1	1%

The data was collected in regards with three variables of demographic segmentation of respondents, i.e., age (18-25 years, 26-35 years, 36-45 years, and 46+ years), gender and occupation (full-time employed, part-time employed, unemployed, student, and pensioner).

Based on the statistical analysis of the data, it was found that majority of the respondents were males. Out of the total of 103 respondents 54.4 % were males and 45.6 % were females.

A total of 47.6% of respondents were between the age of 18 and 25, with the following largest group being between age of 26-35 years (33%), followed by the 36-45 years (12.6 %) and 46+ years (6.8%). In respect to occupation, unsurprisingly, most of the respondents identified themselves as “student” (40.8 %), while 27.2 % identified as full-time employed, 22.3 % part-time employed, 8.7% unemployed and only 1% identified himself as a pensioner.

Demographic information is the basis of many marketing strategies at a macro and micro level so establishing this information first is important.

Table 19

Table 19: Gender, age, and occupation of the participants

Consumer preferences

These questions were asked in the survey to establish the preferences of consumers in fast-food industry. Knowing how consumers behave is crucial for the performance of a businesses it helps the organization to develop and effective strategy in order to gain a competitive advantage over competitors. To maintain this advantage, behavioural studies are essential to understand what motivates customers to visit these restaurants as well as their decision-making process.

Hence, these questions were asked from participants to find out the frequency of them visiting the fast-food outlets, reason for their visit, and what exactly motivates them to do so.

Statistical analysis of the data indicates that consumers visit fast food restaurants one to two times in a week (46.6%) or in a month (38.8%). Based on response ratings, 34% of participants indicated that they mostly dine at fast food outlets for friends get together and while 24.3 % dines for convenience. By contrast, 3.9 % indicated “other” as a reason for dining at fast food outlets, some specifying it as “working there”.

Figure 23: Frequency of participant’s visit

Figure 23

<i>Reasons for visiting a fast food outlet</i>	<i>Number of respondents</i>	<i>Percentage %</i>
<i>Friends get together</i>	35	34%
<i>For convenience</i>	25	24.3%
<i>For fun</i>	14	13.6%
<i>For change</i>	13	12.6%
<i>Family Outing</i>	12	11.7%
<i>Other</i>	4	3.9 %

<i>Source of influence</i>	<i>Number of respondents</i>	<i>Percentage %</i>
<i>Friends</i>	49	47.6%
<i>Family members</i>	20	19.4%
<i>Advertising/Media</i>	14	13.6%
<i>Children</i>	9	8.7%
<i>Other</i>	11	10.7%

In order to understand the reasoning behind consumer behaviour when it comes to visiting a restaurant, they were asked to pick a factor which influences their decision the most. Most consumers (47.6%) reported that their preference of visiting a particular restaurant was mostly influenced by their friends, followed by 19.4% was influenced by family members, while 13.6% have been influenced by advertising/media, and the rest of the participants were influenced by children (8.7%) and other (10.7%) reasons, some relating it to “particular cuisine”

Table 20

Table 20: Reasons for visiting fast-food outlets

Selecting the restaurant

These sets of questions were designed to evaluate the standards and the qualities that customers have in mind in order to select a restaurant. How customers perceive value is based on how well their expectations are met withing any transaction. Therefore, QSR outlets are expected to meet these demands by customers and try to satisfy their expectation in order to increase the degree of their satisfaction with the business.

In this section the Linkert scale questions were designed based on the literature of this study, which participants were asked to choose between scores from 1 to 5, where “5” is the most important and “1” is the least important to them. After the data collection, the weighted average rate was calculated for each criterion to determine the degree of relevance.

Criteria	Not important				Very important	Weighted Average Score
	1	2	3	4	5	
Quality & taste of food	1	1	6	20	75	4.62
Cleanliness/Hygiene	1	3	13	17	69	4.46
Quality of service	3	12	9	34	45	4.03
Menu variety	2	12	26	44	19	3.64
Service speed	5	10	32	38	18	3.52
Location	11	12	32	30	18	3.31
Price	10	22	29	25	17	3.17
Ambience/Interior	8	24	30	27	14	3.15
Brand name/Reputation	23	17	32	19	12	2.81

The results indicate that consumers place higher importance on the quality & taste of food (4.62), cleanliness & hygiene (4.46), and quality of service (4.03), followed by the menu variety (3.64), service speed (3.52), location (3.31), price (3.17), ambience/interior (3.15) and brand name or reputation of the restaurant (2.81).

Table 21

Table 21: Linkert scale questions of perceived value by the participants

Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is without doubt one of the priorities of any business in any sector. This is especially important in hospitality and restaurant business due to the higher rate of customer visits to these outlets. As a result, by keeping the customers satisfied through the quality of food and services, it is safe to assume that this would lead to a better performance. Additionally,

the degree of satisfaction has a significant relationship with repeat purchasing behaviour, which makes it even more important because it leads to increased profitably.

In this section, several sets of questions were designed in order to establish the degree of customer satisfaction within these QSR outlets. Most participants have said that they are happy with the service they have received in these restaurants. This suggests that, most probably these customers are likely to purchase again from these restaurants.

Overall, I am satisfied with my dining experience at fast food restaurant, and my expectations are met

	<u>Number of respondents</u>	<u>Percentage %</u>
<i>Strongly Disagree</i>	2	1.9 %
<i>Somewhat Disagree</i>	10	9.7%
<i>Neither Agree nor Disagree</i>	26	25.2 %
<i>Somewhat Agree</i>	46	44.7 %
<i>Strongly Agree</i>	19	18.4 %

Consumers were further asked to evaluate the perceived value of their transaction with the quick service restaurants. 64.1 % of respondents indicated that the value of their transaction is worth equal of the money they paid for this experience. 18.4 % stated the value of the transaction to be worth more than the amount they had paid, while 17.5% considered the value of transaction to be less than the amount paid for it. The overall results show that consumers primarily perceive the value of their transaction with fast food restaurants as valuable.

Figure 24: Overall satisfaction and perceived value of the participants

Figure 24

Undoubtedly, determining the customer satisfaction level for every requirement gives local business owner a chance to identify and enhance the areas that was lacking and not very pleasurable for consumers. With the changing eating habits of customers and the desire to have more healthy options and vegan foods, it is essential that these QSR's adjust themselves with the change and include these foods to their menu.

Improvement Implications

In this section, there were questions designed to identify the areas that customers think needs improvement within the business. This would allow the business to recognise how well they are perceived by the customers and which areas need more attention to increase their customer satisfaction.

Most survey respondents suggested to increase the number of healthier menu options (58.3 %). The rest suggested to increase the variety of menu items (34 %), improve seating space (32 %), indicate the nutritional value of items (29.1%), increase the number of services (i.e., home delivery) (30.1 %), offer ethnic/local food options (20.4%), and 6.8 % suggested other improvements, such as adding vegetarian menu options, etc.

Table 22

Table 22: Implication for improvement by the participants

The next survey question was designed to assess the consumers' satisfaction level in respect to different dining criteria, i.e., price, speed of service, service quality, menu variety, etc. Based on the statistical analysis of survey results, majority of subjects expressed high satisfaction with different variables such as location of fast-food outlets (63.1 %), service speed (53.4 %), price (52.4 %), cleanliness (51.5 %), etc. However, comparatively low percentage of consumers expressed dissatisfaction with number of criteria among which were menu variety (30.1%), seating space, the interior of the premise (16.5%), brand name (15.5%), etc.

Figure 25: Satisfaction degree of the participants

Figure 25

As it can be seen above, the important criteria for the customer who participated in our survey are the quality and taste of the food. Followed by the location of the restaurant, the cleanliness, and the hygiene. It was also mentioned that the service quality, the variety in menu and the speed of service is important for them. Based on this result, it is safe to assume that QSR suppliers mainly should make sure that these areas are well maintained. Although most customers revealed that they are overall satisfied with the quality and service given by these restaurants, the outcome evidently demonstrates that eating is not the only reason they visit these outlets, they also want to enjoy and meet with their friends and family.

When they were asked what enhancements, they would love to see, most customers stated they want to see more selections of healthier food options therefore health concerns as expected is essential in this industry and could affect the performance of QSR's. In addition, enhancing the seating area, indication of the nutritional value of items, improved food selection range and vegetarian choices are additionally crucial for customers.

RECOMMENDATIONS

During our economic period the QSR will probably find itself in a competitive situation within this industry with respect to recruitment and retention of an adequate number of high-quality employees. To be in a favourable competitive situation, the QSR's must meet the economic and non-economic needs of members of the labour force. There are numerous reports in the popular news media which strongly suggest that individuals, particularly younger persons, are demanding more out of their jobs in terms of autonomy, challenge, and opportunities for growth and fulfilment. In order to satisfy these non-economic needs, it will be necessary for the QSR to devote considerable effort towards accomplishing research concerning possible job and policy changes which will lead to more satisfying jobs.

The definition and measurement of job satisfaction has presented a long-standing problem even though a century of research in this area has yielded a variety of techniques and methods. There are reasons to suspect that the measurement technique utilized may influence the results obtained.

For example, research leading to the development of the two-factor theory used in depth structured interviews for data collection. Others, such as Dawis et al., (1968) and Smith et al., (1969), used various types of questionnaires or inventories. This situation suggests certain cautions may be advisable about method and research, the use of varied techniques such as interviews, surveys or some other combination of methods seems desirable. The use of more than one measurement approach, may lead to conclusions in which greater confidence can be placed that obtained results are not artefactual.

Regarding the measurement of job satisfaction, a potentially useful concept is that of the individual's frame of reference, provided the concept can be operationally defined. One approach to making the concept operational is offered by a technique called the self-anchoring scale which allows the respondent to define his anchor points on a subjective scale. Such an approach could be used to measure overall satisfaction or separate dimensions of satisfaction. Additionally, as an adjunct to the problem of job satisfaction measurement, a comparison of the predictability of various job satisfaction criteria warrants further consideration in research.

Several aspects of the job satisfaction-performance relationship controversy described in this report suggests further inquiry into this problem is justified. One version of Expectancy theory

(Porter & Lawler, 1968a) considered satisfaction as a function of performance and rewards (i.e., job satisfaction is an output).

The Cornell Studies considered both satisfaction and performance as outputs attributable to the interaction of other variables (i.e., both predictable from other variables), and expressed the view that performance may vary depending on aspects of the job. The general model of satisfaction developed and presented in the current effort described two outputs; satisfaction (or the extent to which expectations of the individual are met) and satisfactoriness (or the extent to which expectations of the organization are).

As additional research yields further insight concerning specific changes in job structures that are amenable to alteration within the operational employee system, offer recommendations as appropriate regarding job enrichment/enlargement for QSR's. Ultimately, the development of job enrichment guidelines for managers and supervisors may be feasible. However, the development of overall guidelines should be approached cautiously due to the possibility that the effects of application of job enrichment procedures may vary widely for different occupational career fields and different branches within the QSR industry.

Tenure was assumed to be a joint function of these two outputs. Thus, the present model does not ascribe fully to either the older view that performance is the consequence of satisfaction, or the more recent view that satisfaction is a function of performance. Rather, a more flexible framework or approach is attempted which permits the systematic inquiry of possible relationships between job satisfaction, performance, tenure, and other relevant variables.

Five significant reasons for the hospitality industry's turnover problem were pinpointed as follows (Mulliken, 1975):

- 1- "Poor hiring techniques
- 2- Inadequate orientation and training
- 3- Unsatisfactory hours and working conditions
- 4- Lack of opportunity for advancement
- 5- Ineffective or poor supervision"

(Mullike, 1975)

Some of the reasons appeared to be related to factors contributing to job satisfaction. Another survey by the Employee Relations Committee of American Hotel and Motel Associate (AHMA) reported and ranked the reasons for voluntary terminations (1973):

- 1- Rate of pay and/or benefits considered unsatisfactory
- 2- Employee or family relocates place of residence
- 3- Returns to school
- 4- Illness or injury
- 5- Returns to old job
- 6- Grievances are not heard or resolved
- 7- Job too difficult and demanding
- 8- Home responsibilities
- 9- Dislikes work hours and/or shift work
- 10- Job too uninteresting and not challenging
- 11- Dislikes or does not respect supervisor
- 12- Retired or pensioned
- 13- Progress on job and/or pay increments disappointing
- 14- Pregnant
- 15- Working conditions unpleasant
- 16- Marries; stops work
- 17- Lack of transportation
- 18- Military service
- 19- Overtime too heavy - beyond expectations

In the same survey the following reasons were given for involuntary terminations:

- 1- Excessive lateness or absenteeism
- 2- Misconduct or insubordination
- 3- Unsatisfactory work performance
- 4- Reduction of work force
- 5- Unsatisfactory work performance/unable to learn
- 6- Alcoholic or drug addiction
- 7- Not able to get along with co-workers
- 8- Promoted or transferred
- 9- Deceased
- 10- Unsatisfactory references from former employers

Reducing Turnover

Turnover could be reduced by several methods. Eisen (1982) suggested the following:

1. Hire and screen new employees as if a profitable operation depends on it. It does.
2. Orient new employees as if turnover control depends on it. It does.
3. Train employees as if payroll control depends on it. It does.
4. Promote employees from within as if it is a religion. It should be.
5. Terminate employees as if you are losing a friend. It need not happen.

Other reports suggested improved job satisfaction could help in reducing turnover (Brayfield and Crockett 1955; Roberts and Savage, 1973; McFillen, Riegel and Enz, 1986). Turnover is a serious problem for an organization if the rate is too high. It is controllable through careful planning of work and placement for employees.

McCleary and Weaver (1988) investigated the employment expectation of today's graduates of hospitality management related programs. The top three expectations were chance for promotion and growth, interesting work, and a chance for increasing responsibility. These items appeared to be closely related to factors contributing to job satisfaction.

Hofstede (1984) contended that an important aspect of quality of life is an individual's quality of work life. This explains the aspect why job challenge, achievement, and satisfaction at work are stressed in the United States. Blumenfeld et al. (1986) studied the job/career expectations of potential hospitality managers and found that type of work and advancement opportunities were the top ranked job attribute preferences of the Hotel and Restaurant Management students.

From the above studies, there appeared to be a relationship between career expectations and the job satisfaction factors of hospitality management program students. However, few studies have been conducted on the job satisfaction level of these program graduates and comparing this with the job satisfaction level of other hospitality industry workers who have no or little formal education background in hospitality management.

“Roberts and Savage (1973) contended that there are several reasons for measuring job satisfaction. First, there is growing concern about human as well as physical assets. Second, some studies implied that the higher the job satisfaction level is, the lower the turnover rate will be” (Roberts and Savage, 1973).

Therefore, if the job satisfaction of the hospitality industry workers can be measured, along with their formal education background, more confidence can be placed in predicting their

turnover possibilities. This can help the industry and the educator, to some degree, determine the effectiveness of these education programs.

“Another reason to determine the job satisfaction level of these program graduates is that job satisfaction is highly related to turnover (Brayfield and Crockett, 1955) which has always been one of the major problems in the hospitality industry.

The turnover rate of graduates newly entering the hospitality industry is significant. One reason for this seems to be that many people are attracted to the hospitality field without really knowing what they are getting into (Brayfield and Crockett, 1955). Once fully employed, they discover that they are not prepared for their jobs.

“They dislike the long hours, low pay rates, and physical labour associated with beginning jobs. They recognize too late that they must work during weekends, evenings, holidays, and at other times that most people are not required to work. Improved job satisfaction appeared to hold promise as the key factor in controlling turnover” (McFillen, et al., 1986). Cotton and Tuttle (1986) identified overall job satisfaction as a stable, reliable correlate of turnover.

In 14 or 15 studies covering a range of workers in different types of organizations, turnover was found to be higher when overall job dissatisfaction was higher (Bass and Ryterband, 1979). It can be further determined that there is a relationship between job satisfaction and turnover by a study which noted that increase in the job satisfaction was one of the factors that led to a reduction in turnover (Hulin, 1968).

Although job satisfaction cannot be defined as the only attribute which induces turnover at this point, it is no doubt that measuring and increasing job satisfaction play an important role in the attempt of controlling turnover. To get a clearer picture of how turnover affects the hospitality industry, several measurements have been done on turnover rate in this industry and in comparison, with other industries.

Employee turnover in the hospitality is estimated at approximately 60% (Wasmuth and Davis, 1983b), perhaps the highest of all industries. “Frelander and Pickle (1970), in a survey of six types of industry, found that food store and food service workers achieved the least satisfaction from their jobs. A recent report from the Hotel and Catering Industry Training Board also confirmed a high level of staff turnover in the industry. Gross turnover rates are identified as 55% for craftspeople, 65% for operatives and 94% for supervisors” (HCITB, 2016).

Recently, it has been identified that there is a 105% turnover rate industry wide for hourly employees and 46% for salaried workers. These figures demonstrate that controlling turnover is one of the main issues in this industry. Through the measurement of job satisfaction of future industry leaders, more preventive methods can be implemented before another person with RHIM background and potentiality quits his or her job.

Historically, probably Hoppock's (1935) text marks the first major attempt at summarizing job satisfaction research. About 20 years elapsed before the next major review by Brayfield and Crockett(1955) appeared, followed closely by the Herzberg, Mausner, Peterson, and Capwell (1957) review. From this point on, the amount of research tended to increase, with a concomitant increase in the frequency of literature reviews. In the mid-1960's, an interesting review appeared (Fournet, Di Stefano, & Pryer, 1966) which outlined some of the issues and problems encountered in job satisfaction research.

A report by Cummings and ElSalmi (1968) perhaps reflects a certain shifting of interest or change in emphasis towards "Managerial Motivation" or organizational' behaviour, although it does include the typically broader range of topics in job satisfaction research. However, a review by Schuh (1967) concerning tenure, which covered a wide range of sources, represented a trend towards a more specialized type of literature review. Another such specialized review regarding turnover and absenteeism was provided by Porter and Steers (1972). These authors state that about four more specific turnover and absenteeism literature reviews have been published, with three out of date (Brayfield & Crockett, 1955; Herzberg et al., 1957; and Vroom, 1964) and the one by Schuh (1967).

Another research by Ronan (1970) when compared to the one by Fournet et al., (1966), reveals that many recurrent issues and problems are still unresolved (e.g., dimensions or criteria of job satisfaction, methods of measurement, relation of satisfaction, and performance). However, there are other indications that perhaps job satisfaction research is progressing in an upward spiral direction. For example, there was more attention given to theoretical studies and the belief that satisfaction is the result of the complex interaction of many variables. In an optimistic view, Ronan (1970) contends that certain invariant dimensions of job satisfaction have been isolated, and the bases of job satisfaction differ for various occupational groups. Such examples may be indicative of substantial progress in the area.

Legal Factors

Legal factors are another issue that managers face in quick service restaurants. An example for it is today in many developed countries including the US and the UK there are laws requiring restaurant to clearly specify the calorie counts of the food on their menu. Therefore, managers in fast-food restaurants must adjust themselves with such laws and make them accessible as fast and efficient as possible. Some of these legal laws might even result in a complete transformation of the way some of these quick service restaurants operate which makes it a challenge for their managers.

Business Climate

Fast-food restaurants can be affected by both economic climate and business climate which is a wide-ranging cultural attitude toward fast foods. For example, campaigns such as eating healthy and food safety are business climates that could affect the image of QSRs. Therefore, managers should come up with different strategies to deal with issues such as this and maintain their company image by distancing themselves from practices that cause negative advertising. For example, when Jack in the Box restaurants were caught up in an E. coli outbreak in 1993, other fast-food chains needed to assure consumers that their stores were cooking meat to safe temperatures (QSR, 2010).

Internal pressures

Often in fast-food restaurants managers should deal with a large traffic of customers, inventory and staff cost control and other concerns about profitability which does not occur in most of the full-service restaurants. It is difficult for managers to control how many employees they need at different times of the day because the flow of consumers to the store at different times is unpredictable. Additionally, fast-food restaurants have limited offerings in their food therefore managers face limitations to modify the menu.

Fast-food restaurants are generally low in price thus managers must manage the store with a thin profit margin, therefore managing the inventory and labour cost is essential for quick service restaurants.

Recommendations for Future Research

Throughout the research several recommendations for future studies have been mentioned. Some of the important recommendations are to take advantage of a larger geographical area as well as a larger sample size while conducting the survey. It is also beneficial to use a mixed method of data collection like quantitative and qualitative in the same study to have a deeper and more measurable data to analyse. It is not possible to fully understand the customer's decision-making process just by conducting quantitative data. Therefore, the mixed method would help to enhance our understanding of the reasoning behind their decisions and perceptions.

Covid-19 and future pandemics

“With the international spread of Covid-19 pandemic, the fragility of supply chain and distribution network in the economic globalization comes to be noticeable. In the past, with the worldwide supply chain, international corporations such Subway could organize manufacturing and sales around the world to reduce the price of manufacturing by making use of their comparative benefits.

Thanks to the incorporated procedures and quick reaction at the supply chain, those global fast-food business, such as Subway appreciates comfort as well as transparency when they coordinate their products, details, and values.

Nonetheless, the outbreak of pandemic hindered Subway system, and numerous governments took a lot more rigid actions of control in regards to the transportation as well as the flow of people. In the era of financial globalization, the global division of labour ends up being even more challenging, and business at the global supply chain as well as value chain are creating closer relationships with each other.

The torpidity of production in one nation will certainly affect the whole industrial chain, so the stalled procedure of globalization is among huge difficulties that face Subway.

Either in regards to food expense, transport expenditures, rent or wages, Subway will lose its benefits in the process of globalization prior to the outbreak of a pandemic.

Concurrently, various federal governments released decrees controlling the import and export commodities or established limits on the departure and entry, and all these procedures are not good news for Subway procedure.

Basic economic sectors are dealing with direct impact in several countries because of the spread of pandemic worldwide. The global intake, investment and profession are impeded, and the international aggregate need is shrinking. Subway is no exemption, as the household consumption is directly impacted by the quarantine measures. Those customers that liked to dine in Subway restaurants prior to the pandemic needed to comply with the government orders and stay inside.

At the same time, with the influence of pandemic, the locals felt pessimistic concerning the employment opportunities and earnings in the future. Consequently, the consumer's confidence indicators are declining substantially, and the decline level is close to that throughout the economic crisis of 2008. Because of these factors, the number of Subway customers declining drastically” (Chen, 2020)

“Given that the breakout of Covid-19 pandemic, there is a large concern among the customers of fast-food restaurants regarding the future. Employees are afraid of losing their jobs, getting infected or robbed by the rioters, and all these issues would certainly reduce people's eating behaviours, as they began to deposit money. Because of wide lockdown in service market is enforced by the government, lots of individuals who are helping restaurants, cinemas and shopping malls are losing their job.

Therefore, their income expectation and self-confidence in the economy are showing downward trend. This phenomenon will be exceptionally harmful to the fast-food business such as Subway, when their potential customers become worried about their futures and begin to deposit money.

Additionally, it is well known that fast food store such as Subway is a crowded area where individuals sit near to each other and share their foods, which makes the shop a high-risk area for virus transmission” (Chen, 2020).

Therefore, future studies could be done on global pandemics and their effects on fast-food restaurants and should provide solutions and recommendations about how to keep the business operational and avoid profit loss during the pandemics.

CONCLUSION

After reviewing the literature in this field, the researcher has noticed that there is insufficient or missing information about factors affecting the performance of Subway as a Quick Service Restaurant. Therefore, this study aimed to fill the gap in that area by identifying the most important factors affecting the performance of Subway in London by conducting a conclusive research and with the help of quantitative data collection method.

In short as explained throughout this study, “research into consumer behaviour typically deals with antecedents such as product/service attitudes or consumers’ stated intentions to repurchase. However, the correlation between intention and action may be quite small, and generally includes other factors (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975)”.

Additionally, “sociological, and anthropological views of eating out bring a fresh set of assumptions concerning the act and role of consumption. people rationality, choice, contentment and intent, the keystones of marketing psychology, are here replaced by social pressures of fashion, power relationships, rationalised service, and indicators.

Researchers in this field deal with the exact same overarching issue as all that seek to understand the meal experience, that the complexity of customers' behaviour appears to conceal the simple terms in which they define the experience” (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975).

As discussed, Health concerns over fast foods has increased in the coming years. However, calorie labelling could help to reduce these concerns by educating the customers about the amount of calorie each food contains. Although Subway is among the healthiest fast-food options in the market, health issues still negatively affect the performance of QSR's because the perception of fast-food is generally negative and customers have become more health conscious in the recent years. Subway is currently offering calorie labelling in all their branches throughout the UK but as shown in the previous studies, product labelling has very little influence on consumption, however, after training around it the results improved drastically. Therefore, to tackle this issue it is recommended that Subway should communicate and advertise more frequently about calorie consumption and their effects on our overall health.

Every business is trying to find methods of keeping existing customers and attract new ones while continuing to be affordable and rewarding. As customers today have much more options than in the past, they are eager to try new foods and experience new opportunities.

Therefore, with the fast growth of QSR's, companies are facing new challenges and dealing

with a new target audience in this industry. It is said that effective marketing methods cannot be developed without firstly, analysing the environment in which the company operates. As analysed in this study, several uncontrollable aspects influence Subway's internal and external approaches as well as tactical application.

These groups of components consist of the PESTLE (political, economic, social, technological, legal, as well as environmental), framework of the marketplace and competitors being dealt with (Porter's 5 forces evaluation), evaluation of its stakeholders, customers, as well as product adaptation within its internationalisation technique, BCG matrix, Value Chain as well as VIRO evaluation. All these facets are vital to a business's decision making. The degree of comprehending that exists in these connections will certainly establish the success of a business.

“Aside from the costs involved, employee turnover can also affect employees’ morale and productivity(Huffman, Payne, & Casper, 2013)”. Moreover, “When employee turnover occurs, employee performance productivity decreases. Employee turnover can disrupt the core business operations especially when the high performers leave, where business success depends on them (Tzabbar & Kehoe, 2014)”. Kwon and Rupp (2013) “agreed stating that high performers leave the organization regardless of pay and benefits received from the organization” (Kwon and Rupp, 2013).Additionally, Hancock et al. (2013) “employee turnover does not affect the organizational performance directly. To reduce employee turnover costs financially and non-financially, managers must focus on factors that increase employee motivation and job satisfaction” (Hancock et al., 2013).

“It is generally believed that high job satisfaction will result in higher performance, better attendance, reduced turnover, and increased willingness to work with others. On the other hand, low job satisfaction is usually related to lower performance and increased turnover. To illustrate further. Herzberg recommended job enrichment as the practice of building satisfier factors into job content (i.e., increasing job satisfaction)” (Herzberg, 1959).

Each principle was an action guideline and it reflected increased job depth by allowing subordinates to share in work planning, evaluating responsibilities and in actual task accomplishment.

As discussed in the literature review and further investigated and analysed, the four most important issues that stops Subway from getting to the top are, Consumer Preferences, Health Issues, Internal and External Pressures and Employee Turnover.

As demonstrated in the survey findings there is a significant relationship between turnover with satisfaction and achievement/quality performance, recognition, work itself, responsibility and advancement and growth. As seen above there is a significant relationship between all these variables. It shows that as satisfaction in these factors increases, the turnover within that job decreases. Most of this is in line with the Herzberg's theory (1959), he concluded that as satisfaction factors like advancement and growth in the job increases, the turnover decreases.

In addition, As demonstrated in the survey, there is a significant relationship between turnover with dissatisfaction and company policy, supervision, interpersonal relationship, working conditions, and salary. It shows that as dissatisfaction in these factors in the job increases, the turnover within that job increases too. This is in line with the Misra's theory (2013), and she concluded that as dissatisfaction in working conditions in the job increases, the turnover within that job increases too and Dike's theory (2012), he concluded that as dissatisfaction in the job increases, the turnover within that job increases as well.

Also as demonstrated by the second survey, the important criteria for customers who participated is the quality and taste of the food. Followed by the location of the restaurant, the cleanliness, and the hygiene. It was also mentioned that the service quality, the variety in menu and the speed of service is important for them. Based on this result, it is safe to assume that QSR suppliers mainly should focus on these areas. Although most customers revealed that they are overall satisfied with the quality and service given by these restaurants, the outcome evidently demonstrates that eating is not the only reason they visit these outlets, they also want to enjoy and meet with their friends and family. When they were asked what enhancements, they would love to see, most customers stated they want to see more selections of healthier food options therefore health concerns as expected is essential in this industry and could affect the performance of Subway. In addition, enhancing the seating area, indication of the nutritional value of items, improved food selection range and vegetarian choices are additionally crucial for customers.

In conclusion all the hypotheses have been accepted and found to be negatively affecting the performance of Subway in London, United Kingdom. Therefore, it is recommended that Subway take these issues under consideration in order to fulfil their desire of becoming the **#1 QSR worldwide**.

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Appendix A: Job Satisfaction Survey

	PLEASE CIRCLE THE ONE NUMBER FOR EACH QUESTION THAT COMES CLOSEST TO REFLECTING YOUR OPINION ABOUT IT.	Disagree very much Disagree moderately Disagree slightly Agree slightly Agree moderately Agree very much
1	I feel I am being paid a fair amount for the work I do.	1 2 3 4 5 6
2	There is really too little chance for promotion on my job.	1 2 3 4 5 6
3	My supervisor is quite competent in doing his/her job.	1 2 3 4 5 6
4	I am not satisfied with the benefits I receive.	1 2 3 4 5 6

5	When I do a good job, I receive the recognition for it that I should receive.	1	2	3	4	5	6
6	Many of our rules and procedures make doing a good job difficult.	1	2	3	4	5	6
7	I like the people I work with.	1	2	3	4	5	6
8	I sometimes feel my job is meaningless.	1	2	3	4	5	6
9	Communications seem good within this organization.	1	2	3	4	5	6
10	Raises are too few and far between.	1	2	3	4	5	6
11	Those who do well on the job stand a fair chance of being promoted.	1	2	3	4	5	6
12	My supervisor is unfair to me.	1	2	3	4	5	6
13	The benefits we receive are as good as most other organizations offer.	1	2	3	4	5	6
14	I do not feel that the work I do is appreciated.	1	2	3	4	5	6
15	My efforts to do a good job are seldom blocked by red tape.	1	2	3	4	5	6
16	I find I have to work harder at my job because of the incompetence of people I	1	2	3	4	5	6

	work with.	
17	I like doing the things I do at work.	1 2 3 4 5 6
18	The goals of this organization are not clear to me.	1 2 3 4 5 6

	PLEASE CIRCLE THE ONE NUMBER FOR EACH QUESTION THAT COMES CLOSEST TO REFLECTING YOUR OPINION ABOUT IT.	
		Disagree very much Disagree moderately Disagree slightly Agree slightly Agree moderately Agree very much
19	I feel unappreciated by the organization when I think about what they pay me.	1 2 3 4 5 6
20	People get ahead as fast here as they do in other places.	1 2 3 4 5 6
21	My supervisor shows too little interest in the feelings of subordinates.	1 2 3 4 5 6
22	The benefit package we have is equitable.	1 2 3 4 5 6

23	There are few rewards for those who work here.	1	2	3	4	5	6
24	I have too much to do at work.	1	2	3	4	5	6
25	I enjoy my coworkers.	1	2	3	4	5	6
26	I often feel that I do not know what is going on with the organization.	1	2	3	4	5	6
27	I feel a sense of pride in doing my job.	1	2	3	4	5	6
28	I feel satisfied with my chances for salary increases.	1	2	3	4	5	6
29	The benefit package we have is equitable.	1	2	3	4	5	6
30	I like my supervisor.	1	2	3	4	5	6
31	I have too much paperwork.	1	2	3	4	5	6
32	I don't feel my efforts are rewarded the way they should be.	1	2	3	4	5	6
33	I am satisfied with my chances for promotion.	1	2	3	4	5	6
34	There is too much bickering and fighting at work.	1	2	3	4	5	6
35	My job is enjoyable.	1	2	3	4	5	6
36	Work assignments are not fully explained	1	2	3	4	5	6

Appendix B: Turnover Intention to Leave the Job Scale

1.....	2.....	3.....	4.....	5
Certainly Not	Probably Not	Not sure	Probably	Certainly

- | | | | | | |
|---|-----------|---|-----------|---|---|
| | Certainly | | Certainly | | |
| | not | | | | |
| 1. What are the chances that you will remain in the profession but leave the organization at or before the end of the year? | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |
| 2. What are the chances that you will leave your job | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |

Appendix C: Demographic Questions

The following statements are for demographical classification only. Please check one response per statement.

Gender (Please Check One): Male Female

Age (Please Check One): 18-28 years 29-39 years 40-50 years 51-61 years 62-72 years

Educational Attainment (Please Check One): High school Vocational Undergraduate(1-3) Bachelor degree Others

Current Position (Please Check One): Cashier(Drive thru/Front line) Runner (Counter and drive thru) Fry person Meats person Initiator Assembler Others

Job classification (Please Check One): Part-time Full time

Years of working with current (Please Check One): 5 years 10 years 15 years 20 years

Would like to view results of survey yes no. If yes, send to

Appendix D: Customer survey

Evaluation of consumer perception within fast food industry

Welcome!

Thank you for agreeing to take part in this important survey!

Your thoughts and opinions are valuable contribution towards evaluating consumer perception & customer satisfaction within fast food industry. The survey should only take 2-3 minutes to complete. Be assured all the information provided will be kept in the strictest confidentiality. Please, proceed to questions.

What is your age?

- 18-25 26-35 36-45 46+

Please, state your gender:

- Male Female

What is your occupation?

- Full-time employed Unemployed Pensioner
 Part-time employed Student

How often do you visit a fast food restaurant?

- daily 1 or 2 times a week
 3 or more times a week 1 or 2 times a month

Which of the following influence your restaurant choice the most?

- Friends Family Other _____
 Children Advertising/Media

How important are the following criteria to you for selecting a restaurant?

	Not Important			Very Important	
	1	2	3	4	5
Price	☐				
Service Speed	☐				
Quality & Taste of food	☐				
Location of a restaurant	☐				
Quality of a service	☐				
Cleanliness/Hygiene	☐				
Menu Variety	☐				
Ambience/Interior	☐				
Brand Name/Reputation of a restaurant	☐				

What is your reason for dining at fast food restaurant?

- Friends get together
 For fun
 Family outing
 For change
 For convenience
 Other _____

How satisfied are you with the following criteria?

	Not Satisfied	Neutral	Satisfied
Price	☐	☐	☐
Service Speed	☐	☐	☐
Quality & Taste of food	☐	☐	☐
Location of a restaurant	☐	☐	☐
Quality of a service	☐	☐	☐
Cleanliness/Hygiene	☐	☐	☐
Menu Variety	☐	☐	☐
Ambience/Interior	☐	☐	☐
Brand Name/Reputation of a restaurant	☐	☐	☐

Overall, I am satisfied with my dining experience at fast food restaurant & my expectations are met.

- Strongly Disagree Neither Agree nor Disagree Strongly Agree
 Somewhat Disagree Somewhat Agree

How would you evaluate the value of your transaction?

- Value worth more
 Value worth equal
 Value worth less

What improvements would you like to see in the future?

Note: You can select more than one option

- Improved Seating Space
 Indication of nutritional value of items
 Increased variety of menu items
 More choices of healthier menu items
 Ethnic/Local food
 Increased number of service (for ex. Home delivery)
 Other _____

Personal Values

There are four main reasons for the researcher to choose this topic:

- 1- Planning to get into a franchise business after graduation personally.
- 2- Very interested to invest in Subway franchise here in the UK.
- 3- It is relatively cheaper to purchase a Subway franchise than rest of the Quick Service Restaurants.
- 4- It is beneficial to research on a related field of interest for future investment.

Redacted due to copyright restrictions.

Source: franchisegrade.com

Chart by FitSmallBusiness.com

Related Personal achievements

To better understand the nature of the business the researcher has started working at Subway from the September of 2017 in London to gain more insight and experience about the operation and the ways they conduct their business as well as to understand how the employees are treated and what customers really care about when they visit the stores.

In addition, the researcher has enrolled in numerous courses at Subway University to understand the core values of the business.